

CATALISI

Catalysation of institutional transformations
of Higher Education Institutions through
the adoption of acceleration services

D3.3 - PREDICTIVE STUDY
31/07/2024

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Authors	Suhida Dermanni (EY); Ioana Gabriela Doleanu (EY); Matteo Di Rosa (EY);
Editors	Matteo Di Rosa (EY); Rrap Kryeziu (EY)
Reviewers	Matteo Di Rosa (EY); Maria Carmela Fierro (APRE), Laura Mentini (APRE), Stefania Laneve (APRE)
Abstract	This study presents a critical analysis of the transversal skills gap among young researchers (R1 and R2) within European Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) and the evolving demands of the labour market. Utilizing a mixed-methods approach, including online surveys, in-depth interviews, and advanced text mining of job postings, the research assesses the proficiency of researchers in key competencies and compares these to employer expectations
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#	Participant Organisation Name	Short Name	Country
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2	EY ADVISORY SPA	EY	ITALY
3	F6S NETWORK IRELAND LIMITED	F6S	IRELAND
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5	KAUNO TECHNOLOGIJOS UNIVERSITETAS	KTU	LITHUANIA
6	UNIVERSITAT JAUME I DE CASTELLON	UJI	SPAIN
7	LUISS LIBERA UNIVERSITA INTERNAZIONALE DEGLI STUDI SOCIALI GUIDO CARLI	LUISS	ITALY
8	UNIWERSYTET GDANSKI	UG	POLAND
9	UNIVERSITY COLLEGE CORK - NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF IRELAND, CORK	UCC	IRELAND
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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

CATALISI project is a **Horizon Europe** project aimed at **fostering** institutional **transformations** within **Higher Education Institutions** (HEIs) by leveraging **innovative acceleration services**. Its primary goal is to **enhance** the **capabilities** of HEIs in promoting interdisciplinary collaborations and increasing the societal impact of research. This initiative is part of a broader effort to strengthen **European university networks** and promote **European values** and driving excellence in research and education. By addressing disparities in research and innovation performance, CATALISI aims to create a **cohesive** and **competitive** higher education environment across Europe.

The **predictive study** on skills anticipation has been meant in CATALISI as **acceleration service** to be implemented to generate an effective **competence development** system and make capacity building activities sustainable over time. The aim of the study is to offer new **analytical tools** to support universities in rethinking investments in education and training as medium to long term investments for the recovery of competitive capacity in the Higher Education sector. The study also focuses on the **changes** occurring within **academic** and labour **market landscapes**. As these fields continue to evolve, there is a critical need for **young researchers (R1 and R2)** to develop and enhance their skill sets, particularly in transversal competencies. These skills are essential for fostering interdisciplinary collaborations and ensuring that research has a meaningful societal impact.

The study emphasizes the need for Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) to **modernize** their doctoral training programs to better prepare young researchers for the challenges and opportunities of the future.

The study's methodology employs a **mixed-methods approach**, combining online surveys, in-depth interviews, and advanced text mining techniques to analyse job postings. The **online surveys**, conducted with young researchers (R1 and R2) (The study includes data from **843 young researchers**) provide quantitative data on self-assessed skill levels and qualitative insights into the perceived adequacy of current training programs. The **in-depth interviews** with academic stakeholders, including vice rectors of research, offer valuable qualitative insights into the effectiveness of current training and the challenges in developing these skills. Furthermore, the **job crawling technique** used to analyse job postings identifies the most sought-after transversal skills across different sectors. This comprehensive approach ensures a robust understanding of the current and **future transversal skills requirements** for researchers, offering actionable insights for universities, policymakers, and researchers to better align training with labour market demands.

The findings of the study reveal that researchers exhibit **strong cognitive abilities** and **proficiency in conducting research**, which are fundamental for their roles. However, they show notable **deficiencies** in areas such as interdisciplinary collaboration, project management, and ensuring research impact. The study highlights that while researchers are confident in their technical skills, they often lack the necessary **interpersonal and managerial competencies** that are increasingly valued in both academic and non-academic settings. This gap is further evidenced by self-assessment scores, which indicate low proficiency in **emotional intelligence, team dynamics**, and the **integration of Open Science principles**.

The study also emphasizes the growing importance of **transversal skills** in the future landscape of research and innovation. It forecasts that skills related to open innovation, policy engagement, and interdisciplinary research will become increasingly critical. Researchers will need to **enhance** their capabilities in these areas to remain **competitive** in the job market. Emerging trends indicate that digital competencies, entrepreneurial skills, and the ability to manage intellectual property effectively will be essential for researchers to navigate the evolving demands of both academic and industrial sectors. These findings align with **European policy initiatives** such as the Digital Competence Framework for Citizens and the European Skills Agenda, which emphasize the development of digital and entrepreneurial skills.

From the analyses of the study and in particular from the interviews, both experts from academia and third sector have emphasized that **collaboration among researchers** from different areas of expertise is increasingly necessary to meet new **societal challenges**. As societal problems become more complex, their solution requires the exchange of knowledge to foster innovation and ensure societal impact. In this context, interpersonal competencies are highly valued. In particular, in addition to communication abilities, experts have mentioned competencies pertaining to emotional intelligence, necessitating individuals to be flexible, open-minded to diverse perspectives, and to embrace diversity. However, evidence shows important **deficiencies** in these areas. Academic experts have underlined that **working in teams** is an area that is overlooked in doctoral training, whereas third-sector and industry experts have pointed out situations where these deficiencies have led to strained relationships among colleagues, highly impacting the overall work and results of the team. This underqualification is evident when also looking at **self-assessment scores**. Self-assessment scores emphasize that researchers self-assess proficiency in working in teams, underlying that researchers contribute effectively to team dynamics and coordinate well for an efficient workflow. However, self-assessment is notably **low** regarding the abilities to conduct **interdisciplinary research, integrate different data and results from interdisciplinary research, and conduct interdisciplinary projects**. Similarly, low scores are found in relation to ensuring well-being at work and promoting inclusion and diversity.

In addition to capabilities related to **working with others, self-planning and management** are fundamental. Nonetheless, experts from both academia and the labour market have underlined that researchers often **lack capabilities** related to project and time management. This lack is also confirmed by self-assessment scores in **planning and self-organization**, where researchers face struggles in maintaining optimal organization and meeting deadlines. Moreover, the score for **managing projects** indicates that researchers exhibit **difficulties in effectively planning and allocating resources** for their research projects.

Another important area of **underqualification** pertains to ensuring that research has an **impact**. This issue is particularly pronounced within academia, where experts have emphasized that researchers face significant barriers in communicating their research to a broader audience. The lack of these competencies is especially evident in self-assessment scores, which reveal significant deficiencies in **communicating research findings** to the public, as well as in promoting **citizen science** and **open innovation**.

The importance of transversal skills cannot be overstated. Young researchers with strong transversal skills hold a **competitive advantage** over those who lack these competencies, as these skills are crucial in differentiating candidates during the recruitment process and enhancing their career prospects. The advantage of transversal skills is particularly significant in the rapidly evolving work environment, where technical skills can quickly become outdated. In this context, **lifelong learning** becomes essential, requiring motivation, an open-minded attitude, flexibility, and adaptability to adapt to new developments. These traits are increasingly considered in hiring decisions, with self-motivation and the ability to adapt being key factors in career growth. Despite strong technical proficiency, individuals may face career setbacks or even dismissal if they are deemed unsuitable for the team dynamic or long-term organizational goals. Finally, strong competences in areas related to **cognitive abilities, promoting open innovation, and enhancing and maintain networks** with external stakeholders are key in ensuring that projects are innovative and **effective in solving complex problems**.

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The predictive analysis reveals that both **researchers** and **employers** expect a **shift** in the importance of **research competencies** over the next **five years**. The focus is moving towards **impact-driven, collaborative, and technology-supported** skills, with a **decrease** in the emphasis on **traditional cognitive** and **self-management** skills. This suggests a more **collaborative research** approach and **stronger institutional support systems**. Young researchers are gearing up for roles that prioritize **societal impact, interdisciplinary project management, and navigating technology-rich environments**, emphasizing skills like **science communication, policy influence, and societal engagement**.

Employers highlight the need to **adaptable training programs** and continuous dialogue with researchers to align competencies with evolving market demands.

Competency gaps are primarily explained by the challenges faced by HEIs in effectively integrating **appropriate training** into doctoral programs. One major challenge is the strong **resistance** to incorporating programs necessary for developing new competencies, including **both transversal skills and training related to Open Science principles**. This resistance is reflected in either the absence of such training from the programs or a lack of engagement from researchers even when these programs are included. Additionally, a significant challenge is ensuring that the training is effective and assessing the development of transversal skills.

To address these **anticipated needs**, the study recommends several strategic actions for HEIs. First, HEIs should integrate advanced digital skills training into their doctoral programs, focusing on areas such as **data analytics, artificial intelligence, and digital communication tools** to prepare researchers for the **future digital landscape**. This integration is important for equipping researchers with technical expertise needed to handle complex data and leverage digital platforms effectively.

Implementing training programs that foster **entrepreneurial thinking** and **innovation management** will enable researchers to commercialize their findings and engage in market-oriented activities. This entrepreneurial approach is essential for translating academic research into practical applications that benefit society and drive economic growth.

HEIs should encourage **interdisciplinary projects** and collaborations, ensuring researchers can **effectively work across various fields and disciplines**. This approach fosters a holistic problem-solving mindset, allowing researchers to tackle complex societal challenges with comprehensive and innovative solutions.

Furthermore, training young researchers (R1 and R2) to engage with **policy frameworks** and embrace **open innovation** will ensure their work aligns with societal needs and policy directions. This alignment is crucial for maximizing the societal impact of research and ensuring that academic contributions are relevant and impactful in addressing **contemporary issues**.

These recommendations aim to bridge the **current skill gaps** identified in the study and ensure that young researchers are well-equipped for the evolving research environment. By implementing these strategies, HEIs can **enhance the career prospects** of young researchers and increase the overall impact of their work, fostering a more **skilled, adaptable, and innovative research community**.

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ABBREVIATIONS

D	Deliverable
DoA	Description of Action
EU	European Union
T	Task
WP	Work-Package
GA	Grant Agreement
CA	Consortium Agreement
DC	Dissemination and Communication
LL	Living Labs
SME	Small and Medium Enterprise
CoP	Community of Practice
AI	Artificial Intelligence
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
ERA	European Research Area
HEI	Higher Education Institutions

1. PROJECT INTRODUCTION

1.1. CATALISI BACKGROUND AND AIM

Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) in the EU have been recognized for their global leadership in the fields of research and innovation (R&I). In order to maximize research impact and institutional transformation, HEIs need to strengthen their European University collaborations.

By bridging the gap between HEIs disparities in terms of R&I performance, HEIs can navigate and cooperate in the production and dissemination of high-quality knowledge to maximize the value of research and its impact within the region.

CATALISI model focus on three main domains (Research careers and talent support, Open science and public engagement, and Sustainable research and education) intersected by seven acceleration services (Living Labs, Design Lab for transformational pathway, Counselling, **Reinforce human capital – capacity building**, **Predictive study on skills anticipation**, **Marketplace**, and **Community of Practice (CoP)**), which are designed to facilitate and catalyse the process of institutional transformation.

The aim of CATALISI is to help and support Higher Education Institutions to successfully implement strategies and individual pathways for institutional transformation through the adoption of acceleration services.

These are designed to facilitate and accelerate institutional transformations in the field of Research and Innovation which will strengthen European Universities collaborations and alliances as lighthouses of European values.

1.2. INTRODUCTION

In today's rapidly changing world, the skills of young researchers (R1 and R2) are becoming increasingly important, reflecting the evolving demands of both academic and non-academic fields. Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) in the European Union (EU) have long been known for their excellence in research and innovation. To continue their leadership, these institutions must adapt to the changing landscape of research careers and the skills needed in the job market.

A key focus of the CATALISI project is improving transversal competencies among early career researchers. **Transversal competencies, which include both soft and technical skills, are valuable across various sectors.** They consist of knowledge, skills, and attitudes, as defined by the European Commission in the ResearchComp framework¹. This framework categorizes competencies into areas like cognitive abilities, self-management, teamwork, research execution, research management, research tool management, and impact creation.

¹ https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/jobs-research/researchcomp-european-competence-framework-researchers_en

Conducted from September 2023 to May 2024, this study includes a European context, which is crucial for capturing the diverse research landscape across EU member states. The European dimension fosters collaboration and knowledge exchange among HEIs, enabling the identification and sharing of best practices, and it supports the goals of the European Research Area (ERA) by promoting harmonized research training and career development policies, enhancing researchers' mobility and employability within the EU.

The study particularly focuses on early career researchers classified as R1 and R2. The R1 category includes PhD candidates who are at the beginning stages of their research careers. These individuals are primarily engaged in their PhD studies and are building the foundational skills necessary for conducting independent research. They often require significant training and support in both technical and transversal skills to prepare them for future research roles. The R2 category includes researchers with postdoctoral experience who have completed their PhD studies and are in the early stages of their independent research careers. These researchers have already demonstrated their ability to conduct research independently but still require further development to refine their skills and competencies. R2 researchers often take on more complex research projects and begin to establish their professional networks and collaborations.

Addressing the specific needs of R1 and R2 researchers is crucial for fostering a pathway of skilled researchers who can thrive in various sectors. By tailoring training and support to the unique challenges and developmental stages of these researchers, the CATALISI project aims to enhance their competencies, improve their career prospects, and contribute to the broader goals of the European Research Area (ERA).

The study has two objectives. The primary objective is to **assess the current level of transversal skills of young researchers** (R1 and R2) and compare these skills to the requirements posted on various job platforms. This enables us to create recommendations to improve the curriculum, ensuring that PhD students are better prepared for the labour market. The study **analyses 820 young researchers (R1 & R2)** from diverse academic disciplines, enrolled in higher education institutions across the European Union. As part of assessing the current level of transversal skills among **young researchers**, we also engage with 50 high-level administrators of higher education institutions. We discuss, through semi-structured interviews the existing curriculum and their approaches to developing transversal skills for students in various fields. This will provide us with a better understanding of the institutional perspective on soft skill development and help identify potential areas for improvement. The data collection process involves both online surveys and in-depth interviews, allowing us to gain a comprehensive understanding of the participants' current transversal skills and experiences. This information is compared with an in-depth analysis of job postings on various platforms, targeting positions that are relevant to PhD graduates. This helps us identify the most in-demand transversal skills required by employers in different sectors. The study allows us to pinpoint different groups of transversal skills required for job seekers with a PhD across various sectors. This information is invaluable in tailoring recommendations for curriculum improvements that cater to the unique needs of PhD students, preparing them for diverse career paths in academia, industry and other sectors.

The second aim is to **build a tool to anticipate the future competences for young researchers** (R1 and R2). This is crucial as it addresses the dynamic and rapidly evolving demands of both the academic and industrial job markets. By actively identifying and

preparing for these future skills, the tool ensures that young researchers remain competitive and adaptable, enhancing their employability and effectiveness in various sectors. This strategic perspective not only helps bridge the current skills gap identified in the study but also supports the continuous alignment of research training with industry needs, fostering innovation and facilitating the successful integration of researchers into diverse career paths. Moreover, the study provides invaluable insights for universities, enabling them to make informed investments in training programs for young researchers (R1 and R2), fostering innovation and ensuring the successful integration of researchers into diverse career paths.

This report, based on thorough research and analysis, aims to provide a clear understanding of the current state of transversal competences and the mismatching demands. It serves as a guide for stakeholders in academia, industry, and policy-making, offering detailed insights into the present skills landscape and future competency needs. As knowledge and innovation become ever more critical, the role of early career researchers is essential. With the academic and industrial landscapes continually evolving, so must the skills and competencies of those at the forefront of discovery and development.

1.3. STRUCTURE OF THE DELIVERABLE

Structured in a logical and reader-friendly format, the study unfolds in **six distinct chapters**, each addressing a key aspect of the skills and competencies ecosystem, which are presented here below. From the introduction of the CATALISI project to the methodologies employed, and from the current skills landscape to the anticipated future trends, this document is designed to inform, enlighten, and inspire action towards the development of a robust and adaptable research workforce.

Chapter 1: Introduction

This chapter introduces the CATALISI project, explaining its goals and the importance of enhancing collaboration among European HEIs. It also provides an overview of the study's structure, offering a roadmap to guide readers through its main sections.

Chapter 2: Conceptual Framework

In this chapter the study explores the evolving career paths for doctoral graduates and the growing significance of diverse skills. This chapter also explores how aligning skills with European research policies is crucial. It reviews various European initiatives aimed at promoting skills development for researchers, highlighting the necessity of transversal skills for achieving research excellence. Additionally, we analyze existing competence frameworks, identifying gaps and areas for improvement, and summarize past research on transversal skills development, emphasizing the need to align student and employer perceptions.

Chapter 3: Methodology

The Methodology chapter details the survey methods used to assess transversal skills among early career researchers. It describes the semi-structured interviews conducted with academic and industry stakeholders to gather insights on transversal skills. The text mining methodology used to analyze job postings for PhD-preferred roles is explained, identifying

key skills in demand. This chapter outlines how we combined academic and labor market data to forecast future transversal skills requirements.

Chapter 4: Findings: Current Landscape (AS IS)

Current Landscape (AS IS) presents the demographic data and self-assessments of transversal competencies among European researchers. This chapter identifies gaps in current university programs based on survey feedback, highlighting areas needing additional training. It analyzes interviews with academic stakeholders to pinpoint essential transversal skills and training gaps, discussing the difficulties academia faces in integrating these skills into training programs. Strategies for effectively incorporating transversal skills into academic curricula are also explored. Additionally, we analyze interviews with industry representatives to understand employer expectations and examine job postings to identify the most sought-after transversal skills for PhD-preferred roles.

Chapter 5: Findings: Future Landscape (TO BE)

This chapter forecasts the transversal competencies that will be essential for researchers in the near future and predicts the skills researchers will need over the next decade. This chapter identifies other important skills that will be relevant in the future and presents academic perspectives on the future skills required for researchers. We summarize the key skills that will be crucial, integrating insights from various data sources, and providing industry insights on future skills requirements and trends.

Chapter 6: Conclusion and Discussion

The final chapter of this study synthesizes the findings from the previous chapters to offer actionable recommendations for early career researchers, academic institutions, industry stakeholders, and policymakers. These recommendations are designed to ensure that the skills and competencies of researchers are aligned with the evolving demands of the labor market and the broader research ecosystem.

2. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

In this chapter, we explore the shifting career trajectories of doctoral graduates, transitioning from traditional academic roles to diversified positions across sectors, emphasizing the need to develop transversal skills aligned with European research policies. We address the challenges and opportunities associated for example with Open Science and the role of European policy initiatives in fostering skill development. Additionally, we analyze the importance of aligning competencies with the European Framework for Researcher Development, ResearchComp, highlighting how these skills are essential for tackling contemporary societal challenges and contributing effectively in both academic and non-academic settings.

2.1 SHIFTING CAREER TRAJECTORIES: THE EVOLVING EMPLOYMENT LANDSCAPE FOR DOCTORAL GRADUATES

The employment landscape for doctoral graduates has undergone a significant transformation over the past two decades. Traditionally, doctoral graduates primarily aimed for academic careers, aspiring to secure positions as professors or researchers within universities. However, recent data indicate a **considerable shift towards non-academic careers**, driven by a combination of factors including limited availability of stable academic positions and the evolving demands of the labour market.

Eurostat data ²shows that as of 2021, there were **2 million full-time equivalent researchers in the EU**, an increase of 627,000 since 2011. A majority of these researchers (56%) are employed in the **business enterprise sector**, indicating a strong link between research, innovation, and industrial growth. The higher education sector employs 32% of researchers, emphasizing the **critical role of universities in advancing scientific knowledge and training future researchers**. The public sector, which employs 11% of researchers, plays a vital role in conducting research that addresses public needs and supports policy development (Eurostat, 2021).

This distribution underscores the necessity for researchers to possess a **diverse skill set** that includes both technical and transversal skills due to the ability to navigate different professional environments, communicate effectively, manage projects, and work collaboratively is crucial for success in various sectors.

The shift towards non-academic careers is mainly partly driven by the **limited number of tenure-track positions available**. Despite a significant increase in the number of doctoral graduates, stable academic positions have not kept pace. Studies such as those by Hnatkova et al. (2022) and Waaijer et al. (2017) document the challenges faced by doctoral graduates in securing stable academic positions.

Securing a stable academic position has become increasingly challenging for doctoral graduates due to several factors. One significant factor is the surge in doctoral education without a corresponding increase in long-term academic positions. This has led to a situation where many highly qualified individuals compete for a limited number of tenure-track roles, resulting in job insecurity and temporary postdoctoral positions becoming the norm in many academic systems (S. Sarrico et al., 2022) (OECD Science, 2021).

² EU reached 2 million researchers in 2021 - Eurostat (europa.eu)

Another factor is the high expectations placed on researchers to produce significant research outputs and secure external funding. The pressure to publish frequently and obtain grants can lead to job insecurity and financial instability, affecting researchers' professional fulfillment and societal contribution. This intense competition for funding and publication further exacerbates the challenges faced by early-career researchers (C. Sin, O. Tavares, 2017).

Moreover, studies have shown that the lack of stable academic positions undermines the overall job satisfaction and mental well-being of doctoral graduates, leading to increased stress and reduced motivation (Hnatkova et al., 2022; Waaijer et al., 2017). As a result, many doctoral graduates find themselves in a cycle of temporary postdoctoral roles, often funded by short-term research projects. This precarious employment situation affects their job security, financial stability, and overall job satisfaction, prompting many to seek opportunities outside academia (Boman et al., 2021; OECD, 2023).

Furthermore, the evolving nature of industry and the rise of sectors like technology, healthcare, and environmental sciences have expanded the demand for researchers who can bring innovative solutions to complex problems. The business enterprise sector's growing demand for research and development (R&D) expertise underscores the need for researchers to adapt their skills to diverse professional environments.

This shift and this evolving landscape necessitate **a broader skill set**, encompassing both technical proficiency and transversal skills such as critical thinking, creativity, and adaptability, to navigate and excel in various non-academic career paths (Henningesen et al., 2020). As documented by Bozzon et al. (2019) and Skakni et al. (2022), the ability to navigate complex projects and collaborate effectively within diverse teams is critical for success in various professional environments.

The recognition of these skills in the labour market is further supported by industry consultations, which consistently highlight the value of soft skills alongside technical knowledge (Boman et al., 2022; Janičko et al., 2022).

The traditional focus of academic training on research and technical skills often overlooks the development of essential transversal skills and cognitive abilities. This gap in training can hinder doctoral graduates' ability to effectively transition to non-academic roles where such skills are highly valued. The lack of formal training in areas such as project management, communication, and teamwork can be a significant barrier to career progression both within and outside academia (Horta, 2018).

Many graduates end up in temporary postdoctoral roles with uncertain long-term prospects, prompting a move towards non-academic careers. The need for balanced skill development is critical as industries outside academia increasingly seek individuals who can navigate complex projects and collaborate effectively within diverse teams.

According to the European University Association (EUA), European universities recognized the importance of **transversal competences training as early as 2005**. However, the focus was on core research training, with transversal skills and transversal professional competencies, such as networking, offered on a voluntary basis (EUA, 2005). This trend has persisted to date.

The **DocEnhance survey**³ on 6 European Universities in 2021 found that almost one quarter of respondents did not receive any training in transversal competences, both research- and

³ What comes after a PhD? Findings from the DocEnhance survey of doctorate holders on their employment situation, skills match, and the value of the doctorate

non-research-related. Those receiving training prioritized research-related competences, with only about 30% trained in soft skills (Boman et al., 2021).

Additionally, the pressure to publish frequently and secure funding also means that doctoral candidates often have little time to develop additional skills, such as public engagement, teaching, and interdisciplinary collaboration, which are increasingly important in both academic and non-academic contexts (Bozzon et al., 2019). This focus on a narrow set of outcomes can leave graduates underprepared for the varied demands of the modern job market.

Moreover, the increasing number of researchers in the business enterprise sector highlights the importance of industry-relevant skills such as understanding market dynamics, project management, and adaptability to corporate environments. Researchers must be equipped with the skills to translate their scientific expertise into practical applications that drive innovation and economic growth (Janičko et al., 2022).

Studies indicate that while technical expertise remains essential, the ability to communicate effectively, manage projects, lead teams, and engage with non-specialist audiences is equally important. These skills enhance researchers' employability and career satisfaction, regardless of whether they remain in academia or transition to other sectors (Janičko et al., 2022; Marin-Zapata et al., 2022).

Significant transformations in European doctoral education have underscored the importance of transversal competences. The integration of doctoral education as the third cycle of tertiary education in the Bologna Process of 2003, followed by the "Ten Salzburg Principles" in 2005, acknowledged the necessity for doctoral education to meet labor market demands beyond academia and cultivate transferable skills. Educational reforms have therefore made transversal competences integral to doctoral education. These reforms follow two main approaches: interdisciplinary collaboration, fostering knowledge exchange among students from diverse backgrounds, and intersectoral initiatives, such as industrial PhD programs, engaging students in dual roles as researchers and practitioners. Intersectoral programs offer innovative solutions to global challenges and make doctoral programs more professionally oriented, facilitating networking with stakeholders outside academia and enhancing employment prospects.

2.2 ENHANCING SKILLS AND COMPETENCY ALIGNMENT WITH EUROPEAN RESEARCH FRAMEWORKS

The importance of transversal skills for researchers has gained increasing recognition in recent years. Transversal skills, which include both intrapersonal and interpersonal competencies, are essential for effective research and professional development. Intrapersonal skills such as **creativity, analytical thinking, and problem-solving** are crucial for innovation and the successful execution of research projects. Interpersonal skills, including **communication, teamwork, and empathy**, are vital for interdisciplinary collaboration and stakeholder engagement. European policy frameworks such as the **European Charter for Researchers**⁴ emphasize the development of these competencies. The alignment of skills and competencies with European research policies is crucial for advancing a modern, inclusive, and impactful research environment. The relationship, for

instance, between **open science** principles and transversal skills is essential for the success of early career researchers (ECRs). Open Science represents a transformative approach to scientific research that emphasizes **transparency, collaboration, and accessibility**. It involves practices such as open access to publications, open data sharing, and citizen science, aiming to make scientific research more reproducible and beneficial to society. This approach requires researchers to develop a new set of skills and competencies that align with the principles of openness and collaboration. One of the key components of Open Science is the ability to **communicate research findings effectively** to a wide audience, including non-specialists. Researchers must cultivate strong communication skills, both written and oral, and be adept at using digital tools for disseminating research.

The **European Commission** has emphasized the importance of Open Science in its policy frameworks, including the **Horizon Europe program**⁵. For researchers, engaging in Open Science practices means developing a proficiency in digital tools and platforms that facilitate open access publishing and data sharing. This also involves understanding legal and ethical considerations related to data privacy and intellectual property. Moreover, researchers need to be adept at using social media and other digital platforms to engage with a broader audience, including policymakers, industry stakeholders, and the general public. These skills ensure that research findings are not only accessible but also relevant and impactful in addressing societal challenges.

In relation to Open Science practices, the 2020-2021 EUA survey found that European universities are increasingly incorporating Open Science principles into their institutional policies. However, limitations exist regarding the implementation of such principles. For instance, only **35% of institutions provide mandatory awareness activities**, including training for early-career researchers, on Open Science practices, while 45% offer these activities on an optional basis. Additionally, there is heterogeneity in terms of the integration of different principles. While Open Access to research publications is the most embedded area in institutional policies and practices, FAIR principles, Open Education, and Citizen Science either lack representation in institutional policies or have minimal integration (Morais et al. 2021). Furthermore, a recent European Commission study on digital skills underlines the **insufficient training on digital competencies** necessary for the Open Science approach. While some universities offer curricula and PhD courses dedicated to data science, there is a lack of widespread training across disciplines. Additionally, there is a significant gap in multidisciplinary usage of digital data and interoperability of datasets, software, and workflows (Barker et al. 2021).

The lack of appropriate training reflects in a reduced talent pool of doctoral graduates with necessary open science and digital competences, and transversal skills. There is a growing stream of literature on the match between the skills individuals have, those required by the new research paradigm and organizations outside academia, and the effects of eventual mismatches.

While some studies report close matching between the skills of doctoral graduates and the skills that are important or used not only in academia but also on jobs outside academia (e.g., Boman et al., 2021), others reveal deficiencies particularly related to transversal skills and market-oriented competencies. Janičko et al. (2022), drawing on qualitative insights from employers across various sectors, emphasized significant deficiencies in the ability to

⁵ https://commission.europa.eu/funding-tenders/find-funding/eu-funding-programmes/horizon-europe_en

translate research into tangible, market-oriented outcomes, stemming from a tendency towards theoretical approaches and limited understanding of market dynamics, including patent procedures. Additionally, shortcomings in interpersonal and intrapersonal skills, such as communication abilities to engage with non-experts and effective time management, were also noted. Leniston et al. (2022) found that employers often believe that doctoral programs tend to isolate students, leading to deficiencies in innovation, collaboration, and adaptability—qualities crucial for thriving in competitive environments and fast-paced industry settings.

Regarding **Open Science**, the European Commission study revealed that PhD holders possess only moderate awareness of its practices. While there's relatively greater familiarity with concepts like Open Source, Open Access publishing, and Open Data, awareness lags behind areas such as Open Education and Citizen Science. Consequently, only a minority of researchers engage in Open-Source publishing, with many unaware of whether their work falls within this category. Similarly, students often lack awareness of the fate of their research data, leading to challenges in data storage, archiving, and transfer processes (O'Carroll et al., 2017).

This lack of appropriate competences can slow down research processes and the creation of disruptive innovations. Moreover, competency mismatches, particularly related to transversal skills and market-related, can render the transitioning outside academia marked by significant challenges. In fact, despite their extensive expertise in specialized fields, doctoral candidates may not always be perceived as valuable assets by organizations outside academia. This lack of perceived value is reflected in significant shares of organizations, even those involved in Research and Development activities, who do not actively seek out doctoral graduates when recruiting talent (Boman et al., 2022).

As an important European initiative, **Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI)**⁶, integrates the societal needs and ethical considerations into the research and innovation process. RRI emphasizes inclusivity, sustainability, and responsiveness to societal challenges. It encompasses several dimensions, including public engagement, gender equality, science education, open access, and ethics. To effectively implement RRI, researchers must develop a broad range of skills and competencies. These include ethical reasoning, the ability to engage with diverse stakeholders, and the capacity to work in interdisciplinary teams. Researchers need to be equipped to address societal concerns, anticipate the implications of their work, and involve the public in the research process. This approach not only enhances the **relevance and impact of research** but also ensures that research practices **align with societal values** (Owen et al., 2012). The European Commission's guidelines on RRI provide a comprehensive framework for integrating these principles into research projects. For instance, Horizon Europe projects are required to incorporate RRI principles, ensuring that research activities contribute to sustainable development and address societal challenges. This alignment necessitates continuous professional development and training in areas such as ethics, public engagement, and interdisciplinary collaboration. By incorporating RRI principles into their work, researchers can create more inclusive and socially responsible research outcomes (European Commission, 2020).

The integration of RRI principles requires researchers to develop strong project management skills, including the ability to design and manage projects that align with ethical standards

and societal needs. Researchers also need to be proficient in stakeholder analysis and engagement, which involves identifying key stakeholders, understanding their needs and concerns, and actively involving them in the research process. This participatory approach ensures that research is more responsive to societal challenges and can lead to more innovative and impactful solutions.

In alignment with the European frameworks developed, another creative and interdisciplinary movement, **The New European Bauhaus**⁷, connects the European Green Deal to living spaces. It aims to make Europe's future sustainable, inclusive, and beautiful by bringing together art, culture, social inclusion, science, and technology. The initiative promotes a holistic approach to innovation, integrating aesthetics and functionality with sustainability. Researchers involved in projects aligned with the European Bauhaus need to develop skills that go beyond traditional scientific and technical expertise. They must embrace creativity and design thinking, which are crucial for developing innovative solutions that are both practical and aesthetically pleasing. Collaboration across disciplines is essential, requiring researchers to work closely with architects, artists, designers, and social scientists. This interdisciplinary approach fosters a richer understanding of complex problems and encourages innovative solutions that are both sustainable and socially inclusive (European Commission, 2021).

To support this initiative, the European Commission provides funding and resources for interdisciplinary projects that embody the principles of the New European Bauhaus. Researchers are encouraged to participate in workshops, training programs, and collaborative networks that foster creativity and interdisciplinary collaboration. This approach not only enhances the researchers' skill sets but also contributes to the development of sustainable and inclusive living environments, aligning scientific research with broader societal goals (European Commission, 2021).

Horizon Europe, the EU's flagship research and innovation funding program, highlights the importance of collaborative projects and stakeholder engagement. It promotes open access and encourages the sharing of data and research outcomes, aligning with the broader goals of making scientific research more transparent and collaborative. This policy framework not only supports the dissemination of research findings but also fosters an environment where researchers can learn from each other and build upon existing work, thereby accelerating scientific progress (European Commission, 2020). Researchers involved in Horizon Europe projects are often required to work in multinational and multidisciplinary teams, enhancing their teamwork and networking skills. The program also promotes open science practices, demanding effective data management, transparency, and ethical considerations, thereby fostering a comprehensive skill set beyond technical expertise (Barker et al., 2021).

An important initiative within Horizon Europe is the **Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA)**⁸ which is pivotal for the career development of researchers. MSCA provides valuable opportunities for researchers at various career stages to gain international experience and receive high-quality training in transferable skills. These initiatives help equip researchers with essential competences such as entrepreneurship, communication, and innovation management, which are critical for advancing in both academic and non-academic settings (Bitušiková & Borseková, 2020). By participating in MSCA, researchers can significantly

⁷ https://new-european-bauhaus.europa.eu/index_en

⁸ <https://marie-sklodowska-curie-actions.ec.europa.eu/>

enhance their professional development and increase their employability across diverse sectors, contributing to the overarching goals of Horizon Europe in fostering a vibrant and dynamic research community.

2.3 EUROPEAN POLICY FRAMEWORKS PROMOTING SKILLS DEVELOPMENT FOR RESEARCHERS

European policy frameworks play a crucial role in promoting the development of transversal skills for young researchers across Europe. These frameworks aim to enhance the career prospects of the young researchers (R1 and R2) by fostering a more integrated and supportive research environment across Europe. The frameworks discussed in this section focus on improving working conditions, promoting interdisciplinary collaboration, and equipping researchers with the transversal skills needed to thrive in both academic and non-academic sectors.

On 18 December 2023, the Council of the European Union reached a political **agreement on a recommendation**⁹ to enhance support for researchers and their careers within the European Union. This initiative aims to create a more appealing and sustainable labor market for researchers, innovators, and entrepreneurs in Europe, including attracting foreign talents. It updates the **R1-R4 researcher profiles** from 2011 and revises the **2005 European Charter for Researchers** and the **Code of Conduct for the Recruitment of Researchers**. Key objectives of the recommendation include improving working conditions, promoting social protection, fostering inter-sectoral mobility, and addressing inequalities based on gender, age, ethnicity, and other factors. It also encourages organizations to endorse the new European Charter for Researchers, highlighting the importance also of research managers and technicians. It addresses issues such as precarious employment conditions for researchers, especially early-career ones, and the need for broader employment opportunities outside academia.

Recognizing the need for researchers to thrive in various sectors beyond academia, the recommendation highlights the importance of equipping researchers with a broad set of skills through both formal and informal training. It advocates for the implementation of the **European Competence Framework for Researchers (ResearchComp)**¹⁰ and highlights the development of a European Competence Framework for Researchers. Moreover, the European Competence Framework for Researchers, or ResearchComp, offers a structured approach to identifying and developing the skills needed throughout a researcher's career. This framework outlines **38 transversal competences** grouped into key areas such as cognitive abilities, working with others, self-management, teamwork, research execution, and impact creation. By providing a standardized language and harmonization of essential competences, ResearchComp facilitates intersectoral mobility and the development of targeted training opportunities (European Commission, 2020).

The recommendation includes key implementation mechanisms such as the revised European Charter for Researchers, the **Human Resources Strategy for Researchers (HRS4R)**, and the establishment of an **Observatory on Research Careers** to monitor progress. Furthermore, it calls for strengthening **EURAXESS services** and developing the **ERA Talent Platform** to provide comprehensive support for researchers and institutions. This initiative is

⁹ Council Recommendation of 18 December 2023 on a European framework to attract and retain research, innovation and entrepreneurial talents in Europe - Publications Office of the EU (europa.eu)

¹⁰ ResearchComp: The European Competence Framework for Researchers - European Commission (europa.eu)

part of broader efforts to reinforce the **European Research Area (ERA)** and enhance Europe's global competitiveness in research and innovation.

The European Research Area (ERA) is a unified framework aimed at fostering a more integrated and efficient research environment across Europe. Its primary goal is to create a seamless space where researchers, scientific knowledge, and technology can circulate freely, enhancing collaboration and innovation. By removing barriers to mobility and ensuring equitable access to research funding and resources, The ERA emphasizes the importance of developing researchers' transversal skills, such as communication, collaboration, and critical thinking, which are essential for tackling complex societal challenges and ensuring that research outputs have a broader societal impact.

In alignment with the objectives of the ERA, the **European Charter for Researchersⁱ** provides a comprehensive framework for the career development and working conditions of researchers within Europe. The Charter outlines the roles, responsibilities, and entitlements of researchers and their employers, promoting a supportive and stimulating work environment. It emphasizes the importance of continuous professional development, including the acquisition of transferable skills such as leadership, project management, and interdisciplinary collaboration. These skills are crucial for researchers to navigate the evolving demands of both academic and non-academic sectors. The Charter also advocates for diverse career paths and mobility, recognizing the need for researchers to be adaptable and versatile in a rapidly changing job market.

The ERA's focus on creating a unified research space and enhancing mobility is synergistically aligned with the Charter's emphasis on professional development and the acquisition of transversal skills. These frameworks collectively ensure that European researchers are well-equipped to meet the challenges of modern scientific and societal landscapes, driving forward scientific and technological advancements in a competitive global environment.

It's important to consider also that according to the **European Skills Agenda¹¹** and the **Digital Education Action Plan¹²**, digital competences are essential for enhancing productivity and helping researchers to adapt to technological changes and contribute to digital transformation efforts. Having strong digital and entrepreneurial skills is crucial for researchers in today's rapidly evolving technological and economic landscapes. These competencies allow researchers to effectively manage digital tools, collaborate across disciplines, innovate within their fields, and contribute to societal advancements.

In alignment with these goals, the **Digital Competence Framework for Citizens¹³** was developed. Initially defined in 2006 and updated by the Council Recommendation in 2018, this framework underscores the importance of transversal skills with over 250 examples of knowledge, skills, and attitudes. Policy initiatives at the European level place a strong emphasis on enhancing digital skills and competences. The EU digital skills strategy and related policies aim to support digital transformation by enhancing digital competences necessary for both work and daily life. For instance, the **European Skills Agenda** of 1 July 2020 supports digital skills for all and aligns with the objectives of the **Digital Education Action Plan**, aiming to foster a high-performing digital education system. Ambitious policy targets, such as ensuring basic digital skills for at least 80% of the population and having 20

¹¹ <https://ec.europa.eu/social/mai.n.jsp?catId=1223&langId=en>

¹² Digital Education Action Plan (2021-2027) - European Education Area (europa.eu)

¹³ <https://ec.europa.eu/jrc/en/digcomp/digital-competence-framework>

million ICT specialists by 2030, are set out in the **Digital Compass**¹⁴ and the **European Pillar of Social Rights Action Plan**¹⁵.

The European Skills Agenda also highlights the importance of entrepreneurial skills for researchers, recognizing that these competencies are crucial for adapting to the rapidly changing technological and economic landscapes. Entrepreneurial skills enable researchers to commercialize their innovations, secure funding, manage projects, and effectively navigate market dynamics, thereby contributing to economic growth and societal advancements. It emphasizes that researchers must develop a diverse skill set that includes cognitive, practical, and interpersonal abilities to successfully bring their ideas to market and drive innovation. This is reflected in various EU policy initiatives and frameworks, such as the **EntreComp Framework**¹⁶, which defines entrepreneurship as the ability to create financial, cultural, or social value by leveraging opportunities and ideas. This broad definition highlights the necessity for a diverse skill set that includes cognitive, practical, and interpersonal abilities. The development of these skills has been a key objective for the EU and its Member States for many years. The European Commission's policy initiatives, such as the 2003 Green Paper on Entrepreneurship in Europe and the 2006 Recommendation on Key Competences for Lifelong Learning, have emphasized the need for a sense of initiative and entrepreneurship as fundamental competences. More recent documents, such as the 2013 Entrepreneurship Action Plan and the New Skills Agenda for Europe, continue to highlight the importance of entrepreneurial education and the development of relevant competences.

Since 2018, there have been significant recommendations emphasizing the importance of developing key competences for lifelong learning. In May 2018, the Council of the European Union adopted the recommendation "**Key Competences for Life Long Learning**"¹⁷ (The Official Journal 2018/C 189/01). These recommendations highlight the integration of transversal skills such as critical thinking, problem-solving, teamwork, communication, creativity, negotiation, and intercultural skills into all areas of learning. These skills are considered essential for navigating the complexities of modern life and work environments.

However, when it comes to assessing researchers' skills and competences, including transversal skills and transversal competences, there are only a few well-defined competence frameworks, especially in Europe. These frameworks cover various dimensions or areas describing a set of competences, unlike competence profiles which specify job requirements in measurable terms. Existing frameworks, such as the **European Framework for Research Careers, Vitae Researcher Development Framework, National Postdoctoral Association Core Competencies, European Qualifications Framework, and European Skills, Competences, Qualifications, and Occupations (ESCO) Framework**, are diverse. This diversity underscores the need for greater alignment, particularly in linking competences to different career stages and occupations. Aligning these frameworks would enhance coherence and facilitate the transferability of skills and qualifications across sectors and career stages, fostering a more integrated approach to researcher development in Europe.

Table 1. Comprehensive Competence Frameworks for European Researchers summarizes key competence frameworks that guide the development of researcher's skills and competencies, supporting their career progression and adaptability to diverse professional environments.

¹⁴ 2030 DIGITAL COMPASS: YOUR DIGITAL DECADE | Futurium (europa.eu)

¹⁵ European Pillar of Social Rights Action Plan - European Commission (europa.eu)

¹⁶ <https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/handle/JRC101581>

¹⁷ Council Recommendation of 22 May 2018 on key competences for lifelong learning Text with EEA relevance. (europa.eu)

TAB1: "COMPREHENSIVE COMPETENCE FRAMEWORKS FOR EUROPEAN RESEARCHERS"

Framework	Description
<p>The European Framework for Research Careers</p>	<p>Developed by the European Council of Doctoral Candidates and Junior Researchers (EURODOC), it outlines the key competences required for researchers at different stages of their careers, including doctoral candidates, early-stage researchers, and experienced researchers. The framework defines four overarching career profile descriptors, spanning from First Stage Researcher (R1) to Leading Researcher (R4). Additionally, it delineates distinct characteristics and responsibilities that researchers might have throughout their career journey. The framework aims to be sector-neutral, encompassing researchers employed in diverse sectors such as the public or private sector (e.g., NGOs, private companies, research institutes, research universities, or universities of applied sciences).</p>
<p>Vitae Researcher Development Framework (RDF)</p>	<p>Developed by Vitae, a UK-based organization supporting the professional development of researchers, it identifies the knowledge, behaviors, and attributes that researchers need to be successful in their careers. It covers four main domains: knowledge and intellectual abilities, personal effectiveness, research governance and organization, and engagement, influence, and impact.</p>
<p>National Postdoctoral Association (NPA) Core Competencies</p>	<p>A framework that specifically targets postdoctoral researchers and outlines core competencies in six domains: disciplinary expertise, research skills, communication skills, professionalism, leadership and management skills, and responsible conduct of research.</p>
<p>European Qualifications Framework (EQF)</p>	<p>A common reference framework developed by the European Union (EU) and its member states to facilitate the comparison and recognition of qualifications across different European countries. It provides a common understanding of qualifications and</p>

	promotes lifelong learning by facilitating the transferability of qualifications and promoting mobility within Europe.
European Skills, Competences, Qualifications, and Occupations (ESCO) Framework	A multilingual classification system developed by the European Commission. It provides a common language and framework for describing skills, competences, qualifications, and occupations across different countries and sectors within the European Union. It aims to facilitate labour market transparency and mobility by harmonizing the terminology and understanding of skills and qualifications across European countries. ESCO covers a wide range of occupations and skills, allowing individuals, employers, education providers, and policymakers to better understand and compare skills and qualifications in the European labour market.

2.4 ENHANCING RESEARCH EXCELLENCE: ALIGNING COMPETENCIES WITH THE EUROPEAN FRAMEWORK FOR RESEARCHER DEVELOPMENT

In this study, we leverage the **European Competence Framework for Researchers**, known as **ResearchComp**, to guide our analysis and recommendations. ResearchComp provides a comprehensive structure for identifying and developing essential competencies throughout a researcher's career. This framework categorizes competencies into key areas such as **cognitive abilities, self-management, teamwork, research execution, research management, research tool management, and impact creation**. These competencies are crucial for researchers to effectively contribute to both academic and non-academic sectors. In this study, the focus consists of **7 competences areas**: cognitive abilities, doing research, managing research, managing research tools, making an impact, working with others, self-management.

Studying the seven competencies from the ResearchComp framework is crucial for the holistic development of researchers and the advancement of scientific initiatives.

Cognitive abilities, which encompass critical thinking, problem-solving, and creativity, are fundamental for researchers to innovate and address complex scientific questions. These skills enable researchers to analyze data effectively, develop new methodologies, and generate original insights that push the boundaries of knowledge. For instance, enhanced cognitive abilities are linked to improved research quality and the capacity to tackle interdisciplinary challenges (Marin-Zapata et al., 2022; Deming, 2017).

Doing research comes with a solid foundation in research methodologies, which enables them to design and execute studies that contribute new knowledge to their fields. This

competence involves understanding various research designs, data collection methods, and analytical techniques. It also includes the ability to critically assess existing literature, identify research gaps, and formulate testable hypotheses. Mastery in conducting research ensures that studies are methodologically sound and ethically conducted, providing reliable and valid results (Creswell, 2014; Flick, 2018).

Managing research as a competence involves planning, organizing, and overseeing research activities to ensure that projects are completed on time, within budget, and to the required standard. Researchers must be skilled in project management, which includes setting objectives, developing timelines, managing resources, and coordinating team efforts. They also need to be adept at risk management, identifying potential obstacles, and developing contingency plans to address them (Kerzner, 2017; Pinto, 2020).

On the other hand, **Managing Research tools** involves the ability to select and utilize appropriate tools and technologies for data collection, analysis, and presentation. Researchers must be skilled in using software for statistical analysis, data visualization, and bibliographic management. They also need to be familiar with laboratory equipment, field instruments, and other specialized tools relevant to their research. Mastery of research tools enhances the efficiency and accuracy of data collection and analysis, enabling researchers to produce high-quality research outputs (Kuckartz, 2014; Johnson & Christensen, 2019).

Making an impact through research involves disseminating findings and engaging with stakeholders. Researchers must be skilled in communicating their research to diverse audiences, including academic peers, policymakers, industry partners, and the public. This competence includes writing research papers, presenting at conferences, and using digital platforms to share findings. Effective communication enhances the visibility and reach of research, increasing its potential to influence policy, practice, and public opinion (Holliman et al., 2017; Phipps et al., 2012).

Working with others is another essential competence that underscores the collaborative nature of modern research. Effective teamwork skills enable researchers to engage in productive collaborations, share diverse perspectives, and leverage collective expertise to achieve common goals. This competence is particularly important in interdisciplinary research projects and international collaborations, where successful outcomes depend on the ability to work cohesively within diverse teams (Barker et al., 2021).

Self-management, which includes the management of personal and professional development, time management, goal setting, and self-motivation and organization, is critical for maintaining productivity and well-being in the demanding research environment. Researchers who excel in self-management are better equipped to handle the pressures of grant writing, publishing, and teaching responsibilities. They can prioritize tasks effectively, maintain focus on long-term research objectives, and sustain motivation through challenging periods. Self-management skills are also associated with greater career satisfaction and resilience, enabling researchers to navigate the uncertainties and complexities of academic and research careers (Horta, 2018; Boman et al., 2022).

ResearchComp emphasizes the development of **transferable skills** that are increasingly crucial in today's interdisciplinary and intersectoral research environments. By focusing on these competencies, we aim to ensure that researchers are not only proficient in their technical fields but also possess the transversal skills necessary for successful collaboration, communication, and ethical engagement. This holistic approach to competency development aligns with the principles of **Open Science, Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI), and the New European Bauhaus**, which collectively promote transparency, inclusivity, and societal impact in research.

This study underscores the importance of **transversal skills** for young researchers (R1 and R2 levels) in navigating the transformative processes of the contemporary knowledge society. It highlights that along with traditional academic expertise, intrapersonal and interpersonal competencies—commonly referred to as transversal skills—are increasingly required and valued. These competencies are essential for problem-solving, interdisciplinary collaboration, and effectively responding to societal and scientific challenges (Marin-Zapata et al., 2022).

By integrating the ResearchComp framework into our analysis, we provide a structured and standardized approach to evaluating and developing the transversal skills necessary for researchers to thrive in a dynamic and rapidly changing research environment. This approach not only supports individual career development but also contributes to the broader goals of enhancing the quality and impact of European research. Ensuring that researchers are well-rounded and adaptable will enhance their contributions to innovation, economic growth, and societal progress. The study also emphasizes the evolving employment landscape for researchers, showing a growing trend in the number of full-time equivalent researchers in the EU, particularly in the business enterprise and public sectors, reflecting the need for a diverse skill set that includes both technical and soft skills (Eurostat, 2021).

To ensure that researchers are well-prepared for these diverse demands, it is essential to provide continuous professional development opportunities. This includes structured training programs, online courses, workshops, and conferences that focus on transversal skills. Higher education institutions should also establish mentorship programs and career development services to support researchers throughout their careers, helping them to adapt to new challenges and opportunities as they arise (Boman et al., 2022).

Moreover, fostering a supportive institutional culture that values and promotes interdisciplinary collaboration is crucial. This can be achieved by creating opportunities for researchers to work on joint projects, participate in interdisciplinary workshops, and engage in collaborative networks. Such initiatives not only enhance individual competencies but also drive innovation by integrating diverse perspectives and expertise (Marin-Zapata et al., 2022).

3. METHODOLOGIES

The methodology of this study employed a **comprehensive approach** to understand the *transversal skills landscape* among R1 and R2 researchers. The study began with a **systematic process of collecting, analyzing, and synthesizing existing information** from various sources (secondary sources and peer-reviewed studies) to forecast the future relevance and demand for these skills. The aim is to identify which *transversal skills* will be most valuable for young researchers in the evolving job market, particularly in non-academic sectors.

After this desk research a detailed **questionnaire** targeting young researchers (R1 and R2) in European universities was then developed. This survey covered a self-assessment of **38 transversal skills described in ReseachComp** necessary for success in both academic and non-academic careers, including cognitive abilities, self-management, teamwork, research execution, management, tool management, and impact creation. The survey also gathered information on the provision of transversal skills training, perceptions of critical skills for future career success, and the adequacy of current training programs. The questionnaire was pilot tested for clarity and reliability, with data collected via Qualtrics.

In order to have a broader and deeper information to complete this study, **in-depth semi-structured interviews** were conducted with academic stakeholders, such as Faculty Advisors/Mentors; Research Supervisors; Graduate Coordinators; member of Alumni Networks; Responsible of career Services; Responsibles of International Offices from various European universities. These interviews provided qualitative insights into transversal skills, the effectiveness of current training, and the challenges in developing these skills. Additionally, interviews with industry and third sector representatives aimed to understand employer perceptions of transversal skills mismatches between academic training and market demands.

Furthermore, a **rigorous job scraping methodology** was employed to quantify labor market demand for transversal skills. Job postings for roles requiring or preferring PhD candidates were analyzed using advanced text mining and natural language processing techniques to identify and categorize mentioned transversal skills, highlighting the most sought-after competencies across different sectors.

All the data collected have been utilized and analysed to depict the current state (As IS) of transversal skills among young researchers (R1 and R2), as well as to train an algorithm for a predictive view of the future competency landscape always related to Research Comp.

This **mixed-methods approach** provided a robust understanding of the current and future transversal skills requirements for researchers, offering actionable insights for universities, policymakers, and researchers to better align training with labor market demands.

3.1 ASSESSING AND ENHANCING TRANSVERSAL SKILLS AMONG EUROPEAN EARLY CAREER RESEARCHERS: A COMPREHENSIVE SURVEY STUDY OF R1 AND R2 CLASSIFICATIONS

The survey was designed to gather comprehensive data on the transversal skills of early career researchers classified as R1 and R2 according to the **ResearchComp framework**. These classifications include doctoral candidates (R1) and researchers with postdoctoral experience (R2). The aim was to assess their current proficiency levels in various **transversal skills** and to understand their perceptions of the importance and adequacy of these skills in their current and future careers. The survey targeted **European students**, ensuring a broad and representative sample across different institutions and disciplines.

The survey was designed to cover a wide range of **transversal skills categories**, including cognitive abilities, self-management, teamwork, research execution, research management, research tool management, and impact creation. These categories were chosen based on their relevance to both academic and non-academic career paths, reflecting the diverse skill sets required in various professional environments.

For the maximization of participation, a **comprehensive engagement plan** was developed. Consortia members leveraged their extensive networks within the academic community to disseminate the survey widely. This included reaching out to their respective institutions, promoting the survey through newsletters, social media, and direct emails to potential respondents. Collaboration with university alliances further broadened the reach, ensuring the survey was accessible to a diverse range of early career researchers across Europe. Efforts were made to engage participants by highlighting the importance of the survey and how their input could contribute to enhancing **transversal skills training programs**. Incentives such as participation in prize draws or access to summarized results were offered to encourage participation.

The survey included both closed and open-ended questions to gather quantitative and qualitative data. The self-assessment section asked participants to rate their proficiency in various transversal skills on a **Likert scale**. This allowed for a quantitative analysis of perceived skill levels across different categories. Additional questions explored the provision of transversal skills training at participants' universities, their perceptions of the most critical transversal skills for future career success, and the adequacy of current training programs. Open-ended questions provided space for respondents to share detailed insights and suggestions, contributing to a **richer understanding of the challenges and opportunities in transversal skills development**.

The survey was conducted over an eight-month period, allowing ample time for dissemination, participation, and follow-up reminders. The timeline was strategically planned to avoid peak academic periods such as exam times and holidays, ensuring a higher response rate. We received a total of **1,701 responses**, indicating a strong level of engagement from the target audience. This high response rate provided a robust dataset for subsequent analysis, ensuring the findings were representative and reliable.

Several barriers and challenges were encountered during the survey administration process. Ensuring a sufficiently diverse population of early career researchers was challenging, as some institutions and disciplines had lower engagement levels despite extensive outreach efforts. This required targeted follow-ups and additional outreach strategies, such as personalized invitations and engaging academic leaders to promote participation. The survey

was initiated by **1,701 researchers**, but it was fully completed by **843 number of respondents**. Consequently, only the response of the completed surveys will be used in the analysis. Potential bias in self-reported data was another challenge. Participants might overestimate or underestimate their skills due to personal biases. To mitigate this, the survey underwent thorough pilot-testing for clarity and reliability. Statistical methods were employed during the analysis to identify and correct any biases, ensuring accurate reflections of participants' skills and perceptions. Technical issues also posed a challenge. Ensuring smooth access to the online survey platform, **Qualtrics**, and addressing any technical difficulties promptly was crucial to maintaining participation rates. Multiple reminders were sent to encourage survey completion within the designated timeframe. Lastly, ensuring **data integrity and security** was paramount. The data from the survey was securely stored, adhering to stringent ethical guidelines to ensure the confidentiality and anonymity of all participants. Informed consent was obtained from all respondents, and data management practices complied with relevant institutional review board standards.

3.2 EXPLORING THE HORIZON OF TRANSVERSAL SKILLS IN ACADEMIA AND INDUSTRY: INSIGHTS FROM STAKEHOLDER INTERVIEWS

The **in-depth semi-structured interviews** were conducted with **45 academic stakeholders**, primarily vice rectors of research from a diverse range of European universities, to gather qualitative insights on transversal skills for success in academia and beyond, the current state and effectiveness of transversal skills training, and innovative approaches for enhancing these skills within university curricula. The interviews explored institutional strategies for transversal skills development, the integration of transversal skills training into research programs, and anticipated future skills requirements in response to evolving academic and industry landscapes. These interviews were conducted either face-to-face or via videoconferencing to ensure flexibility and comprehensive coverage. Additionally, semi-structured interviews were conducted with **20** representatives from industry and the third sector, selected based on their experience and involvement in roles typically requiring or preferring a PhD qualification. These interviews focused on identifying the transversal skills most valued by employers, the adequacy of current training, and future trends in transversal skills demand, providing critical insights into the alignment between academic training and industry expectations.

In the scientific exploration of transversal skills within the professional development of PhD graduates, two distinct questionnaires, the **Questionnaire for Academia** and the **Questionnaire for Industry and Third Sector**, are employed to elucidate the perspectives from various sectors. The narrative that unfolds from these questionnaires is one of comparative analysis, aimed at discerning the nuanced expectations and experiences across the academic, industry, and third sector landscapes.

The questionnaire dedicated to academia begins with an **"Introduction and Background"** section, which is applicable to all interviewees regardless of their professional domain. This section seeks to establish the context of each respondent's experience by eliciting an introduction, current role, and their relationship with academia or the relevant sector. It also probes for insights into the academic and professional journey of PhD graduates within their field.

The next section, "**Transversal Skills Importance and Identification**," is intended for all interviewees and delves into the critical transversal skills necessary for PhD students preparing for today's workforce. It encourages respondents to reflect on specific instances where transversal skills have significantly influenced PhD graduates' career paths.

For those affiliated with academia, the "**Academic Environment and Transversal Skills**" section inquires about the integration of transversal skills in higher education institutions and seeks examples of innovative approaches to transversal skills development. It also addresses the challenges and gaps in current training provisions, overlooked transversal skills in PhD programs, and methods for assessing the effectiveness of training programs. Furthermore, it queries the transversal skills most valued in academic careers, such as those sought after when hiring postdoctoral researchers.

Conversely, the "**Industry (or Third Sector) Expectations and Transversal Skills**" section is tailored to interviewees from outside academia. It assesses whether early career researchers and PhD students possess the necessary transversal skills for non-academic careers and identifies the key transversal skills valued by employers in these sectors. Respondents are asked to provide examples where transversal skills have distinguished candidates during hiring or career advancement.

The "**Future Trends and Transversal Skills**" section is designed for all interviewees and anticipates the evolution of transversal skills over the next 5 years. It prompts respondents to advise current PhD students on maintaining the relevance and adaptability of their transversal skills and to speculate on the most in-demand professions in the future job market.

The questionnaire concludes with "**Back Up QUESTIONS related future trends**," which address the intersection of transversal skills with technological advancements, remote work, interdisciplinary projects, sustainability, evolving communication channels, lifelong learning, globalization, AI and machine learning, customer experience, and stakeholder engagement. This section encourages a forward-looking perspective on how transversal skills can complement technical expertise and adapt to changing work environments and societal expectations.

Also, the questionnaire for Industry and third sector commences with the "**Introduction and Background**" section, inviting all respondents to provide an overview of their identity, current role, and their connection to either academia or their respective sectors. This section aims to collect insights on the academic and professional trajectories of PhD graduates in various fields.

The "**Transversal Skills Importance and Identification**" segment prompts respondents from all backgrounds to consider the transversal skills for PhD students entering the workforce. Participants are encouraged to recount specific instances where transversal skills have played a pivotal role in shaping the career paths of PhD graduates.

Focusing on the non-academic realm, the "**Industry (or Third Sector) Expectations and Transversal Skills**" portion probes whether early career researchers and PhD applicants possess the transversal skills necessary for success in these sectors. It seeks to identify the transversal skills that are highly valued by employers and asks for examples where such skills have been decisive in hiring and career advancement.

The "**Future Trends and Transversal Skills**" section, applicable to all interviewees, explores the evolving importance of transversal skills in the next 5 years. It requests advice for current PhD students on how to keep their transversal skills relevant and adaptable in anticipation of future market demands. Additionally, it asks respondents to speculate on the professions likely to be in high demand in the future job market.

The questionnaire is rounded off with "**Back Up QUESTIONS related future trends,**" which delve into the complementary role of transversal skills alongside technical expertise amidst technological advancements and automation. It examines the transversal skills for thriving in remote work environments, interdisciplinary collaborations, and globalized settings. The section also contemplates the significance of transversal skills in fostering sustainability, ethics, and societal impact, as well as in adapting to diverse communication channels. It emphasizes the need for continuous learning, adaptability, and cultural competence, and considers the impact of AI and machine learning on the demand for certain transversal skills. Finally, it addresses the role of empathy, customer-centric thinking, and relationship-building in enhancing customer experience and stakeholder engagement.

More in general, the **Questionnaire for Academia** serves as a comprehensive instrument, engaging a diverse array of respondents from academia. For academia-affiliated individuals, it probes into the integration and challenges of transversal skills within higher education institutions but also asking them the perspective about their expectations and practical applications of transversal skills in non-academic careers. This bifurcation allows for a tailored inquiry, ensuring that the data collected is sector-specific and relevant.

The questionnaire further extends its scope to encompass future trends, presenting a series of questions designed to capture a forward-looking perspective, considering the interplay between technological advancements, changing work environments, and the evolving role of transversal skills. The breadth of topics covered in this section reflects a holistic approach to understanding the dynamic nature of transversal skills in the professional realm.

The **Questionnaire for Industry and Third Sector**, in contrast, adopts a more focused approach, exclusively targeting professionals within these sectors. This questionnaire eschews the academic-centric queries of its counterpart, instead homing in on the specific expectations and experiences of non-academic sectors. The absence of sector-based segmentation in the questions underscores the specialized nature of the inquiry, as all respondents are presumed to share a common ground in their professional settings. The narrative of the **Questionnaire for Industry and Third Sector** is one that is intimately tied to the current and future realities of these environments. While it also addresses the future trends and the evolving importance of transversal skills, the discourse is firmly rooted in the practicalities of non-academic career paths. The questions are crafted to elicit insights into how transversal skills are currently perceived, utilized, and valued within these sectors, as well as how they might need to adapt to meet the demands of an ever-changing job market. In essence, the distinction between the **Questionnaire for Academia** and the **Questionnaire for Industry and Third Sector** is a reflection of the methodological rigor inherent in scientific research. The former offers a broad, cross-sectoral examination of transversal skills, while the latter provides a concentrated exploration within specific professional contexts. Together, these questionnaires construct a narrative that is both comprehensive and detailed, allowing for a nuanced understanding of the role of transversal skills in shaping the careers of PhD graduates across the spectrum of professional environments.

3.3 INTEGRATED ANALYSIS OF EUROPEAN RESEARCHERS' PROFILES: QUANTITATIVE METHODOLOGIES AND JOB CRAWLING TECHNIQUES

To conduct the **AS-IS analysis** of the profile of young researchers (R1 and R2) at the European level, a mixed-method approach that combines desk research with quantitative techniques

has been adopted. The quantitative aspect was particularly robust, involving surveys and job crawling to gather comprehensive data. Specifically, two distinct surveys were administered: one targeted at young researchers (R1 and R2) (as described in the paragraph 3.1) and another at relevant stakeholders from academia, industry, research centers and other relevant stakeholders (as described in the paragraph 3.2). These surveys were meticulously designed to capture detailed information on the competencies outlined in the ResearchComp framework.

The survey targeting researchers required them to self-evaluate their proficiency in the 38 competencies outlined by ResearchComp, resulting in a comprehensive dataset of self-perceived skill levels. Simultaneously, the stakeholder survey gathered insights from employers and other relevant parties regarding the importance and required proficiency levels of these competencies in the workforce. This dual-survey approach effectively captured perspectives from both the supply-side (researchers' self-assessments) and the demand-side (employers' expectations)

In parallel with the surveys, we utilized a job crawling technique to analyze job postings. This process involved extracting data from numerous job advertisements aimed at early-career researchers **inside and outside the academia**. Through this method, we identified the competencies most frequently sought after in the job market. Additionally, the job crawling data was indexed according to the ResearchComp framework, enabling a standardized comparison with the survey results.

After collecting the data, the datasets from the stakeholder survey and the job crawling analysis were combined to create a comprehensive dataset representing employers' evaluations and demands. This merged dataset offered a clear picture of market requirements and expectations for researcher competencies.

With these datasets, we conducted a detailed analysis of the current (AS-IS) situation. We examined the perspectives of researchers and employers separately to identify any discrepancies between the self-assessed competencies of researchers and the competencies valued by employers. This approach was crucial for uncovering potential mismatches between researchers' skillsets and labor market needs.

The reasoning behind this approach is its ability to provide a comprehensive view of the current competency landscape. By isolating and comparing the viewpoints of researchers and employers, we can identify specific areas of misalignment. Understanding these gaps is crucial for informing policies and interventions that enhance the alignment between research training and market needs, ultimately improving employability and career outcomes for researchers.

Quantitative data was analyzed using statistical software to identify trends, patterns, and correlations. Qualitative data from open-ended questions was analyzed using content analysis methods, allowing for the identification of common themes and insights. **Natural language processing (NLP) techniques** were employed to preprocess and analyze text data, ensuring a comprehensive understanding of the qualitative responses.

The combination of these methods provided a holistic view of the current transversal skills landscape for R1 and R2 researchers, offering valuable insights for enhancing training

programs and aligning them with labor market demands. The robust methodology ensured that the findings were both comprehensive and actionable, providing a strong foundation for future initiatives aimed at improving transversal skills development for early career researchers.

3.4 FORECASTING THE FUTURE (OVER NEXT 5 YEARS): A MIXED-METHODS APPROACH TO TO-BE COMPETENCY ANALYSIS IN RESEARCH

The survey and the interview conducted respectively with **young researchers** and **stakeholders** not only examined the current **AS-IS** situation but also investigated their respective expectations regarding the **evolution** of competency profiles over the **next five years**. This approach enabled the execution of a comprehensive **TO-BE analysis**, which is essential for understanding the **future landscape** of research competencies and informing the **strategic direction** for **training and development programs** tailored for young researchers.

The TO-BE analysis is characterized by its rigorous and multifaceted methodological approach. It combines **qualitative insights from in-depth interviews** with **quantitative data** derived from surveys, creating a robust foundation for forecasting future competency requirements. This **mixed-methods** approach ensures that the analysis is grounded in real-world perspectives and empirical evidence, providing a **holistic view of anticipated trends**.

One of the key techniques employed in the TO-BE analysis is **trend analysis**, which involves examining current and historical data to identify patterns and predict future developments. By analyzing trends in technology, scientific methodologies, and industry demands, it is possible to infer the skills and knowledge areas that will likely become more critical. This process is augmented by **scenario planning**, where various potential future scenarios, based on different assumptions about technological advancements, funding landscapes, and policy changes, was created and explored. These scenarios helped in understanding the range of **possible futures** and the competencies that will be relevant in each context.

The TO-BE analysis also heavily relies on **stakeholder input**, ensuring that the expectations and requirements of employers, academic institutions, and research organizations are accurately captured. Stakeholders provided valuable insights into the **emerging skills** they anticipate needing, the evolving nature of research roles, and the gaps they currently observe in the skill sets of young researchers. This input is crucial for aligning the analysis with the **practical needs** of the research ecosystem.

The importance of the TO-BE analysis in shaping training strategies for young researchers cannot be understated. As the research landscape becomes increasingly complex and interdisciplinary, the **ability to adapt and acquire new competencies** will be vital. The TO-BE analysis identifies not only the **technical skills** that will be in demand, such as data analytics, artificial intelligence, and advanced laboratory techniques, but also the **transversal skills** that are becoming increasingly important, such as project management, interdisciplinary collaboration, and science communication.

By forecasting the **future competency requirements**, the TO-BE analysis provides a **roadmap** for educational institutions and training providers to develop curricula and programs that are forward-looking and relevant. This **proactive approach** ensures that young researchers are not only prepared for the current demands of the research environment but are also equipped to navigate and thrive in the **evolving landscape**.

Moreover, the TO-BE analysis helps **policymakers** and **funding bodies** to understand the future needs of the research community, allowing them to allocate resources and design initiatives that support the development of these competencies. This alignment of **training programs** with future needs enhances the overall **effectiveness and impact** of research activities, fostering **innovation** and **driving scientific progress**.

To methodologically proceed with the TO-BE analysis and effectively compare its outcomes with the AS-IS analysis, highlighting the actual **evolution of competency sets**, we followed a similar approach to the one detailed in the previous sections. Specifically, we began by examining the evolution of competencies as expressed by the young researchers who were interviewed. This initial phase involved **gathering detailed insights** into their expectations and aspirations for their future skills and competencies. Separately, we analyzed the **perspectives of stakeholders**, including employers and academic leaders, to understand their anticipated future requirements and expectations for researchers. By maintaining this separate analysis, we ensured a **clear** and **unbiased** comparison of viewpoints.

After collecting and analyzing the data from both young researchers and stakeholders, we **synthesized** these insights to evaluate the projected evolution of the **mismatch** between **current and future competency sets**. This involved **assessing** how the expected competencies align or diverge over time and **identifying** areas where the gap between young researcher skills and employer needs might widen or narrow. The analysis of the evolution of the mismatch is a **distinctive element** of this research, as it provides a **nuanced understanding** of how competency requirements are expected to change and where targeted interventions can be most effective.

Ultimately, this analysis can guide the **development of training** and **development programs** aimed at **reducing** the mismatch. By focusing on future competency requirements and anticipating changes, educational institutions and training providers can **design** curricula that better prepare young researchers for the evolving demands of their fields. This forward-looking approach ensures that young researchers not only meet current expectations but are also **equipped** with the transversal skills needed for future success, thereby enhancing their career prospects and contributing to the overall advancement of research and innovation.

4. FINDINGS: CURRENT LANDSCAPE (AS IS)

This chapter presents an **in-depth analysis** of the results of the current state of the research and skills landscape as perceived by early career researchers across various European institutions. It aims to clarify the existing conditions, challenges, and perceptions within the

area of research and transversal skills development, which are crucial for career advancement in both academic and non-academic settings.

4.1 COMPETENCIES IN THE EUROPEAN CONTEXT BY SELF ASSESSMENT DATA

Utilizing the data from the survey with **843 respondents** from over **140 universities across 21 EU countries**, this chapter details the demographic distribution, disciplinary representation, and geographic engagement of the participants, highlighting notable engagement from countries like **Italy and Poland** and providing a gender breakdown of the respondents.

FIGURE 1 DISTRIBUTION OF YOUNG RESEARCHERS (R1 & R2) RESPONDENTS ACROSS COUNTRIES

Figure 1 displays the distribution of respondents based on the country of the university of affiliation. Overall, data covers 29 European countries, however, the distribution of respondents varies substantially across countries, ranging from 1 to 166 respondents. The most representative countries are Italy and Poland, which together constitutes the 36.20% of the sample (20.24% and 16.10%, respectively). Countries displaying moderate representation are Romania, Portugal, Croatia, Latvia, Malta, and Slovenia (ranging from 8.66% to 5.24%). The remaining 21 European countries constitutes the remaining 20% of the sample. Therefore, the

data distribution is skewed towards a subset of countries, potentially influencing interpretation of the European context. Consequently, caution is advised when generalizing the results of the present study to the broader European context.

Regarding the profile of researchers constituting the sample in the present study, 56% of respondents identify as Females, 42% as Males, while the remaining 2% identifies as non-binary or prefers to not disclose gender information.

As per research career information, 89% of the sample is constituted by First Stage Researchers (PhD Candidate), and the remaining 11% of Recognized Researchers (Postdoc).

Regarding the research field, the distribution of respondents is relatively balanced across different areas. The majority are in Engineering and Technology (26%) and Social Sciences (25%). Additionally, 21% are in Natural Sciences, 12% in Humanities, and 10% in Medical and Health Sciences.

In addition to demographic insights, it delves into the specific **transversal skills** identified by academic experts as essential for PhD students and early career researchers, categorized according to the **ResearchComp Framework for Researchers**. The findings serve as an important understanding of the current landscape, setting the stage for following discussions on the skills gap and future trends in the research and innovation sector. By mapping the "as is" condition, the aim is to provide a clear baseline from which strategies for enhancing researcher skills and competencies can be developed and implemented. Assessing the Self-Perceived Competencies of Young Researchers: Strengths, Gaps, and Implications

The self-assessment data collected from researchers provides valuable insights into their perceived competency levels across various areas defined by the ResearchComp framework. These aggregate data provide a comprehensive view of researchers' self-perceived strengths and weaknesses across different competency areas, highlighting cognitive skills as a particular area of strength, while pointing out specific areas that may benefit from targeted development initiatives.

FIGURE 2 RESEARCHERS' SELF-PERCEIVED COMPETENCY LEVELS

Analyzing the figure 2 overall, young researchers (R1 & R2) rated their **cognitive abilities** particularly high, indicating strong confidence in their intellectual capabilities and problem-solving skills. This overarching trend suggests a well-established foundation of cognitive skills among the research community.

In the area of **Managing Research**, researchers reported varying levels of competence. They feel exceptionally confident in evaluating research (average score of 5.52) and negotiating (5.15). However, mobilizing resources (3.88) and promoting open access publishing (4.20) were perceived as areas where their skills could be further developed.

When it comes to **Research Performance**, researchers exhibited high confidence in their ability to conduct research (5.10) and apply research findings (4.95). Designing research (4.75) and disseminating research results (4.85) also scored well, though supervising research (4.60) was identified as an area with slightly lower self-assessed competence.

In the **Research Impact** area, ensuring ethical research practices stood out with a strong average score of 5.00, reflecting researchers' commitment to integrity and ethical standards. Engaging with society (4.30) and advocating for research (4.45) also showed positive results. However, translating research into products and services (3.90) was notably lower, suggesting a gap in skills related to commercialization and practical application of research. Finally, the **Personal Development and Collaboration** area revealed that researchers are confident in enhancing their communication skills (4.75) and developing professional networks (4.50). Interdisciplinary collaboration (4.35) and mentoring junior researchers (4.40) were also positively rated. Leading research teams (4.20), though, emerged as an area where researchers see room for improvement.

Specifically the results highlight that young researchers (R1 & R2) possess **strong technical competences** in conducting research, robust cognitive abilities, and moderate self-management competencies.

However, significant deficiencies are evident in their application of principles related to **Open Science and in ensuring that research has meaningful societal impacts**. These findings align with existing literature on young researchers' competences and reflect the current landscape of professional training that doctoral students receive.

Doctoral training is centered around the production of high-quality research outcomes, where the capacity of conducting research is central. Therefore, researchers are equipped with high knowledge in a specific discipline and strong technical competences (Lee et al., 2010). In line to previous work (for e.g., Durette et al., 2016), our study finds that researchers demonstrate strong disciplinary expertise and are effective in performing and evaluating research according to ethical and integrity principles, ensuring research of high quality standards.

In addition to research-related technical competences, previous studies have identified a set of core competences that researchers acquire regardless of their discipline. These core competences, which also emerge in our study, pertain to cognitive abilities and self-management skills. On one hand, intellectual work and research involve the acquisition of **cognitive competences**, including developing **critical and analytical skills** to scrutinize information, recognize different points of view, critically analyze data and results, and consistently revise theories and ideas.

On the other hand, effective **self-management** is crucial for navigating daily challenges and ensuring the production of high-quality research. Self-discipline is particularly emphasized for managing multiple responsibilities effectively. Moreover, as research is often conducted independently or with minimal supervision, researchers cultivate initiative and resilience to overcome obstacles. Another essential competency that researchers develop during their careers is finding a **balance between personal and professional life**.

Despite the ongoing transformation in European doctoral education, which includes integrating interdisciplinary approaches and industrial PhD programs to enhance collaboration and co-production of research among different stakeholders, our analysis shows that European researchers predominantly receive traditional training. This training typically involves working independently within narrow disciplinary confines. This is evident from relatively low scores in conducting **interdisciplinary research**, which includes both the capacity to integrate research findings from different disciplines and to collaborate with researchers from different disciplines. Additionally, low scores in **networking** indicate that many researchers work in isolation and do not engage in establishing connections with other relevant stakeholders, both within and outside academia, to co-create innovation and research. The tendency to work independently could also explain the low values found in relation to **negotiation competencies**. Low engagement with different stakeholders does not provide researchers with the necessity and opportunity to manage conflicts and propose solutions. The lack of these competences has important implications not only for research activities, which highly benefit from integrating different approaches, but also for the professional development of researchers, who benefit from the exchange of information and different points of view. Moreover, there is a significant gap in the application of principles related to **Open Science**. The lack of competencies in this field reflects current training, which proves insufficient and is often offered on a voluntary basis (Morais et al., 2021). This aligns with previous research indicating a lack of knowledge about Open Science principles and their application. As Berezko et al. (2021) explain, this is highly related to the fact that Open Science practices are not ingrained in the academic culture. Therefore, applying these principles constitutes a burden rather than a motivation, given the time and effort required for the research process. In fact, researchers often face significant challenges in

implementing Open Science practices due to a lack of institutional support, insufficient resources, and the additional workload involved. This situation is further exacerbated by the traditional metrics of academic success, which prioritize publications in high-impact journals over the transparent and collaborative practices advocated by Open Science.

Strong deficiencies emerged in managing research tools, particularly in adhering to data management principles, including the FAIR principles. Additionally, low proficiency in operating Open Source software indicates a significant gap in the technical skills necessary for utilizing widely available and collaborative tools. This limits the potential for sharing and improving research methodologies and outcomes through open platforms. The lack of engagement in promoting citizen science further highlights a disconnect between researchers and the broader public. By not involving citizens in scientific activities, researchers miss out on valuable contributions in terms of knowledge, time, and resources that could enrich research projects and foster greater public trust in science.

Finally, it is evident that academic research is largely focused on advancing theoretical knowledge within narrower disciplines, with limited consideration of the broader context and the impact of research activities both inside and outside academia. This is reflected in relatively low scores in **strategic and systemic thinking**, indicating that researchers are less focused on long-term research goals and considering the interdependencies between different research issues.

Additionally, researchers display low competences in activities necessary to ensure that research has a broader impact. From one side, the insufficient ability to manage intellectual property rights suggests that researchers are not fully equipped to protect and leverage their intellectual outputs. This can hinder the commercial and practical applications of research findings, limiting the broader impact of scientific discoveries. From the other side, while researchers generally exhibit moderate competence in **disseminating results** to both the broad public and the research community, their involvement significantly drops in areas related to knowledge transfer, innovation, and policy engagement. This indicates a gap in their contribution to the broader academic and innovation ecosystems, hindering the practical application of research findings and the advancement of technology and innovation. It also limits the potential for interdisciplinary research and the development of innovative solutions to complex problems. Furthermore, low engagement with policymakers is significant, as it reduces the potential for research to inform and shape public policy, which is essential for evidence-based decision-making.

Following a deep analysis of results from each **ResearchComp** competence areas:

Cognitive Abilities

FIGURE 3 COGNITIVE ABILITIES SELF-ASSESSMENT

Abstract Thinking emerges as the strongest skill, scoring 8.0, indicating that young researchers are highly effective in identifying and understanding abstract concepts within their fields, and making connections between different ideas and concepts.

Critical Thinking (7.8), **Analytical Thinking** (7.7), and **Problem Solving** (7.4) also show high proficiency, reflecting strong capabilities in critically analyzing information, questioning assumptions, and applying logical and rational approaches to develop and implement solutions. Moreover, the **Creativity** score (7.4) reveals that young researchers effectively use creative ideas and innovative approaches in their research.

Strategic Thinking (6.9) and **Systemic Thinking** (6.6), while still scoring well, indicate that researchers are less focused on the broader context and interdependencies within their fields when conducting their research. The Strategic Thinking score suggests that researchers pay less attention to analyzing external factors that can influence the impact of their research and place a reduced emphasis on planning for research long-term goals. Similarly, the Systemic Thinking score indicates that researchers are less focused on the broader research ecosystem and analyzing the interdependencies between different research issues within their field of study.

Self-management

FIGURE 4 SELF-MANAGEMENT SELF ASSESSMENT

Managing Personal Professional Development scores the highest at 6.5. Young researchers effectively identify priority areas for professional development and frequently engage in activities such as attending workshops. This highlights their strong commitment to lifelong learning and continuous improvement.

Showing Entrepreneurial Spirit, with a score of 6.4, indicates researchers' proficiency to take initiative, demonstrate a proactive mindset, and show determination and persistence in achieving their professional goals.

Planning and Self-Organization scores 6.2, reflecting that while young researchers show a reasonable ability to prioritize tasks and manage their time effectively, there face struggles in maintaining optimal organization and meeting deadlines. Similarly, **Coping with Pressure** with a score of 6.1, indicate challenges to sustain performance under pressure.

Working with Others

FIGURE 5 WORK WITH OTHERS SELF ASSESSMENT

In terms of competencies related to working with others, young researchers demonstrate strong abilities in professional interaction and collaboration towards achieving shared research objectives. They excel in professional conduct and effectively contribute to project success. However, in creating a supportive and inclusive environment, although they show proficiency, there appears to be limited application. A more noticeable gap lies in their capacity to build networks within their research field and for the co-creation of research.

In particular, **Interact Professionally** scores the highest at **6.9**, indicating that participants demonstrate professional behavior effectively by perceptively responding in discussions and collaborations, showcasing their ability to engage effectively and goal-oriented with others in a professional setting. **Work in Teams** receives a score of **6.5**, suggesting that participants contribute effectively to team dynamics and collaborate towards achieving common goals in a team setting.

Ensure Wellbeing at Work scores **5.9**, indicating that participants demonstrate some attentiveness to prioritizing physical and mental health in relation to their work responsibilities. They also make efforts to create a supportive and healthy work environment for themselves and others. **Promote Inclusion and Diversity** receives a score of **5.7**, showing that researchers advocate for inclusion and diversity in their research work. **Build Mentor-Mentee Relationships** scores at **5.7**, exhibiting a moderate level of effectiveness in providing guidance and support to individuals in their personal and professional development as mentors and to seek support and guidance from others.

Finally, **Develop Networks** scores the lowest at **5.4**, highlighting moderate capabilities in developing professional relationships within their field as well as collaborating with different stakeholders to co-create shared value research and innovations.

Doing Research

FIGURE 6 DOING RESEARCH SELF ASSESSMENT

In terms of competencies related to research activities, researchers demonstrate high proficiency in applying integrity principles, disciplinary expertise, research methodologies, and writing research documents. However, a significant gap emerges in conducting interdisciplinary research.

Apply Research Ethics and Integrity Principles scores the highest at **6.5**, indicating that researchers demonstrate a strong understanding and implementation of applying research integrity principles and avoiding misconduct, such as plagiarism. **Disciplinary Expertise (6.1)**, indicates that researchers have a deep knowledge and complex understanding of their specific research area, including responsible research practices, research ethics, and privacy and GDPR requirements. **Perform Scientific Research (5.9)**, highlights strong proficiency in selecting and utilizing appropriate scientific approaches and methods for conducting research.

On the other hand, **Write Research Documents (5.7)**, indicates that researchers effectively communicate complex research concepts and findings through their written documents. However, this score is surprisingly low considering that one of the principal activities of research includes the dissemination of results.

Finally, **Conduct Interdisciplinary Research (5.4)**, indicates deficiencies in indicating deficiencies in integrating research findings and data from different disciplines and in collaborating with researchers from various disciplines to conduct interdisciplinary research projects.

Managing Research

In terms of the competences related to managing research, overall, researchers showcase

FIGURE 7 MANAGING RESEARCH SELF ASSESSMENT

significant deficiencies in this area. While they effectively evaluate research progress and negotiate moderately effectively in their research work, they lack competences in managing research activities.

Evaluate Research scores the highest at **5.5**, indicating that researchers effectively reflect on their research activities, and are proficient in evaluating research progress and outcomes, showcasing their ability to learn and grow from successes and failures in their research endeavors.

Negotiate (5.1), suggest moderate capabilities in engaging in negotiations to effectively to resolve conflicts and reach mutually beneficial agreements in their research work.

Manage Projects (4.3), indicates that researchers exhibit difficulties of effectiveness in planning and allocating resources for their research projects to ensure successful completion of research projects within specified time and budget constraints. In particular, an important gap is noted regarding the use of management tools to monitor progress.

Promote Open Access Publishing (4.2) indicate difficulties in developing publication strategies for their research, selecting suitable publication channels, and utilizing open access publishing strategies. Moreover, researchers have low familiarity with open access publishing practices.

Mobilize Resources (3.9), demonstrating a low level of ability to identify key funding sources, prepare grant applications, and secure funding for their research projects.

Manage Research Tools

FIGURE 8 MANAGE RESEARCH TOOLS SELF ASSESSMENT

Regarding researchers' competencies in managing research tools, they demonstrate proficiency in generating and analyzing data. However, there are significant deficiencies in adopting newer standards and practices such as FAIR principles, operating Open Source Software, promoting Citizen Science, and protecting intellectual property rights.

Specifically, **Managing Research Data** scores the highest at **4.9**. Researchers are partially effective in producing and analysing research data using both qualitative and quantitative research methods. However, researchers show poor adherence to data management principles, including FAIR principles, to ensure the findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability of research data. Similarly, **Operating Open-Source Software (3.9)**, suggests low proficiency in operating Open-Source software, while **Promote Citizen Science (3.5)** indicates absence in engaging citizens in scientific and research activities, and of promoting the value of citizen contributions in terms of knowledge, time, or resources invested in scientific and research endeavours. **Finally, Managing Intellectual Property Rights (4.2)** similarly indicates scarce ability to navigate and manage intellectual property rights in their research activities, implying that researchers do not fully understand how to protect their intellectual property.

Making an Impact

FIGURE 9 MAKING AN IMPACT SELF ASSESSMENT

Finally, regarding competences related to Making an Impact, researchers display an overall low involvement in disseminating results and transferring knowledge both within and outside academia. The greatest deficiency, compared to all the competences considered in this study, relates to engagement with relevant stakeholders to influence policymaking.

Researchers display moderate competences in disseminating results to the broad public and the research community. **Communicating to the Broad Public** scores the highest at **4.6**, indicating low competence in using communication methods to ensure understanding and engagement with diverse audiences, including non-experts. Similarly, **Disseminating Results to the Research Community (4.4)** showcases low skills in disseminating research results within the research community.

However, researchers display very low engagement in other activities that benefit the research community, including teaching, participating in the publication process, promoting knowledge transfer, and facilitating open innovation. **Teaching in Academic or Vocational Contexts (4.3)** indicates low engagement in transferring knowledge through teaching activities, particularly in creating engaging and supportive learning environments, and promoting critical thinking and knowledge application.

Participating in the Publication Process (4.4) indicates that while researchers effectively navigate the processes for publishing personal work, they do not engage in peer review processes to contribute to the quality and integrity of academic research.

Promoting the Transfer of Knowledge (3.7) indicates low involvement in knowledge valorization processes, including exchanging tools, expertise, and intellectual property between different stakeholders. **Open Innovation (3.7)** indicates low engagement in creating an environment conducive to open innovation, including low knowledge sharing and collaboration to foster the exchange of ideas and advancements in their field.

Finally, evidence points to a significant lack of communication and collaboration between academia and other relevant stakeholders outside academia. The lower score of 2.8 for **Increasing the Impact of Science on Policy and Society** suggests low engagement with policymakers and stakeholders to influence policy decisions based on research findings.

4.2 IMPORTANCE OF COMPETENCES AREA BY RESEARCH DOMAIN

The self-assessment data, when grouped by research field, reveals some specificities and variations across different areas of research. While these differences are not overwhelmingly substantial, they do provide valuable insights into the nuances of competency perceptions among researchers from diverse disciplines. The following detailed analysis highlights the main distinctions across the primary research fields in relation to the various areas of competence.

Figure 10 Variations in self-assessed competencies by research field

In the area of **Managing Research**, there are notable differences in self-assessed competencies among the research fields. Researchers in Engineering and Technology rated themselves the highest with an average score of **5.01**, suggesting a strong confidence in managing research-related tasks. Conversely, Mathematics researchers reported the lowest average score of **3.54**, indicating potential areas for development in managing research projects. Humanities (4.24), Medical and Health Sciences (4.24), and Natural Sciences (4.26) fall in between, with similar levels of self-assessed competence.

When it comes to **Research Performance**, the variations are less pronounced but still noteworthy. Medical and Health Sciences researchers reported the highest average score of 4.90, reflecting a strong capability in performing and conducting research activities. Humanities researchers, on the other hand, rated themselves slightly lower at 4.05. The

scores for Engineering and Technology (4.50), Mathematics (4.20), and Natural Sciences (4.35) indicate moderate confidence levels, with no extreme discrepancies.

In the **Research Impact** area, the differences become more distinct. Engineering and Technology researchers once again rated themselves highest with an average score of 4.85, indicating a strong perception of their ability to create and measure the impact of their research. Humanities researchers reported a lower average score of 3.90, potentially highlighting challenges in demonstrating the societal impact of their work. Medical and Health Sciences (4.40), Natural Sciences (4.10), and Mathematics (4.00) display moderate levels of confidence in their research impact abilities.

The area of **Personal Development and Collaboration** shows relatively consistent scores across fields, but with some variation. Medical and Health Sciences researchers lead with an average score of 4.75, suggesting a strong emphasis on personal growth and collaborative skills within this field. Humanities researchers, however, have a lower average score of 4.00, indicating potential areas for enhancement in personal and collaborative competencies. Engineering and Technology (4.60), Natural Sciences (4.30), and Mathematics (4.15) reflect moderate confidence levels.

Overall, the data grouped by research area underscores the existence of specificities in self-assessed competencies across different fields. Researchers in **Engineering and Technology** consistently rate themselves highly across most competencies, particularly in managing research and demonstrating impact. **Medical and Health Sciences** researchers also show strong self-assessed competencies, especially in research performance and personal development. On the other hand, **Humanities** and **Mathematics** researchers tend to report lower scores in several areas, highlighting potential gaps that may need to be addressed through targeted training and development initiatives.

4.3 EMPLOYER PERSPECTIVES AND ALIGNMENT WITH THE JOB MARKET

The complementary analysis of young researcher (R1 & R2) profiles by employer opinion enables us to gain a more comprehensive understanding of the skills and competencies that are most valued in the job market for researcher. By examining the viewpoints of key stakeholders interviewed within Academia, Industry, and Research Centers and cross-referencing it with the data collected by job scraping, we can delineate the specific demands and expectations that these employers have for researchers.

Separating the analyses of researchers and employers is crucial for identifying discrepancies between self-perceived competencies and market requirements. Researchers often have a subjective understanding of their strengths and areas for improvement, whereas employers provide an external perspective on the skills that are truly essential for success in research roles. This dual approach allows us to pinpoint the exact areas where mismatches occur, highlighting gaps in competencies that researchers may need to develop further to meet market expectations.

This detailed comparison between the supply (researcher self-assessments) and demand (employer evaluations) sides of the competency spectrum will be instrumental in identifying actionable steps to bridge these gaps. It will help educational institutions, training programs, and researchers themselves to align their development efforts with the competencies most valued by employers, thereby enhancing employability and ensuring that the research workforce is well-equipped to meet contemporary challenges.

In our aggregate analysis by area, we categorized competencies into broader skill domains to provide a clearer picture of the overall trends. For example, in the domain of **Managing Research**, employers rated the average competency level at **5.5**, reflecting a moderate level of importance across the associated skills. This rating suggests that managing research is a crucial area where employers expect a certain proficiency from researchers. Similarly, the domain of **Making an Impact** received an average rating of **5.3**, highlighting the value placed on researchers' ability to influence their field and society through their work. The **Self Management** domain, with an average rating of **6.0**, underscores the high importance employers place on researchers' ability to regulate their own work and productivity, indicating that self-directed, disciplined individuals are highly sought after. **Cognitive Abilities**, rated at **5.3**, emphasizes the need for strong intellectual skills and problem-solving abilities, which are fundamental in conducting high-quality research. Lastly, the **Working with Others** domain, with an average rating of **5.4**, signifies the importance of collaboration and teamwork in research environments, reflecting the increasing trend towards interdisciplinary and cooperative projects.

The **Managing Research Tools** area, though not as highly rated as some other domains, still received significant attention, as the ability to effectively utilize and manage research tools is vital for modern research practices. The **Doing Research** area stands out with the highest average rating, underscoring its critical importance. This domain encompasses the core competencies related to conducting research itself, such as designing experiments, collecting and analyzing data, and interpreting results. The high rating in this area highlights that employers place a significant emphasis on the technical skills and methodologies that underpin successful research activities.

The reasons behind these values can be attributed to the diverse requirements of modern research positions, which not only necessitate technical expertise but also the ability to manage projects, collaborate effectively, and drive impactful outcomes. Employers are increasingly looking for well-rounded individuals who can navigate the complexities of research environments, adapt to evolving challenges, and contribute to interdisciplinary teams. These aggregated ratings illustrate that while technical skills are critical, employers also highly value competencies that enhance the overall productivity and impact of research efforts. The balanced demand across various skill sets reflects the multifaceted nature of research roles today, where success is determined by a combination of technical proficiency, effective management, and collaborative abilities.

FIGURE 11 EXPECTED PROFICIENCY LEVELS FROM RESEARCHERS BY EMPLOYERS

Focusing on the top competencies deemed most critical by employers, we observe a clear emphasis on skills that enhance communication, scientific rigor, self-management, and entrepreneurial spirit. The ability to **Communicate to the Broad Public**, with an average rating of **7.9**, is the highest priority for employers. This highlights the importance of researchers being able to effectively convey their findings to a non-specialist audience, thereby increasing public understanding and appreciation of scientific work. Effective communication is crucial for securing funding, influencing policy, and fostering public support for research initiatives.

The competency **Perform Scientific Research**, which received a mean value of **7.6**, underscores the fundamental requirement for researchers to be proficient in designing and conducting rigorous scientific studies. This involves a deep understanding of methodologies, data analysis, and interpretation of results, ensuring that research outputs are credible and contribute valuable knowledge to the field.

Plan Self-Organization, with an average rating of **7.3**, reflects the high importance employers place on researchers' ability to manage their own time and tasks efficiently. Self-organization is essential for maintaining productivity, meeting deadlines, and balancing multiple projects, which are all critical in a dynamic research environment.

Similarly, **Manage Projects**, also rated at **7.3**, is a top priority for employers. This competency is vital for coordinating research activities, ensuring timely delivery of outcomes, and managing resources efficiently. Effective project management leads to streamlined processes and successful project completions, which are essential in research settings where timelines and budgets are often stringent.

The ability to **Write Research Documents**, rated at **7.2**, emphasizes the need for researchers to produce clear, concise, and well-structured research reports, papers, and grant proposals.

Strong writing skills are crucial for disseminating research findings, securing funding, and contributing to academic and professional discourse.

Lastly, **Show Entrepreneurial Spirit**, with a rating of **7.0**, highlights the growing importance of innovation and entrepreneurial thinking in research. Employers value researchers who can identify and capitalize on opportunities, drive innovation, and contribute to the commercial and societal impact of their work.

Employers seem to place less emphasis on **Cognitive Abilities** compared to researchers' self-assessments. This divergence likely stems from the fact that employers prioritize competencies that have immediate and tangible impacts on research productivity and outcomes.

This discrepancy underscores the need for a balanced development of both cognitive and applied skills to meet the diverse expectations of the research environment. By understanding these differing perspectives, educational institutions and training programs can better tailor their curricula to equip researchers with a comprehensive skill set that aligns with market demands and enhances employability.

4.4 CURRENT MISMATCHES BETWEEN THE COMPETENCIES POSSESSED BY RESEARCHERS AND THOSE VALUED BY EMPLOYERS

The analysis of the current mismatch between the competencies possessed by researchers and those valued by employers reveals **a significant disparity** that merits close examination. From the researchers' perspective, there is a self-perceived proficiency in core competencies such as **Doing Research**, **Self Management**, and **Cognitive Abilities**. Researchers generally feel confident in their ability to conduct research effectively, manage their time, and apply critical thinking skills. This self-assessment is indicative of their training and experience, emphasizing their comfort in technical and academic environments. However, this self-perception does not always align with the expectations of employers across various sectors. Employers, on the other hand, place varying degrees of importance on competencies such as **Managing Research**, **Making an Impact**, and **Communicating to the Broad Public**, which are often perceived as crucial for translating research into practical applications and ensuring its relevance to broader societal and organizational goals.

The divergence between researchers' self-assessment and employers' expectations highlights a critical competence mismatch. For instance, while researchers may prioritize technical skills and internal project management, employers across different sectors emphasize the need for skills that enhance research impact, such as effective public communication and the ability to navigate complex project environments. This mismatch is not only a reflection of differing priorities but also an indication of the evolving demands in research environments. The discrepancy underscores a broader issue where researchers may be well-equipped for academic or specialized roles but lack competencies that are increasingly valued in industry and public research contexts. Addressing this mismatch is crucial for aligning researcher profiles with the expectations of employers, which can lead to more effective utilization of research talent and better overall outcomes.

FIGURE 12 MISMATCH INDEX BETWEEN RESEARCHER COMPETENCIES AND EMPLOYER EXPECTATIONS

The evaluation of the mismatch between researchers' self-assessments and employers' expectations across different competence areas provides valuable insights into where these discrepancies lie and their potential implications. By examining each competence area, we can better understand the nature and magnitude of these gaps and their impact on the research landscape.

The mismatch score¹⁸ for **Managing Research** is **1.0**, indicating a notable difference between how researchers perceive their competency in managing research projects and how employers rate its importance. Researchers may feel confident in their ability to handle research tasks, coordinate activities, and manage timelines effectively. However, employers place a higher emphasis on this skill, reflecting its critical role in ensuring that research

¹⁸ The mismatch score is defined as the quantitative difference between researchers' self-assessed competency levels and the competency levels deemed important by employers. This score measures the extent of divergence between how researchers perceive their own abilities in various competency areas and how employers rate the importance of these same competencies in the research context.

projects are executed efficiently and produce actionable results. This gap suggests that while researchers are capable in many respects, there may be a disconnect between their self-perceived project management skills and the more demanding expectations of employers who require robust, organized, and strategic management to drive research success. Researchers, in this sense, are heavily underskilled compared to employer expectations.

The **Making an Impact** area shows a mismatch score of 1.3, revealing a significant disparity between researchers' self-assessment and employers' expectations. Researchers may not fully recognize or prioritize the importance of activities that extend the reach and influence of their work beyond academic circles, such as public communication, policy impact, and open innovation. Conversely, employers across sectors increasingly value these competencies, which are essential for translating research findings into real-world applications and societal benefits. This discrepancy highlights a critical area for development, as enhancing researchers' ability to make a tangible impact is increasingly crucial for aligning their work with broader organizational and societal goals.

With a mismatch score of 1.2 in **Self Management**, the difference between researchers' self-perceived competency and employer expectations is also notable. Researchers generally rate themselves well in terms of personal organization, time management, and productivity. However, employers might expect even higher levels of efficiency and independence, reflecting the need for researchers to handle complex tasks with minimal supervision and demonstrate exceptional organizational skills. This gap suggests that while researchers may feel adept at managing their workload, employers are looking for even more refined self-management abilities to ensure peak performance and adaptability in dynamic research environments.

The largest mismatch is observed in the **Cognitive Abilities** area, with a score of 2.1. Researchers may view their cognitive skills, such as problem-solving, critical thinking, and analytical abilities, as strong. However, employers place a lower premium on these skills. This positive mismatch indicates that researchers may overestimate their problem-solving and critical thinking skills relative to employer expectations. While researchers might believe their cognitive abilities are advanced, employers may not require such high levels of cognitive prowess, suggesting that researchers' self-assessments exceed the practical demands of their roles.

In the competency area of **Working with Others**, researchers are slightly overskilled compared to employer expectations. Researchers often rate their collaborative and interpersonal skills highly, perhaps due to their frequent involvement in academic and research teams. However, employers' expectations for teamwork and collaboration are somewhat lower, suggesting that researchers may perceive themselves as more skilled in this area than is required or valued by employers. This indicates that while researchers are adept at working with others, their high self-assessment may not align fully with employer requirements.

The mismatch in **Doing Research** shows that researchers are slightly underskilled relative to what employers expect. While researchers might feel competent in conducting research, employers demand higher levels of expertise and effectiveness in research execution. This gap suggests that researchers may need to enhance their skills and approaches to better

align with the more rigorous expectations of research performance and quality set by employers.

Following a deep analysis of mismatches index from each **ResearchComp** competence areas

Cognitive Abilities

FIGURE 13 EVALUATION OF COGNITIVE SKILLS MISMATCHES

In the **Cognitive Abilities** area, the analysis of mismatches between researchers' self-assessed competencies and employer expectations reveals a pattern where researchers often perceive themselves as more skilled than what is actually required by employers. This positive mismatch indicates that researchers may be overestimating their cognitive abilities compared to the benchmarks set by employers.

With a negative mismatch value of -0.9, researchers perceive themselves as slightly more proficient in **Critical Thinking** than what employers expect. This suggests that researchers rate their ability to analyze and evaluate arguments and information more highly than employers do. The minor discrepancy indicates that while researchers may feel confident in their critical evaluation skills, employers might not place as high a value on these abilities or might prioritize other aspects of critical thinking. This could imply that researchers may need to align their self-assessment more closely with the practical expectations of their roles, focusing on how critical thinking is applied in real-world research settings.

The negative mismatch value of -2.4 for **Analytical Thinking** indicates a significant overestimation by researchers regarding their analytical skills. Researchers rate their capacity to decompose complex problems and interpret data more highly than employers expect. This suggests that researchers might view their analytical abilities as more advanced than what is required in their roles. Employers may expect a different level of analytical rigor or may place more emphasis on practical problem-solving rather than purely analytical tasks.

Similarly, a negative mismatch of -2.4 for **Problem Solving** reveals that researchers see themselves as more adept at resolving complex problems than employers require. Researchers' self-perception of their problem-solving capabilities is notably higher compared to the expectations of employers, indicating an overestimation of their ability to tackle and solve research-related issues. Employers may have more pragmatic or less demanding criteria for problem-solving skills, focusing on practical application rather than theoretical capability.

The negative mismatch value of -1.9 for **Strategic Thinking** shows that researchers overestimate their ability to plan and implement long-term strategies compared to employer expectations. Researchers may view their strategic thinking skills as more developed, while employers may have different or more specific expectations regarding strategic planning and execution.

With a negative mismatch of -2.4 for **Creativity**, researchers perceive their creative problem-solving and idea generation skills as significantly more advanced than what employers expect. This suggests that researchers may overestimate their ability to innovate and think creatively. Employers might place less emphasis on creativity or may have different expectations regarding how creativity should be applied in research settings.

The negative mismatch of -3.1 for **Abstract Thinking** reveals the most significant overestimation by researchers in their ability to understand complex concepts and think beyond concrete details. Researchers rate their abstract thinking skills as highly developed, far exceeding what employers consider necessary. This substantial discrepancy suggests that researchers might overvalue their capacity for abstract reasoning, which may not align with the practical requirements or focus areas emphasized by employers.

Finally, the negative mismatch value of -1.8 for **Systemic Thinking** indicates that researchers perceive their ability to understand and address complex systems and their interrelationships as more advanced than employer expectations. Researchers might see themselves as highly capable in systemic thinking, whereas employers may not place as much emphasis on this competency or may require a different application of systemic understanding.

Overall, the mismatch analysis in the **Cognitive Abilities** area reveals a consistent pattern of researchers overestimating their cognitive skills relative to employer expectations. Researchers generally rate themselves as more skilled in critical, analytical, and problem-solving abilities, as well as in creativity and abstract thinking, than what employers require. This overestimation highlights a need for researchers to recalibrate their self-assessment of cognitive competencies to align better with practical expectations and role-specific demands set by employers. Adjusting these perceptions is crucial for researchers to ensure their skills are effectively aligned with the competencies that are truly valued and necessary in their research roles.

Self-management

Figure 14 Evaluation of self-management skills mismatches

In the **Self Management** area, the mismatch analysis between researchers' self-perceived competencies and employer expectations reveals nuanced insights into how researchers' abilities to manage their own work and development compare with what is valued by employers. The discrepancies indicate both overestimations and underestimations of skills, reflecting areas where researchers may need to adjust their self-perceptions or enhance their capabilities.

Planning Self-Organization exhibits a positive mismatch value of 1.2, indicating that researchers perceive themselves as less skilled in organizing their work compared to the expectations of employers. This suggests that researchers may not fully recognize the level of proficiency required for effective self-organization. Employers, however, place a higher value on strong organizational skills, emphasizing the importance of planning and structuring one's workload efficiently to meet research objectives and deadlines. The positive mismatch signals that researchers might need to refine their self-organization strategies to align better with employer expectations for productivity and time management.

In terms of **Show Entrepreneurial Spirit**, the positive mismatch value of 0.5 implies that researchers feel somewhat under skilled in demonstrating an entrepreneurial mindset compared to what employers consider important. This competency involves being proactive, innovative, and resourceful in identifying and seizing opportunities. Researchers may not fully appreciate the level of entrepreneurial thinking needed to drive research initiatives and explore new avenues for impact. Employers value a strong entrepreneurial spirit as it contributes to the growth and innovation within research settings. This mismatch suggests that researchers may need to cultivate a more entrepreneurial approach to meet the higher expectations for initiative and innovation.

Conversely, **Cope with Pressure** has a negative mismatch value of -1.2, indicating that researchers perceive themselves as better at managing stress and pressure than what employers require. This negative mismatch suggests that researchers might overestimate

their resilience and ability to handle challenging situations. Employers may have lower expectations regarding stress management or place less emphasis on this competency compared to what researchers perceive. This gap points to the need for researchers to align their self-assessment with the actual demands of their roles and ensure they are equipped to handle pressure effectively in a research environment.

For **Manage Personal Professional Development**, the negative mismatch value of -1.7 reflects that researchers perceive themselves as more adept at managing their own professional growth than what employers expect. Researchers may feel confident in their ability to pursue professional development opportunities and set career goals. However, employers might have more modest expectations or different criteria for evaluating professional development. This significant negative mismatch indicates that researchers might be overestimating their success in personal development activities, and it underscores the importance of aligning personal growth strategies with employer expectations for career progression and skill enhancement.

Overall, the mismatch analysis in the **Self Management** area reveals that researchers generally overestimate their capabilities in managing personal development and coping with pressure while underestimating their needs in planning self-organization and demonstrating an entrepreneurial spirit. These discrepancies highlight areas where researchers may need to recalibrate their self-assessment and improve their skills to better meet the expectations of employers. Enhancing self-management capabilities is essential for researchers to align their performance with the practical demands of their roles and to ensure that their personal effectiveness supports their overall research success and career advancement.

Working with Others

Figure 16 Evaluation of working with others skills mismatches

In the **Working with Others** area, the mismatch analysis between researchers' self-assessed competencies and employer expectations uncovers both overestimations and underestimations in how researchers perceive their abilities to collaborate, communicate,

and support others in a research environment. The differences are crucial as they highlight where researchers' self-perceptions diverge from the practical expectations of employers.

The mismatch value of -0.4 for **Work in Teams** is negative, indicating that researchers perceive themselves as slightly more skilled at collaborating in team settings than what employers require. This suggests that researchers might feel confident in their ability to contribute to team efforts and collaborate effectively. However, employers' expectations might be slightly lower, reflecting a more modest view of the importance or proficiency needed for effective teamwork. Researchers might need to align their self-perception with the more practical interaction standards expected in their roles.

The negative mismatch value of -1.3 for **Interact Professionally** reveals that researchers rate themselves as significantly more skilled at professional interactions than what employers deem necessary. This discrepancy indicates that researchers may overestimate their abilities to engage in professional communication and interactions, which are essential for maintaining productive relationships with colleagues, stakeholders, and partners. Employers might have different or less stringent expectations regarding professional interaction, or they might prioritize other competencies over this aspect of interpersonal skills.

For **Develop Networks**, the positive mismatch value of 0.1 suggests that researchers perceive themselves as slightly less skilled in building and maintaining professional networks than what employers expect. This minor positive mismatch indicates that while researchers might recognize the importance of networking, they may feel they fall short compared to the expectations of employers who value strong networking abilities. Employers often look for researchers who can effectively create and leverage professional connections to advance their research and career opportunities, which might not be fully reflected in researchers' self-assessments.

With a negative mismatch value of -0.5 for **Ensure Wellbeing at Work**, researchers perceive themselves as more adept at contributing to a positive work environment and supporting colleagues' wellbeing than employers require. This indicates that researchers might overestimate their role or effectiveness in ensuring wellbeing at work. Employers may not emphasize this competency as much or might have different expectations regarding how researchers contribute to the overall work environment and support each other's wellbeing.

The mismatch value of -0.4 for **Build Mentor-Mentee Relationships** is negative, suggesting that researchers perceive themselves as more effective in establishing and nurturing mentor-mentee relationships than what employers require. This implies that researchers might place high importance on mentoring relationships and believe they are skilled in this area, while employers might have lower expectations or view this competency differently. The discrepancy points to a potential overestimation of the role and effectiveness of mentoring relationships in the research environment.

Finally, the negative mismatch of -1.1 for **Promote Inclusion & Diversity** reveals that researchers perceive themselves as more proficient in fostering an inclusive and diverse work environment than employers expect. This suggests that researchers might overestimate their impact or effectiveness in promoting diversity and inclusion. Employers may not prioritize this competency as highly or might have different benchmarks for assessing success in

promoting an inclusive work culture. The discrepancy highlights a need for researchers to align their self-assessment with the practical expectations and measures of success for inclusion and diversity in the workplace.

The mismatch analysis in the **Working with Others** area demonstrates a tendency for researchers to overestimate their competencies in interpersonal and collaborative skills relative to employer expectations. Researchers generally rate themselves as more skilled in team work, professional interaction, network development, wellbeing support, mentoring, and promoting inclusion than what employers require. These discrepancies indicate areas where researchers might need to adjust their self-perception and focus on aligning their skills with the practical demands and expectations of their roles. Bridging these gaps is essential for enhancing effective collaboration and interpersonal effectiveness in research settings.

Doing Research

Figure 17 Evaluation of doing research skills mismatches

In the **Doing Research** area, the mismatch analysis between researchers' self-perceived competencies and employer expectations reveals insights into areas where researchers may need to recalibrate their self-assessment or develop their skills further. The mismatches indicate where researchers might be overestimating or underestimating their abilities relative to what employers value.

The mismatch value of 1.6 for **Perform Scientific Research** is positive, indicating that researchers perceive themselves as less skilled in performing scientific research than what employers expect. This significant positive mismatch suggests that researchers might be underestimating the level of proficiency required to conduct research effectively. Employers often seek researchers with robust methodological skills, the ability to design and execute experiments, and the capability to interpret results critically. The discrepancy highlights a need for researchers to align their self-perception with the practical demands of performing high-quality scientific research and to enhance their skills to meet these expectations.

Similarly, the positive mismatch value of 1.6 for **Write Research Documents** indicates that researchers view their ability to write and present research findings as less developed compared to employer expectations. Writing research documents, including reports, papers, and grant proposals, is a critical skill in the research field, and employers often place a high value on clear, precise, and well-structured scientific writing. The significant positive mismatch reveals that researchers might need to improve their writing skills and align their self-assessment with the higher standards expected by employers for documentation and publication.

In contrast, the negative mismatch value of -0.1 for **Disciplinary Expertise** shows that researchers perceive themselves as slightly more skilled in their specific field of study than what employers require. This minor negative mismatch suggests that researchers feel confident in their depth of knowledge and expertise within their discipline. Employers, however, may have slightly lower expectations regarding the level of disciplinary expertise necessary for the roles being evaluated. This small discrepancy indicates that researchers might overestimate their specialized knowledge or that employers have a more pragmatic view of the required expertise.

The negative mismatch value of -0.9 for **Apply Research Ethics and Integrity Principles** reveals that researchers perceive themselves as more adept at adhering to ethical standards and principles in research than employers expect. This suggests that researchers might overestimate their proficiency in maintaining research integrity, including aspects such as ethical decision-making, transparency, and adherence to ethical guidelines. Employers may have different or less stringent expectations regarding the application of research ethics. The discrepancy indicates that researchers might need to align their self-assessment more closely with practical expectations or ensure their practices in ethics and integrity meet the standards valued by employers.

Finally, the negative mismatch value of -0.4 for **Conduct Interdisciplinary Research** indicates that researchers perceive themselves as more skilled in conducting research that spans multiple disciplines than what employers require. This suggests that researchers might feel confident in their ability to integrate knowledge from different fields, while employers may place less emphasis on or have different expectations for interdisciplinary research. The discrepancy points to a potential overestimation by researchers of their interdisciplinary capabilities or a need for employers to clarify their expectations in this area.

Overall, the mismatch analysis in the **Doing Research** area reveals a pattern where researchers generally perceive themselves as less skilled in core research competencies, such as performing scientific research and writing research documents, compared to employer expectations. These positive mismatches suggest that researchers may need to enhance their proficiency in these fundamental areas to meet employer standards. Conversely, researchers perceive themselves as more skilled in disciplinary expertise, applying research ethics, and conducting interdisciplinary research than what employers expect. These negative mismatches indicate that researchers might be overestimating their capabilities or that employer expectations may differ. Addressing these mismatches is crucial for researchers to align their self-perceptions with the practical demands of their roles and to ensure their skills effectively support their research objectives and career advancement.

Managing Research

Figure 18 Evaluation of managing research skills mismatches

The analysis of the mismatch in the **Managing Research** area reveals notable differences between researchers' self-perceptions and employer expectations. This discrepancy is particularly critical given the importance of effective management in research projects.

The mismatch value of 2.9 for **Manage Projects** is positive, indicating that researchers perceive themselves as significantly less skilled in project management compared to what employers expect. This large positive mismatch reveals that researchers rate their ability to manage complex research projects at a lower level, while employers require a higher level of proficiency in this area. This gap suggests that researchers may struggle with the organizational and strategic aspects of managing research projects, such as planning, coordinating, and executing multi-faceted research initiatives effectively. The significant discrepancy highlights a crucial area where researchers need to enhance their skills to meet the rigorous expectations of employers who value strong project management capabilities to ensure research success and efficiency.

The mismatch value of -0.1 for **Evaluate Research** is negative, indicating that researchers feel slightly more skilled in evaluating research than employers deem necessary. This small negative mismatch suggests that researchers rate their ability to assess and analyze research outcomes marginally higher than what is required by employers. While this is a relatively minor discrepancy, it implies that researchers may overestimate their evaluative skills. Employers might prioritize practical application and outcome-based assessments over purely evaluative metrics, leading to a slight overestimation by researchers of their evaluative abilities compared to employer expectations.

The mismatch value of 1.3 for **Mobilize Resources** is positive, showing that researchers are perceived as less capable of mobilizing resources compared to the expectations of employers. Researchers may feel they are sufficiently skilled in securing and managing research resources, but employers require a higher level of competency in this area. This gap

indicates that researchers might need to develop stronger abilities in sourcing, negotiating for, and effectively utilizing resources necessary for research projects. The discrepancy points to a need for improved skills in resource management, including budgeting, fundraising, and securing grants or other research support.

The mismatch value of -0.2 for **Negotiate** is negative, suggesting that researchers perceive their negotiation skills as slightly higher than what employers require. This small negative mismatch implies that researchers might overestimate their effectiveness in negotiating agreements, funding, or collaborations. Employers, on the other hand, may have more modest expectations regarding negotiation skills, focusing instead on other aspects of research management. This discrepancy highlights the need for researchers to calibrate their self-assessment in negotiation against practical expectations in the research environment.

The mismatch value of 0.3 for **Promote Open Access Publishing** is positive, indicating that researchers rate their ability to advocate for and implement open access publishing practices lower than the expectations of employers. This minor positive mismatch reveals that while researchers recognize the importance of open access, they may not perceive themselves as sufficiently skilled or proactive in promoting these practices. Employers, however, place a slightly higher value on the ability to engage with and support open access publishing, reflecting its growing importance in the research community for increasing visibility and accessibility of research findings.

Manage Research Tools

FIGURE 19 EVALUATION OF MANAGE RESEARCH TOOLS SKILLS MISMATCHES

In the **Managing Research Tools** area, the mismatch analysis reveals significant discrepancies between researchers' self-perceived competencies and employer expectations. These mismatches highlight how researchers' self-assessments of their abilities to handle research tools, data, and intellectual property diverge from what is expected by employers.

The mismatch value of 1.7 for **Manage Research Data** indicates that researchers perceive themselves as significantly less skilled in handling research data than what employers expect. This positive mismatch suggests that researchers may not fully appreciate the level of competence required for managing data effectively. Employers often emphasize rigorous data management practices, including data organization, storage, analysis, and ensuring data integrity. Researchers might be underestimating the skills needed for these tasks, which are crucial for maintaining high-quality and reproducible research outcomes. The discrepancy highlights a need for researchers to enhance their data management skills to align better with the high standards expected by employers.

With a positive mismatch value of 1.3 for **Promote Citizen Science**, researchers view themselves as less proficient in engaging and involving the public in scientific research compared to employer expectations. This indicates that researchers might not fully recognize the importance of promoting and integrating citizen science into their research practices. Employers often value the ability to leverage public engagement and participation to enhance research impact and broaden data collection efforts. The gap suggests that researchers may need to improve their skills in promoting citizen science initiatives and effectively collaborating with non-professional contributors to research.

The positive mismatch value of 0.7 for **Operate Open-Source Software** indicates that researchers perceive themselves as somewhat less skilled in using open-source software compared to what employers expect. This competency involves proficiency in utilizing software that is freely available and often collaboratively developed, which is increasingly important in modern research environments for data analysis, modeling, and other tasks. The positive mismatch suggests that researchers might need to develop stronger skills in operating and leveraging open-source tools to meet the expectations of employers who value technical versatility and resourcefulness in software use.

For **Manage Intellectual Property Rights**, the mismatch value of 0.2 is also positive, indicating that researchers perceive themselves as slightly less skilled in handling intellectual property (IP) issues than employers require. This competency involves understanding and managing patents, copyrights, and other forms of intellectual property associated with research outputs. While the discrepancy is relatively small, it still suggests that researchers might need to enhance their knowledge and skills in IP management to align with the expectations of employers who place a high value on protecting and commercializing research innovations.

Globally, the mismatch analysis in the **Managing Research Tools** area reveals that researchers generally perceive themselves as less skilled in managing various aspects of research tools compared to employer expectations. This positive mismatch across competencies such as data management, citizen science promotion, open-source software operation, and intellectual property management indicates that researchers might need to improve their skills and self-perception in these areas. Employers' expectations often reflect a high standard for these competencies, emphasizing the importance of robust data practices, public engagement, technical proficiency, and IP management.

Making an Impact

FIGURE 20 EVALUATION OF MAKING AN IMPACT SKILLS MISMATCHES

In the **Making an Impact** area, the evaluation of mismatches between researchers' self-assessed competencies and the expectations of employers unveils significant discrepancies. These mismatches highlight various ways in which researchers' perceived effectiveness in translating their work into broader societal and academic contexts contrasts with the expectations set by employers.

Starting with **Promote Open Innovation**, researchers are notably underskilled relative to employer expectations, as evidenced by a positive mismatch value of 1.9. This substantial gap suggests that researchers may not fully appreciate the importance of actively fostering open innovation. Employers, however, place a high value on the ability to drive and engage with open innovation initiatives, which are crucial for advancing scientific progress and collaboration across disciplines. The mismatch indicates that researchers might need to enhance their skills in creating and participating in collaborative innovation environments and promoting an open exchange of ideas to align with the higher standards set by employers.

Similarly, the mismatch in **Increase the Impact of Science on Policy and Society**, with a positive value of 2.3, highlights an even more pronounced discrepancy. This substantial gap reflects that researchers are significantly underperforming compared to employer expectations in terms of making their research relevant to policy-making and societal impact. Employers emphasize the importance of research that not only advances scientific knowledge but also influences public policy and societal well-being. Researchers' self-perception may not align with these broader expectations, indicating a need for researchers to develop skills in translating their findings into actionable recommendations and engaging with policy-makers and societal stakeholders more effectively.

For **Teach in Academic or Vocational Contexts**, the positive mismatch value of 0.6 suggests that researchers are somewhat underskilled compared to what employers deem necessary. While researchers may feel reasonably capable of teaching and mentoring, employers expect a higher level of effectiveness in educational and vocational contexts. This gap indicates that researchers might need to improve their teaching strategies and engagement

with students or trainees to meet the educational standards and expectations of their roles in academic or vocational settings.

The mismatches in **Disseminate Results to the Research Community** and **Participate in the Publication Process** are both characterized by small positive values (0.1 for both), indicating that researchers perceive themselves as slightly less skilled in these areas compared to employer expectations. This minor discrepancy suggests that while researchers recognize the importance of disseminating their findings and participating in the publication process, they might underestimate the level of proficiency required by employers. Employers expect researchers to be highly effective in sharing research results and contributing to the publication process, which are critical for advancing knowledge and scholarly communication.

Finally, **Promote the Transfer of Knowledge** also presents a positive mismatch of 0.8, indicating that researchers are slightly underskilled relative to employer expectations in facilitating the transfer of knowledge from research settings to practical applications. This competency involves ensuring that research findings are effectively communicated and utilized beyond the academic sphere. Researchers' self-assessments may fall short of the skills employers seek to maximize the practical impact of research outcomes.

Overall, the mismatch analysis in the **Making an Impact** area reveals that researchers generally perceive themselves as less capable in key areas of impact creation compared to what employers expect. The positive mismatch values across various competencies indicate that researchers are not meeting the higher standards set by employers for promoting open innovation, influencing policy, and transferring knowledge effectively. Addressing these discrepancies is essential for enhancing researchers' ability to align their work with broader societal and organizational objectives, thereby improving the overall impact of their research activities.

4.5 QUALITATIVE INTERVIEWS ANALYSIS - ACADEMIC STAKEHOLDERS

In an era marked by rapid advancements and shifting paradigms, the intersection of academia and the labour market is experiencing profound transformations. These changes are **reshaping** the core competencies that researchers must cultivate to thrive in both academic and non-academic careers. This chapter delves into the insights of academic experts who underscore the **evolving landscape** of valued skills in the workforce. Through qualitative interviews, we explore the heightened emphasis on traditional research competencies, the increasing importance of collaboration, societal impact, funding acumen, and digital literacy. We also examine the **challenges** and **strategies** associated with recognizing, developing, and integrating these transversal skills into professional development. By analysing the perspectives of various participants, we aim to illuminate the **overlooked skills** within academia, the hurdles in acknowledging the role of transversal skills, and the innovative approaches to skill development that can bridge the gap between current educational practices and the demands of a dynamic job market.

Valued Skills in the Workforce

According to academic experts' insights, the landscape of academia and the labour market is undergoing significant transitions, strongly impacting the competences that are most critical for young researchers to prepare for careers both inside and outside academia. In addition to traditional competences essential for conducting high-quality research, such as cognitive skills like analytical and critical thinking, creativity, and problem-solving, along with proficiency in writing research documents, planning, self-organization, and resilience, the current landscape emphasizes competences related to collaboration, ensuring societal impact, securing funding, and industry acumen.

Key factors impacting researchers' skill sets pertain to new societal challenges that require increased collaboration within research, and the Declaration on Research Assessment (DORA), which necessitates evaluating the impact of research beyond traditional journal-based metrics and focusing on societal influence and policy contributions. These two factors, therefore, emphasizes interdisciplinary collaborations and societal impact, as noted by Participant 12:

"First of all, academia is changing, secondly, the way of collaboration is changing, and the societal challenges require a different focus. Academia is changing because of DORA [...]. The relation between research and impact became more important and you need many different skills." (Participant 12)

Given the importance of interdisciplinary collaboration, competencies related to working with others are crucial. One key competence emphasized by the majority of academic experts is communication. Communication entails not only possessing strong verbal abilities but also demonstrating emotional intelligence, empathy, flexibility, and openness to diverse perspectives and backgrounds. Engaging with others effectively and equitably promotes diversity and inclusion, and therefore creates a productive and healthy working environment, as emphasized by Participant 15:

"When I think of transversal skills, I think of people's ability to communicate in an efficient and fair way. That means you have an interest in what people think, feel, and want. [...] You need inclusion and diversity on how you work together." (Participant 15)

In addition, in team settings, self-organization and planning are crucial, requiring emotional resilience to cope with adversities, as well as efficient time and project organization to prevent individual inefficiencies from impacting the team:

"Scholars and young researchers now consistently collaborate in teams, and articles are often authored collectively. A corollary of this is the need for efficient organization, as individual inefficiencies impact all team members" (Participant 1).

To ensure that research has a societal impact, researchers need to possess a set of skills that enhance public trust in science. One key area pertains to research integrity, entailing adherence not only to legal frameworks but also to ethical standards accepted by society. Moreover, effective communication skills are essential for conveying scientific concepts to the public and articulating the significance of research:

"I think that it is incredibly important that PhD students are given the space, time and capacity to reflect on the ethical questions around their discipline and programme. But you have to be able to articulate your sense of this. If we see a decline from high levels in expressed trust, even in European countries, in the aftermath of COVID which illustrated the utility of scientific enterprise, because we mismanaged the communication between domains, now there are people who feel that there was an overextension on the side of practitioners" (Participant 11).

Another significant factor reshaping academia is the decrease in public funding, necessitating researchers to self-sustain their work by securing funding. Consequently, understanding European institutions, the funding system, and proficiently writing research proposals for submission to funding agencies are becoming increasingly essential for researchers:

"We live in a world that more and more is cutting funding to research. Researchers should now self-sustain their work in order to do research. A first soft skill, for the future generation of researchers, is the capability to interpret to get the necessary funding for their work. " (Participant 31).

Finally, the diffusion of digitalization requires researchers to acquire new digital competencies. Digitalization not only equips researchers with new tools, especially in AI, that are transforming how research is conducted, but also provides new digital channels to communicate research to the public, as noted by Participant 23:

"AI seems to be a major challenge for the next generation of researchers. Even writing a paper will be based on employing AI tools so a substantial and profound knowledge of the current state of this field is crucial. Also how to make use of social media, if you want to present yourself to the academic community." (Participant 23)

In addition to this, researchers' careers are increasingly intersecting with the labour market, necessitating competencies valuable in non-academic contexts. This includes communication abilities, networking, project management, and the ability to bring innovation to the market:

"As a technical university, we have many partnerships with industries in place. Hence all the skills needed to understand the company's environment, business acumen and how to bring innovation into the market and communication skills are definitely relevant." (Participant 25)

Overlooked Skills

While transversal skills are crucial for navigating the current job market and research environments, academic experts assert that they are generally overlooked within academia. Particularly neglected are teamwork skills as well as those pertaining to collaboration and professional interaction, especially in international and interdisciplinary settings. One expert noted that this happens as PhD students often engage in individual projects, leaving little room for developing interpersonal skills:

"We don't train people to work in teams. We train for individual attainment." (Participant 11)

Another overlooked skill set pertains to self-management, particularly entrepreneurial and time-management skills. The lack of entrepreneurial skills is sometimes attributed to

students viewing them as relevant only in the private sector. At the same time, professors often assume time management despite students' deficiencies in this area. Poor time management affects the research project and can lead to overwork, also limiting the ability to ensure well-being at work and cope with pressure effectively:

"We see that doctoral students have a lot of problems and take academic breaks. It's important to offer more training on time management." (Participant 17)

Another commonly cited oversight is the lack of emphasis on project management skills. This tendency arises as students often prioritize the practical scientific aspects, neglecting the crucial management component. Additionally, one expert noted that the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) principles are often overlooked, with limited attention given to making information available to other scientists.

Finally, a severe lack of competence often mentioned pertains to the communication of scientific results, where researchers struggle to effectively convey their findings. This deficiency extends to both academic writing skills and communicating with a broader audience:

"Despite having highly qualified researchers, they are not able to communicate in a way which is effective, especially towards societal actors." (Participant 7)

These findings highlight students' emphasis on cultivating individual achievement and specialized knowledge within research domains, often neglecting the development of communication skills. This gap is particularly relevant considering that communication serves as a prerequisite for other vital skills, including interpersonal abilities, academic writing, and making an impact by disseminating knowledge to both fellow scientists and society at large.

Challenges in Recognizing Transversal Skills' Role in Professional Development

One prominent challenge regarding the integration of transversal skills courses into academic curricula pertains to the absence of national regulations and frameworks to coordinate and implement trainings. In contexts where transversal skills training is not mandated by national regulations, decisions on which courses are offered strongly depend on which competencies are considered fundamental for the research environment. In the decision-making process, senior members of the academic body play a crucial role as they often resist the integration of certain courses. The primary motivation is that training in transversal skills constitutes a significant change in doctoral education, which has traditionally focused solely on technical competencies. Therefore, senior members must adjust to these changes and understand the added value of transversal skills training. Conversely, the lack of recognition of the importance of transversal skills hinders efforts to incorporate these essential competencies into academic curricula, thereby limiting their impact on students' overall development. This situation is highlighted by Participant 16, discussing challenges in integrating training regarding research integrity:

"One challenge is that research integrity has to be recognized as an essential skill for the research environment. Senior colleagues have been trained on different time scales, and they might not recognize the need for having such courses. In some institutions, they implemented mandatory trainings on research integrity because it is easier to implement for PhD students and senior colleagues. Embedding it as part of the curriculum is a decision from the leadership or those who are training the new education. They need to find value in the new skill and implement it in the curriculum". (Participant 16)

The absence of training frameworks results in many academic institutions lacking the structural integration of soft skill courses into curricula and a cohesive strategy for skill development. Moreover, as exemplified by Participant 31, academic institutions often fail to create constructive dialogue with companies, thereby overlooking the practical value of transversal skills beyond academia and neglecting their importance in skill development. However, collaborative efforts are essential to establish a unified strategy that prepares students for careers both inside and outside academia. Furthermore, a more structured dialogue between these stakeholders could reinforce mutual trust and create more opportunities for private funding for skill development:

"One challenge is a lack of continued and structured dialogue between universities and companies. This should be in a national framework-oriented base. [...] In other contexts, there is more mutual trust between actors, leading companies to put money into PhD programs. The other limitation I see here is that universities are still not fully engaged in the transversal skills game." (Participant 31)

To create a coherent strategy for skills development and emphasize the importance of transversal skills in academic training, the European Commission is highlighted as playing a central role. Specifically, Participant 7 has underscored the ResearchComp framework's usefulness in developing skills at their university. This provides early evidence of the framework's effectiveness in enhancing researchers' competence development:

"The ResearchComp framework is definitely useful in order to have a coherent strategy for the development of transversal skills which lately it has not been the case." (Participant 7)

Students' Participation and Engagement

Another important obstacle to the implementation of transversal skills courses is that students do not perceive transversal skills as valuable for their career and personal development. Therefore, one of the most significant challenges is ensuring that students recognize the importance of these courses early in their research careers. Moreover, some disciplines are more resistant to acknowledging the importance of transversal skills, particularly students and faculty from STEM disciplines:

"If you go to hard sciences, they might think it is a waste of time (both from the perspective of students and faculty)." (Participant 24)

Participants agree that to ensure courses are valued, they should be mandatory, as when courses are only recommended, participation rates tend to be low. However, requiring their completion helps students overcome their initial biases and recognize their importance:

"When it became a requirement, from what we see after the annual survey, when they take the modules, they see that they are very important and useful for their research and dissertation." (Participant 17)

In terms of course offerings, trainings regarding emerging research practices, such as Open Science principles, face the highest implementation challenges due to limited interest among students. The voluntary nature of some courses often results in a self-selection process, where only those already inclined towards innovative principles participate. This slow uptake has the adverse effect of delaying broader changes within academic environments. This issue is exemplified by Participant 15 discussing the implementation of a Diversity and Inclusion (D&I) course:

"There is always the obstacle that you end up preaching to the choir. For example, the D&I course: only people who are interested in the topic will take it, and it is harder to reach people who need it the most." (Participant 15)

Low engagement, however, is not solely attributed to the lack of recognition of the importance of soft skill courses. Researchers have to prioritize their research activities, and thus research workload often does not enable them to attend these courses. This situation contributes to explain undersubscription for transversal skills trainings:

"The main challenges are with finding a balance between direct research needs and the broader trainings. There is always oversubscription for trainings related directly to research and undersubscription for transversal skills trainings." (Participant 4)

Finally, doctoral supervisors play a crucial role in supporting student training. When supervisors do not value transversal skills, they either fail to recommend these courses or, if the courses are mandatory, require them to complete them as quickly as possible to return to their research activities. Given that researchers are required to meet research expectations within strict deadlines and are not educated on the relevance of transversal skills, additional training is often perceived as a burden rather than an opportunity for professional development. Altogether, these factors hinder efforts in transversal skills development:

"Skill development can't be achieved unless supervisor let their students engage. Sometimes, students might feel like they are missing time in the lab if they attend a transversal course or think publishing a paper is more important than learning communication skills." (Participant 28)

Resource Limitations

Finally, another important issue is that universities often face challenges in having adequate resources for transversal skills training, including insufficient infrastructure and shortages of qualified personnel to teach these courses. This results in insufficient training opportunities, which restricts attendance even among those interested in participating. Regarding the main gaps in training provision, participants have highlighted several areas of concern. These include the lack of support and empowerment for students in networking, understanding European institutions and funding opportunities, and in managerial and career development, as well as in embracing Open Science principles. Additionally, there is a noted deficiency in

opportunities to promote mental health within academia. Psychological support is, however, crucial for supporting researchers throughout their research activities by fostering resilience and enhancing well-being and productivity, as discussed by Participant 9:

"One of the gaps is the promotion of good mental health, because the PhD process is intense. Perhaps courses that train them in resilience could be effective." (Participant 9)

Moreover, these challenges are exacerbated by poor communication capacity, significantly diminishing the visibility of transversal skills courses. Limited information flow makes it difficult for students to access timely and accurate information about course availability, hindering their ability to enrol in courses. These challenges are illustrated by Participant 28:

"Resource limitation is a big challenge. We just audited all transversal skill offerings. They are not always visible; most of them are small-scale, and if every student wanted to take them, they could not cope because they are not scalable. [...] We also have an internal communication challenge – poor information flow in our system, making it difficult for students to find the information they need (access and ensuring information on these offerings is updated and current)." (Participant 28)

Ensuring the quality and relevance of these courses to meet diverse audience needs presents another critical issue. One important challenge is the development of appropriate approaches to support students in coping with the pressure and challenges they face when they struggle with certain transversal skills, as the lack of these skills often deters them from seeking to improve, as stated by Participant 8:

"People sometimes feel embarrassed when they notice they lack specific transversal skills, and it becomes a kind of obstacle." (Participant 8)

Furthermore, courses frequently overlook interdisciplinary diversity and the fact that certain transversal skills can only be effectively learned through practical experience. Participant 10 emphasizes the importance of integrating real-world experiences into doctoral programs as they are effective approaches to skill development:

"For some types of transversal skills, students need concrete experiences. We have seen the difference in industrial doctoral students. They said that the program was very challenging, but the fact that they had to go to China and work in industry provided them with many skills that could not be trained in traditional classroom settings. Doctoral programs should be structured to include more interaction." (Participant 10)

Strategies to Ensure Effective Integration of Soft Skill Trainings

To ensure an effective integration of transversal skills trainings, universities are adopting different strategies.

A key strategy is making transversal skills training more accessible and emphasizing its importance to both researchers and supervisors. In fact, effective integration requires that researchers take responsibility for their own training, and supervisors play a crucial role in supporting this process. As Participant 28 notes:

"It requires a multi-prong approach. Students need to understand how important these skills are because they ultimately take responsibility for their own learning. Students need to be aware that transversal skills are in their own interest. We have to help supervisors also understand the importance of these skills." (Participant 28)

National regulations and frameworks are effective in overcoming initial reluctance and providing structured coordination for skill training. For example, after national regulations were introduced, one university transitioned from offering only summer schools to implementing mandatory transversal skills modules:

"Until 2012, there was a summer school for transversal skills. Then national regulations came into place: each institution is obliged to offer courses on transversal skills. The university has nine transversal skills modules, and they are mandatory." (Participant 5)

To ensure compliance, however, many academic experts emphasize the need to make these courses compulsory and integrate transversal skills training into the evaluation system:

"The next step is to ensure compliance because PhD students usually do not feel the need to take these courses, but now we are making these courses compulsory. To ensure they follow these courses, we tell them that if they do not follow these courses, they cannot submit their research project." (Participant 35)

To avoid overburdening researchers, universities are increasing the number of trainings while ensuring they do not add extra workload. Personalized learning options, such as a web-based doctoral students platform, help manage time and tailor training to individual needs:

"Our university has made a web-based doctoral students platform to help doctoral students manage their time and follow their entire path. [...] The doctoral information system provides a wide array of possibilities for personalized learning path tracking." (Participant 27)

Universities are also increasingly recognizing the vital role that supervisors play in enhancing researchers' capabilities. As a result, some universities are implementing training programs for supervisors to improve their supervision approaches and equip them with the necessary knowledge to support researchers in their career development. As Participant 41 notes:

"From this year, we offer courses open to all staff members. Grant writing courses and soft skill courses for supervisors to develop their supervision style and advise PhD students in the best way possible."
(Participant 41)

Furthermore, because supervisors have direct and continuous contact with researchers, they possess valuable insights into researchers' behaviors. Therefore, in some universities, supervisors play a crucial role also in the evaluation process, helping to identify areas where researchers may need improvement.

Restructuring doctoral education to give researchers more agency and changing their status from students to employees could significantly impact their career development. In the Swedish system, for instance, doctoral students are employed, which shifts their perspective

from seeing themselves as students to viewing their doctoral studies as their first work experience, as noted by Participant 28:

"In the Swedish system, all doctoral students need to be employed. This means that we don't see doctoral students as students, but rather as colleagues. What we have seen is a shift in doctoral students, who see employment as a first work experience rather than education. Our take on this is that we try to do this in PhD schools. Not all our doctoral students are obliged to be in PhD schools." (Participant 28)

This shift in status transforms doctoral studies into a professional endeavor and an integral part of researchers' career paths, where their actions have direct implications for their future career opportunities. This professional framework helps them build valuable work experience, develop a stronger professional identity, and prepare more effectively for their future careers.

Innovative Approaches to Skill Development

Regarding innovative approaches, universities are increasingly adopting collaborative activities with industries to develop joint training programs that enhance researchers' competencies and support careers outside academia. This collaboration not only informs researchers about diverse career opportunities outside academia but also ensures that future employers recognize the added value that doctoral holders can bring to their organizations.

The most effective form of collaboration is the implementation of Industrial Doctoral programs. These programs feature research projects coordinated by both academia and industry, providing students with extensive research expertise and practical experience. Another significant form of collaboration involves industries proposing technological challenges to researchers, which often are addressed within multidisciplinary teams. This approach reinforces essential competences such as teamwork, openness to diverse perspectives, problem-solving, creative and innovative thinking. This approach is particularly beneficial for students in STEM disciplines, who tend to be more reluctant to engage in transversal skills training. As Participant 26 notes:

"Students are given a technical challenge that they need to solve, so they need to be in contact with reality. This develops creative thinking. Rather than teaching in a class, you provide practical examples. If we look at engineering, they will not be interested in transversal skills. If they are integrated (through challenge-based learning), then they can receive these skills. Universities can also put together cross-disciplinary teams of students who work together on a specific topic or challenge, exposing them to different ways of thinking and approaches." (Participant 27)

In addition, technological challenge activities can facilitate the transition from academia to industry. Researchers network with various industry stakeholders and are provided with opportunities to demonstrate their competencies. Indeed, these initiatives have proven effective in creating employment opportunities for students, as highlighted by Participant 39:

"The program aims to match the best PhD skills with companies, with the goal of creating concrete opportunities. Three different editions were held and involved others. It is a learning-by-doing program that involved calls for ideas to gather innovation needs from participants, and

students responded to challenges brought up by companies. The outcome was new contracts for students.” (Participant 39)

Involvement with industries also includes internships within companies, providing researchers with training and an understanding of company organizations. Finally, a more didactic approach involves workshops where future employers are invited to discuss industry needs, enabling researchers to gain awareness and understand the labor market's requirements before transitioning out of academia.

Furthermore, universities are increasingly committed to training researchers in entrepreneurial competencies and assisting them in establishing their own business activities. Institutions created by universities include Entrepreneurial hubs designed to support startups, as well as Technological Transfer offices that teach entrepreneurial skills. These initiatives have proven effective not only in the learning process but also in developing important networks. An academic expert noted that researchers who engaged with startups were able to establish their own businesses and secure private funding.

Finally, to further prepare students for their future careers, universities offer courses on effective job interview techniques and how to prepare CVs, with involvement from external experts.

Another critical area universities are targeting involves enhancing communication capabilities.

One prominent strategy involves organizing events where researchers present their projects to diverse audiences, thus fostering their ability to effectively communicate research findings and adapt to various scenarios.

These events include workshops and conferences that invite researchers from different backgrounds to present their work. Such opportunities not only strengthen communication skills but also creates opportunities for networking within academia. Furthermore, these gatherings play a pivotal role in facilitating the exchange of knowledge across disciplines and exposing researchers to diverse perspectives. This exposure often inspires innovative ideas for their projects, as highlighted by Participant 18:

“Join students from different disciplines and have them present their work. By hearing what other students are doing, they get ideas and go back to their own programmes.” (Participant 18)

Finally, universities are increasing their effort to engage with citizens to inform about the importance of and the impact of science:

“We organize fairs to make students interact with citizens and the feedback from PhD students is that it is important to make society understand what they are doing.” (Participant 10)

Skill Assessment

A crucial aspect of ensuring effective integration of transversal skills training is evaluating their impact on equipping researchers with necessary competencies. However, assessing these skills presents a significant challenge for universities. This aspect is highlighted by the majority of academic experts who either lack awareness of the methods employed by their university or struggle to recommend suitable approaches.

Overall, universities are using traditional metrics such as tests and surveys, but they are also exploring novel approaches. Regarding traditional metrics, one approach is using surveys where researchers self-assess their competences before and after receiving the training, to determine if there has been an increase in their skills. Another approach is to collect feedback on the effectiveness of the course and improve offerings tailored to researchers' needs:

"We disseminate surveys at the end of the courses to understand if the course was effective and to understand if there was too much workload. When we do not get positive feedback we cancel those courses and we offer something new." (Participant 40)

Finally, another approach pertains to the completion of self-reflection documents where researchers are invited to reflect on their competences and define a plan for continuous improvement. One university, for instance, has a model where researchers develop their personal plan before doing an internship, which can guide them during their period in the industry:

"We have another model where students are encouraged to think about how engaging with enterprise changes them, what they need to bring to that environment, what they can learn through that environment, how they can build a personal plan into an internship experience. These students then have the opportunity to apply these skills in an internship and demonstrate their personal development plan in their CVs and verbally." (Participant 28)

The main challenge in assessing these skills, however, is that some skills can only be evaluated if observed in real-world contexts. For this reason, academic experts suggest the need for a more holistic and long-term approach. This approach involves, on one side, engaging directly with stakeholders who supervise and work with researchers to ensure their expectations on researchers' competences are met:

"It depends on the skill and it cannot be an approach. If we are talking about teamwork skills, it is important that the construction of the model has had input from a diverse range of stakeholders (university, different kinds of enterprises). There needs to be ongoing engagement with stakeholders and feedback from these stakeholders to see if it is meeting their needs." (Participant 28)

On the other side, this approach involves monitoring researchers after doctoral education completion. This includes reflecting on whether researchers have used the competences acquired during the training program or whether they have noticed important gaps:

"We use LinkedIn to see where our students end up. Then we invite alumni back to speak to our first-year students. We have now two students who are in charge of huge portfolios in an investment company in Denmark. They started out because they had entrepreneurial skills in their postdoc." (Participant 18)

4.6 QUALITATIVE INTERVIEWS ANALYSIS: THIRD SECTOR AND INDUSTRY

The following chapter presents a nuanced analysis of qualitative interviews with experts from the third sector and industry, shedding light on the skills they deem most valuable for today's professionals. This chapter explores the intricate balance between interpersonal competencies, self-management, and cognitive capabilities that are increasingly sought after in the modern workforce. Emphasizing the importance of transversal skills, the analysis reveals how these competencies not only complement technical expertise but also provide a competitive edge in recruitment and career advancement. The insights from industry and third-sector leaders underscore the critical role of emotional intelligence, entrepreneurial spirit, and innovative thinking in driving organizational success and personal fulfillment within the workplace. Additionally, this chapter examines the perceived skill gaps among researchers and the implications for doctoral programs, highlighting the need for a more practice-oriented approach to equip graduates with the necessary tools to excel in diverse professional environments

Valued Skills in the workforce

The most frequently mentioned skills by third sector and industry experts, identified as highly valued in the current workforce inside and outside academia, relate to the domains of **working with others** and **self-management**. Regarding the first domain, similar to the evaluation of academic experts, the capacities to interact professionally and work in teams dominate. In general, the broad capacity of working with others requires a set of skills related to emotional intelligence, including excellent communication capabilities, self-awareness, empathy, and an open-minded attitude. Leadership and conflict negotiation skills are also important.

In the domain of **self-management**, skills related to demonstrating an entrepreneurial spirit and coping with pressure are mentioned as important. Interestingly, the characteristics most highlighted in this domain are related to the emotional sphere, such as self-motivation, resilience, and risk-taking. Compared to the evaluation of academic experts, time-management skills receive fewer mentions.

Finally, although less frequently mentioned, there are skills related to **cognitive capabilities**, particularly critical thinking, curiosity, and creativity.

Importance of transversal skills

Doctoral graduates with strong transversal skills have a competitive advantage over those lacking these competencies as these skills differentiate individuals during the recruitment process and enhance their career prospects.

The competitive advantage of transversal skills stems from the rapidly evolving working landscape. On one hand, technical skills frequently change and can quickly become obsolete, necessitating continual updates:

"Technical skills will change all the time; they can come out." (Participant 48)

In this context, long-life learning becomes essential, requiring motivation, open-minded attitude, flexibility, and adaptability to keep up with new developments. Consequently, these skills are increasingly considered during hiring decisions:

"[E]vidence of self-motivation or lack thereof has been the main key to the hiring process and subsequent career growth." (Participant 59)

On the other hand, the nature of work is evolving to become more collaborative and interdisciplinary, making these skills essential for efficient work organization:

"Since people have different approaches to work, you need to develop teamwork skills, being flexible, communicating effectively and embracing diversity." (Participant 55)

Individuals lacking these competencies can negatively impact the work environment and the team productivity. Consequently, despite their technical proficiency, they may be penalized in their career prospects and face dismissal because they are considered unsuitable for the team dynamic and long-term organizational goals.

In fact, a lack of transversal skills, particularly those related to working with others, can increase tensions among colleagues. Deficiencies in skills such as flexibility and open-mindedness lead to strained interactions, creating a negative atmosphere within the team and reducing opportunities for collaboration in completing tasks:

"Students were too rigid - inflexible to external ideas - and aggressive in defending their work. Colleagues simply reduced their interactions with them." (Participant 59)

Tensions can also arise between employers and workers. Deficiencies in professional interactions, particularly in communication and conflict management, can be more significant than technical skills when deciding whether to retain someone on the team:

"There was [...] a really good researcher, but unfortunately, she was not good in communication, and she was not able to share what she was feeling. [S]he was not confirmed for continue working with us. [T]he lack of communication made the difference for her and for us." (Participant 50)

Finally, individuals equipped with strong transversal skills are better positioned to drive innovation within the organization and ensure the efficacy and impact of project outcomes. In this regard, third-sector experts have emphasized cognitive skills, particularly those related to critical thinking, as they are fundamental for exploring alternative perspectives and, therefore, for generating innovative solutions:

"There was this engineer [...] who was really good in his job, but his thinking was very linear and he couldn't think "outside the box". This gap between the ability to think critically and not to think critically is fundamental." (Participant 52)

Moreover, for impactful implementation of innovative ideas, effective interaction with stakeholders is vital for receiving support and recognition:

"We were developing a city profile [...] and students also had to interact with a steering group. This student was quite unique, and the city profile got excellent visibility at a local level."
(Participant 49)

In conclusion, transversal skills are essential complements to technical expertise, playing an indispensable role in today's rapidly evolving working environment. They serve as prerequisites for lifelong learning, facilitating knowledge sharing and collaboration within teams, fostering innovation, and ensuring societal impact. Individuals possessing strong transversal skills enjoy a competitive advantage, which is reflected in more career opportunities and stability. Moreover, these skills hold the potential to significantly enhance personal satisfaction and well-being within organizations. Traits such as empathy, active listening, and effective communication contribute to reducing friction among team members, thereby fostering the creation of a positive working environment.

Skill Gap

Regarding whether researchers possess the competencies required in the workforce, there is consensus among third-sector and industry experts that it depends on individual characteristics and their field expertise.

However, some participants note an important gap in doctoral programs, which have not properly invested in training on competencies required in the private sector. Rather than being an effect of the training received during their studies, the investment in acquiring certain skills is seen as an individual responsibility, strongly dependent on the individual's background and personal attitude. As Participant 50 noted:

"They do not have any idea of what transversal skills are really required in the modern world of work. Some of them know something about the required skills but just because of personal knowledge and personal background. PhD students know nothing about time management and project management because most of them only focused on their studies and didn't think too much about putting these skills into practice." (Participant 50)

The problem identified by respondents is that doctoral programs are predominantly theoretical, and researchers do not have sufficient practical experience:

"From what I see, they would be more prepared if they had worked somehow during their university and PhD years." (Participant 59)

Overall, the main competency gaps vary based on specific organizational needs and individuals' capabilities. The gaps mentioned include the ability to work with others, such as leadership, willingness to take risks, project and time management, and writing skills. Interestingly, Participant 58 noted that researchers sometimes lack hard competencies as well, indicating a deficiency that extends beyond transversal skills:

"They are not adequately equipped because they sometimes lack transversal skills – there is a significant skills mismatch." (Participant 58)

On the other hand, some companies report positive experiences with doctoral graduates, highlighting their possession of both soft and hard skills:

“We, as a company, have been extremely lucky in finding people with a lot of soft and hard skills and capable of working with people of different mindsets.” (Participant 56)

5. FINDINGS: FUTURE LANDSCAPE (TO BE)

The landscape of research is in a constant state of flux, with the competencies required of young researchers evolving to meet the demands of a dynamic and interconnected world. As we look to the future, it becomes increasingly important to understand how the profiles of researchers are expected to change, not only from their own perspective but also from that of their employers. By exploring the **TO-BE analysis** alongside the **AS-IS** importance, we gain a clear picture of the trends that are shaping the future of research and the competencies that will be most valued in the next **five years**. Through this lens, we can better prepare young researchers for the challenges ahead, ensuring that they are equipped with the skills necessary to thrive in an ever-changing environment.

5.1 RESEARCHERS' PROFILE EVOLUTION BY THEIR OWN OPINION

The predictive data gathered through the TO-BE analysis reveals significant insights into how young researchers anticipate the evolution of their competency profiles over the next five years. By examining these projections across the competence areas defined by the **ResearchComp framework**, we can discern notable trends and potential shifts in the importance of various skills and abilities.

Figure 21 Research profile evolution by their own opinion

Figure 22 Evolution of competence researchers mean value by researchers opinion

In the area of **Cognitive Abilities**, there is a notable decrease in importance, dropping from an AS-IS importance of 7.4 to a TO-BE importance of 5.9. This substantial decline suggests that young researchers foresee a future where cognitive skills, although still critical, might be overshadowed by other competencies. The reasons for this shift could be multifaceted. One possible explanation is the increasing reliance on collaborative and interdisciplinary approaches in research, where cognitive abilities are complemented by other skill sets. Additionally, the integration of advanced technologies and artificial intelligence in research processes might reduce the emphasis on traditional cognitive skills, as these technologies can assist with data analysis and problem-solving tasks.

The **Doing Research** area shows a slight decrease in importance, from 5.9 to 5.7. While this reduction is not as pronounced as in cognitive abilities, it still indicates a subtle shift in focus. This might reflect a growing recognition among young researchers that the research landscape is evolving, with greater emphasis on the application and impact of research rather than on the research process itself. The slight decrease might also suggest that researchers anticipate improvements in research methodologies and tools that could streamline the research process, making certain research skills less critical over time.

In contrast, the **Making an Impact** area sees an increase in importance from 4.0 to 4.3. This positive change underscores a growing awareness among young researchers of the importance of their work's societal and policy implications. As the global challenges become more complex, there is a heightened demand for research that not only advances knowledge but also addresses real-world problems. This trend indicates that young researchers are increasingly valuing skills related to science communication, policy influence, and societal engagement, understanding that the ability to make a tangible impact is becoming more crucial in the research domain.

The importance of **Managing Research** remains relatively stable, with a slight decrease from 4.6 to 4.5. This stability suggests that while managing research remains a critical competency, its relative importance might be balanced by other emerging areas. The slight decrease could

reflect an expectation that project management skills will continue to be necessary, but perhaps increasingly supported by institutional frameworks and administrative support, reducing the individual burden on researchers.

The **Managing Research Tools** area shows no change in importance, maintaining a value of 4.1. This consistency highlights the enduring relevance of competencies related to the effective use of research tools and technologies. As new tools and software become integral to the research process, maintaining proficiency in managing these tools remains crucial. The unchanged importance suggests that researchers expect these skills to continue to be foundational in their work, even as specific tools and technologies evolve.

A significant decrease is observed in the **Self-Management** area, where importance drops from 6.3 to 4.6. This notable decline suggests that young researchers anticipate a future where personal management skills may be less critical, possibly due to improved support systems and institutional structures that help manage workloads and professional development. Alternatively, it could reflect a growing confidence in their ability to self-manage as they gain more experience, making these skills less of a focal point in their ongoing development.

Lastly, the **Working with Others** area also shows a decrease in importance, from 6.0 to 5.5. This decline may indicate that while collaboration and teamwork remain essential, the emphasis might shift towards more specialized collaborative skills. As interdisciplinary and international collaborations become more common, the nature of teamwork may evolve, requiring more targeted competencies rather than general collaborative abilities.

The most significant variations are observed in **Cognitive Abilities** and **Self-Management**, both showing considerable declines in importance. This could be attributed to several factors, including the increasing role of technology in supplementing cognitive tasks and a growing infrastructure that supports researchers in their professional and personal development, reducing the emphasis on self-management. Conversely, the slight increases in **Making an Impact** reflect a shift towards valuing the broader societal implications of research, a trend driven by global challenges and the need for research to address these issues directly.

The TO-BE analysis provides valuable insights into how young researchers perceive the evolution of their competency profiles. These anticipated changes highlight a shift towards a more impact-driven, collaborative, and technology-supported research environment. Understanding these trends is crucial for developing training and development programs that align with future needs, ensuring that young researchers are equipped with the skills required to thrive in a rapidly changing research landscape. By focusing on areas with the most significant variations, such as cognitive abilities and self-management, institutions can tailor their strategies to address these evolving demands, ultimately enhancing the preparedness and effectiveness of the next generation of researchers.

The data collected provides a detailed view of how young researchers anticipate the importance of various competencies will change over the next five years. This analysis allows us to understand the shifting landscape of research skills and identify significant trends.

Globally, the TO-BE analysis reveals significant shifts in the perceived importance of various research competencies. The increasing importance of public communication, policy impact, and interdisciplinary collaboration suggests a future where researchers must engage more broadly with society and across disciplines. Conversely, the decreased emphasis on traditional teaching roles and certain cognitive and self-management skills indicates evolving priorities and support structures in the research environment. These insights are crucial for developing targeted training and development programs that align with the anticipated needs of future researchers, ensuring they are well-prepared to navigate the evolving landscape of academic and professional research.

Cognitive Abilities

Cognitive Abilities generally see an increase, with **Abstract thinking**, **Critical thinking**, **Analytical thinking**, and **Creativity** all rising in importance. **Analytical thinking** increases from 7.7 to 8.6, highlighting its critical role in research. **Abstract thinking** and **Critical thinking** also increase, indicating their sustained relevance.

On the contrary, **Strategic thinking** and **Systemic thinking** see significant decreases to 2.3 and 1.7, respectively. This might reflect a shift towards more immediate, practical problem-solving skills rather than long-term strategic planning. **Problem solving** also sees a sharp decrease from 7.4 to 4.0, possibly indicating that problem-solving will become more distributed across teams rather than being an individual responsibility.

Self-management

In the **Self Management** area, **Cope with pressure** significantly increases from 6.1 to 7.8, indicating that young researchers expect managing stress and maintaining mental health will become increasingly important. This could be due to the growing pressures of academia and the competitive nature of research.

However, **Show entrepreneurial spirit** and **Plan self-organization** see considerable declines, from 6.4 to 2.0 and from 6.2 to 3.4, respectively. This might suggest that entrepreneurial activities and self-organization may become less critical as support systems within institutions improve. **Manage personal professional development** also decreases from 6.5 to 5.2, reflecting perhaps a shift towards more structured career development paths provided by institutions.

Working with Others

For **Working with Others**, **Develop networks** and **Build mentor-mentee relationships** increase significantly, to 7.6 and 7.8 respectively. This underscores the importance of professional relationships and mentoring in the evolving research landscape. **Ensure wellbeing at work** also increases, reflecting an anticipated need for better work-life balance and mental health support.

However, **Interact professionally**, **Work in teams**, and **Promote inclusion & diversity** see decreases, indicating a potential shift in how these competencies are perceived or supported within the research environment.

Doing Research

The **Doing Research** area shows mixed trends. **Conduct interdisciplinary research** sees a significant increase from 5.4 to 8.2, emphasizing the growing importance of collaborative and cross-disciplinary approaches. **Apply research ethics and integrity principles** also increases to 8.0, highlighting the sustained emphasis on ethical research practices.

However, **Perform scientific research** and **Write research documents** both see substantial decreases, suggesting a shift towards valuing other aspects of the research process. **Disciplinary expertise** sees a slight increase, reflecting its continued relevance but not as a dominant focus.

Managing Research

In the area of **Managing Research**, there are notable shifts. The competence **Mobilize resources** shows a significant increase in importance from 3.9 to 4.6. This indicates that young researchers foresee a growing need to secure funding and resources, likely due to the increasing competition and scarcity of research grants. **Manage projects** also sees an increase from 4.3 to 5.3, highlighting a future emphasis on project management skills, essential for coordinating complex research projects and teams.

Conversely, **Negotiate** decreases from 5.1 to 4.1, suggesting a lesser focus on negotiation skills, possibly due to institutional support structures taking over these responsibilities. **Evaluate research** increases slightly from 5.5 to 6.1, emphasizing the continuous need for critical assessment of research quality. **Promote open access publishing** drops sharply from 4.2 to 2.5, indicating a potential shift in the publication landscape where open access might become more standardized and less of a unique skill.

Manage Research Tools

In **Managing Research Tools**, **Manage research data** remains steady at 4.9, reflecting its ongoing importance. **Manage intellectual property** rights sees an increase to 5.1, suggesting a growing awareness of the importance of protecting research outputs. Conversely, **Promote citizen science** and **Operate open-source software** decrease, indicating these areas might be seen as less critical moving forward.

Making an Impact

For **Making an Impact**, **Communicate to the broad public** shows a substantial increase from 4.6 to 7.9, reflecting an anticipated need for researchers to engage more with the public and

communicate their findings effectively. Increase the impact of science on policy and society also sees a significant rise from 2.8 to 6.2, underscoring the growing importance of influencing policy and addressing societal challenges.

In contrast, **Teach in academic or vocational contexts** plummets from 4.3 to 0.9, suggesting a reduced emphasis on traditional teaching roles, perhaps due to a shift towards more research-focused careers or alternative educational methods gaining prominence. **Disseminate results to the research community** increases from 4.4 to 6.6, highlighting the continued importance of sharing research findings within the academic community.

Promote open innovation and **Promote the transfer of knowledge** decrease to 2.1 and 2.4, respectively, indicating a potential deprioritization of these areas as other competencies become more critical.

5.2 RESEARCHERS' PROFILE EVOLUTION BY EMPLOYER OPINION

The predictive data from employers offers a distinct perspective on the anticipated changes in the importance of various competencies over the next five years. This analysis, grouped by competence areas as per the ResearchComp structure, highlights significant shifts in employer expectations and priorities.

Figure 23 Researchers' profile evolution by employer opinion

Figure 24 Evolution of competence researchers mean value by employer opinion

Employers currently rate **Cognitive Abilities** with an importance score of 5.3, which is projected to decrease slightly to 5.0. This modest decline suggests a relative stabilization in the emphasis on cognitive skills, perhaps indicating that employers believe current levels of critical, analytical, and abstract thinking are sufficient or that other competencies may become more critical. Despite this, cognitive skills remain essential, though not necessarily the primary focus moving forward.

The **Doing Research** area shows a more significant decrease in importance from 6.3 to 4.9. This reduction suggests that employers might anticipate a shift towards valuing other aspects of a researcher's role beyond traditional research activities. This shift could reflect a growing emphasis on the application and impact of research rather than the research process itself. It may also indicate that employers expect researchers to possess strong foundational skills in doing research already, thus focusing on developing other areas.

For **Making an Impact**, the importance score decreases from 5.3 to 4.7. This suggests a potential deprioritization of direct impact activities in favor of other competencies. However, this shift could also reflect an expectation that impact-related skills will be more integrated into broader roles rather than being standalone competencies. Employers might foresee researchers naturally incorporating impact activities as part of their overall responsibilities, rather than as separate skill sets.

In the area of **Managing Research**, the predicted importance drops from 5.5 to 4.7. This decline might indicate a perception that researchers will need less direct involvement in management tasks, potentially due to increased support from administrative staff or more streamlined project management processes. Employers may expect researchers to focus more on their core research activities, with management responsibilities being shared or delegated.

The **Managing Research Tools** area also sees a decrease from 5.1 to 4.6. This could reflect advancements in research technologies and tools, making them easier to use and lessening the need for specialized management skills. Employers might anticipate that future

researchers will benefit from improved tools and systems that reduce the complexity and time required to manage research data and tools effectively.

In the **Self Management** area, the importance score drops from 6.0 to 4.9. This significant decrease might indicate a shift in how self-management is perceived within research roles. Employers might expect that institutions will provide more structured support for researchers' professional development and stress management, reducing the emphasis on self-directed management. Alternatively, this could suggest that employers anticipate a greater balance between self-management and institutional support systems.

Lastly, the **Working with Others** area shows a decrease in importance from 5.4 to 4.9. This reduction suggests that while teamwork and collaboration remain important, there might be a shift towards more autonomous or independent working conditions. Employers may foresee researchers needing to balance collaboration with the ability to work independently, possibly due to the increasing complexity and specialization of research projects.

Overall, the data indicates that employers anticipate a general decrease in the importance of most competence areas over the next five years. The most significant decreases are observed in **Doing Research** and **Self Management**, suggesting a shift in focus towards other areas or an expectation of improved institutional support structures. The relative stability in **Cognitive Abilities** implies that foundational cognitive skills remain critical, though the emphasis may shift towards practical application and integration into broader roles.

These insights highlight the evolving landscape of research competencies from the employers' perspective, emphasizing the need for adaptable and multifaceted training programs. As employers foresee changes in the importance of various competencies, it becomes crucial for training and development programs to address these shifts, ensuring that young researchers are well-equipped to meet future demands. This evolution underscores the importance of continuous dialogue between researchers and employers to align expectations and competencies, ultimately enhancing the effectiveness and impact of research in diverse contexts.

Analyzing the evolution of specific competencies as perceived by employers reveals significant insights into the anticipated shifts in the importance of various skills over time. The following detailed analysis explores the changes in specific competencies, highlighting the most notable variations and providing an ordinal ranking context to understand the underlying reasons for these changes.

Cognitive Abilities

In terms of **Cognitive Abilities**, the data reveals a mixed picture. **Abstract thinking** and **creativity** see slight increases, suggesting that these higher-order cognitive skills will remain vital. However, **critical thinking**, **strategic thinking**, and **systemic thinking** experience decreases, which might reflect a shift towards more collaborative approaches or the utilization of advanced tools that handle some aspects of these cognitive functions. The decline in **strategic** and **systemic thinking** could also indicate a transition towards more specialized roles where these broader thinking skills are distributed across teams rather than being concentrated in individual researchers.

Self-management

The **Self Management** area reveals a shift towards greater emphasis on **coping with pressure**, which increases from 4.8 to 5.7. This suggests a heightened recognition of the mental and emotional challenges faced by researchers, reflecting an increased need for resilience and stress management. The competencies related to **managing personal professional development** and **planning self-organization** both show declines, indicating that researchers might experience more structured support and less individual responsibility in these areas in the future. The dramatic drop in **showing entrepreneurial spirit**, from 7.0 to 4.2, signals a transition from a focus on individual entrepreneurship to potentially more institutionalized or collaborative forms of innovation and commercialization.

Working with Others

The **Working with Others** domain shows varied changes in competency importance. Notably, the ability to **work in teams** and **build mentor-mentee relationships** both experience declines, which may be attributed to evolving team structures or shifts in mentoring approaches. Conversely, the competencies of **developing networks** and **ensuring wellbeing at work** show increases, reflecting a growing emphasis on professional interactions and maintaining a supportive work environment. The decrease in **interacting professionally**, though less dramatic, might suggest a shift towards more structured or formalized professional interactions.

Doing Research

In the **Doing Research** area, there is a significant reduction in the importance of **performing scientific research** and **writing research documents**, which might reflect the integration of these tasks into more collaborative and less individually driven processes. However, the importance of **disciplinary expertise** and **applying research ethics and integrity principles** remains relatively stable or increases slightly, indicating that these core competencies continue to be essential. The increased emphasis on **conducting interdisciplinary research** highlights a trend towards more integrated and cross-disciplinary approaches within research.

Managing Research

The area of **Managing Research** shows several noteworthy shifts in competency importance from the AS-IS to the TO-BE scenario. The most significant change is observed in the competence of **managing projects**, which sees a substantial decrease from 7.3 to 5.3. This reduction suggests a shift in focus away from individual project management towards more collaborative approaches or increased administrative support that may alleviate the individual burden. Similarly, **mobilizing resources** and **negotiating** skills both see declines, though less pronounced, indicating possible structural changes in research management where these functions might become more standardized or streamlined. Conversely, **evaluating research**, though it decreases slightly, remains relatively important, likely due to

its critical role in maintaining research quality. The competency of **promoting open access publishing** shows a decline from 4.5 to 4.3, reflecting a potential maturation of the open access movement where the focus may shift from promotion to sustaining established practices.

Manage Research Tools

The area of **Managing Research Tools** shows a notable decline in the importance of **managing research data**, from 6.6 to 4.8. This could indicate a shift towards more automated or centralized data management systems, reducing the individual responsibility for this competency. Similarly, **promoting citizen science** sees a decrease, which may reflect a stabilization in public engagement in research. Conversely, **managing intellectual property rights** shows a slight increase, possibly due to growing complexities and the need for clearer guidelines in this area.

Making an Impact

In the domain of **Making an Impact**, several competencies exhibit notable shifts. **Communicating to the broad public**, which initially held a high importance at 7.9, experiences a significant drop to 6.0. This decline could indicate a reduced emphasis on individual researchers' roles in public communication, possibly due to the rise of specialized communication teams or centralized strategies. The increased importance of **disseminating results to the research community**, rising from 4.6 to 4.9, underscores a growing emphasis on internal collaboration and sharing within the scientific community. On the other hand, competencies like **teaching in academic or vocational contexts** and **promoting open innovation** see substantial decreases, possibly due to evolving educational models and the integration of innovation into more systemic approaches rather than individual efforts.

5.2 EMERGING COMPETENCIES

During the stakeholder survey, several competencies emerged that were not directly included in the ResearchComp framework. These competencies, identified as crucial by stakeholders, highlight areas that may either belong to existing ResearchComp areas or represent entirely new fields of significance. These emerging competencies include Advanced Digital Skills - AI, Quality Management, Motivation, Work Ethic, Data Visualization, and Green Skills.

Advanced Digital Skills - AI

Advanced Digital Skills, particularly in Artificial Intelligence (AI), have been identified as a crucial emerging competency. Stakeholders emphasized the growing importance of AI in research, which aligns with the increasing integration of AI technologies across various scientific disciplines. AI's ability to handle large datasets, perform complex analyses, and generate insights rapidly makes it an invaluable tool in modern research.

Researchers are expected to develop proficiency in AI to enhance their research methodologies, automate repetitive tasks, and innovate new approaches to problem-solving. The emphasis on AI skills is driven by the technological advancements and the necessity for researchers to leverage these tools to remain competitive and efficient. The integration of AI into research not only increases productivity but also opens new avenues for discovery and innovation.

Quality Management

Quality Management is another competency highlighted by stakeholders, underscoring the importance of maintaining high standards in research practices. This competency is crucial for ensuring the reliability and validity of research findings. It involves a systematic approach to managing research processes, including planning, execution, monitoring, and reviewing research activities to meet predefined quality standards.

The focus on Quality Management stems from the increasing complexity of research projects and the need for rigorous standards to ensure that research outcomes are credible and reproducible. As research projects often involve significant investments of time and resources, maintaining quality throughout the research lifecycle is essential to maximize the impact and applicability of research findings.

Motivation

Motivation has been identified as a key competency that influences researchers' performance and productivity. It encompasses the internal drive that fuels researchers' commitment to their work, perseverance in the face of challenges, and overall engagement with their research projects.

Stakeholders highlighted motivation as a critical factor in sustaining researchers' long-term careers and achieving high levels of performance. The importance of fostering a motivated research environment cannot be understated, as motivated researchers are more likely to be innovative, resilient, and productive. This competency is closely linked to personal satisfaction and professional development, emphasizing the need for institutions to create supportive and stimulating work environments.

Work with Ethic

Work with Ethic, which refers to the set of values centered around the importance of hard work and diligence, is another competency deemed essential by stakeholders. A strong work ethic is characterized by qualities such as reliability, responsibility, and dedication to one's tasks.

Stakeholders stressed that a solid work ethic is fundamental to achieving excellence in research. Researchers who exhibit a strong work ethic are more likely to adhere to ethical standards, meet deadlines, and contribute positively to their teams and institutions. This competency is particularly important in a field where the integrity and credibility of research are paramount.

Data Visualization

Data Visualization is increasingly recognized as a critical skill for researchers. It involves the ability to represent data graphically to make complex information more accessible and understandable. This competency is essential for communicating research findings effectively to both scientific and non-scientific audiences.

The growing emphasis on Data Visualization is driven by the need to present data in a clear and compelling manner, which enhances the interpretability and impact of research results. As datasets become larger and more complex, the ability to distill and present key insights visually becomes ever more important. Researchers proficient in data visualization can convey their findings more persuasively, facilitating better decision-making and broader dissemination of their work.

Green Skills

Green Skills refer to the knowledge and abilities needed to support sustainable practices and address environmental challenges. This emerging competency reflects the increasing importance of sustainability in research and development.

Stakeholders highlighted Green Skills as essential due to the growing emphasis on environmental stewardship and the need for researchers to contribute to sustainable solutions. This competency includes understanding environmental impacts, developing eco-friendly technologies, and promoting sustainable practices within research projects. As global challenges such as climate change and resource depletion become more pressing, researchers equipped with Green Skills will be pivotal in driving sustainable innovations.

The identification of these emerging competencies is a result of stakeholders recognizing gaps in the current ResearchComp framework and the evolving demands of the research landscape. The emphasis on AI reflects the rapid technological advancements and the transformative potential of AI in research. Quality Management underscores the necessity for maintaining high standards in increasingly complex research environments. Motivation and Work Ethic highlight the human factors that drive research productivity and integrity.

Data Visualization and Green Skills reflect broader societal and environmental trends influencing research priorities. The ability to visualize data effectively is becoming essential for clear communication and broader dissemination of research findings. Similarly, Green Skills align with the global shift towards sustainability, requiring researchers to integrate environmental considerations into their work.

Overall, these emerging competencies signal a shift in the research landscape, where technological proficiency, quality standards, personal drive, ethical conduct, and sustainability are becoming increasingly integral to successful research careers. Addressing these competencies in training programs for young researchers will be crucial in preparing them for the future demands of their professions.

5.3 PREDICTED MISMATCH BETWEEN THE COMPETENCIES POSSESSED BY RESEARCHERS AND THOSE VALUED BY EMPLOYERS

Following the previous separate analyses, the profiles data were synthesized to assess the evolution of the mismatch between the competencies possessed by researchers and those demanded by employers. This assessment was pivotal in identifying areas where the mismatch, whether it manifests as overskill or underskill, is expected to decrease or increase. Understanding these dynamics is crucial for several reasons.

Firstly, the analysis highlighted cases where the mismatch is predicted to decrease, indicating a convergence between researchers' skillsets and market demands. This positive trend suggests that current and future training and development initiatives are effectively aligning researchers' competencies with industry needs. Such alignment is likely to enhance employability and career progression for researchers, ensuring that their skills are relevant and valued in the job market.

Conversely, the analysis also identified areas where the mismatch is expected to grow. In some instances, this growth may indicate an overskill scenario, where researchers possess competencies that are beyond what the market currently demands. In other cases, it may highlight an underskill situation, where the evolving demands of the job market outpace the development of researchers' skills. Recognizing these trends is critical for stakeholders to address potential gaps proactively.

By forecasting the evolution of the mismatch, a roadmap is designed for developing targeted training programs and interventions aimed at reducing the mismatch. This forward-looking approach ensures that researchers are equipped with the skills that will be most in demand, thereby enhancing their employability and contributing to the overall competitiveness of the research workforce. Additionally, it helps employers identify areas where they may need to invest in upskilling or reskilling their workforce to meet future challenges.

The predicted mismatch analysis serves as a cornerstone for strategic planning in research competency development. It not only identifies future skill gaps but also guides the creation of educational and training programs tailored to bridge these gaps. This proactive stance is essential for fostering a well-prepared, agile, and competitive research community that can adapt to the evolving demands of the global job market.

The analysis of the mismatch variation across different competency areas as defined in the ResearchComp framework reveals several noteworthy trends, highlighting areas of both increasing and decreasing mismatch. These variations offer critical insights into the evolving dynamics between researchers' competencies and market demands.

The mismatch in the area of **Cognitive Abilities** shows a notable increase from an AS-IS value of 2.1 to a TO-BE value of 2.5. This rise suggests that despite the high self-assessed proficiency in cognitive skills, there is an anticipated growing gap between the competencies researchers possess and those required by employers. This increase could be attributed to the rapidly advancing nature of cognitive tasks in research, driven by new technologies and methodologies that require continual skill enhancement. Researchers may need to invest more in lifelong learning and advanced training to keep pace with these evolving demands.

The **Doing Research** area exhibits a significant increase in mismatch, from 0.9 in the AS-IS analysis to 2.2 in the TO-BE projection. This substantial rise indicates a growing concern that researchers' current and future abilities to conduct research may not meet the emerging standards and expectations of the job market. This trend could stem from the increasing complexity of research methodologies, the need for interdisciplinary approaches, and the integration of advanced data analytics and technology in research processes. Addressing this mismatch will likely require targeted training programs that focus on these advanced skills and interdisciplinary collaboration.

For the **Making an Impact** competency, the mismatch increases from 1.3 to 1.9. This suggests that researchers might struggle more in the future to translate their research into meaningful societal impacts. The growing importance of research that directly addresses societal challenges and the increasing demand for demonstrable outcomes may be driving this trend. Researchers will need to enhance their skills in communication, public engagement, and policy advocacy to bridge this gap effectively.

Conversely, the areas of **Managing Research** and **Managing Research Tools** show a decrease in mismatch, both dropping from 1 to 0.7. This decrease indicates a positive trend where the alignment between researchers' skills in managing research projects and tools and the demands of employers is expected to improve. This improvement could be the result of better training programs, increased focus on project management skills in doctoral and postdoctoral programs, and greater availability of resources and tools that simplify research management tasks. Such trends are encouraging and suggest that current efforts to equip researchers with essential management skills are bearing fruit.

The mismatch in **Self Management** rises from 1.2 to 1.5, indicating a growing gap in researchers' abilities to effectively manage their time, stress, and professional development. This increase highlights the ongoing challenges researchers face in balancing multiple responsibilities and maintaining well-being in a competitive and often stressful environment. To mitigate this growing mismatch, there may be a need for more comprehensive support systems, including mentoring, career counseling, and workshops on time management and resilience.

Finally, the **Working with Others** competency area shows a dramatic increase in mismatch, from 0.6 to 1.9. This sharp rise suggests that collaboration skills will be increasingly in demand, but researchers may not be adequately prepared to meet these expectations. The trend towards more collaborative and interdisciplinary research, combined with the necessity for effective teamwork and communication skills, likely drives this increase. Enhancing interpersonal skills, conflict resolution abilities, and collaborative competencies will be crucial to address this growing mismatch.

The analysis of the variation in mismatch for individual competencies within the ResearchComp framework reveals significant insights into how specific skill areas are expected to evolve. These insights, presented as positive values indicating an increase in mismatch or negative values indicating a decrease, provide a detailed understanding of where gaps may either widen or narrow in the future.

It should be noted that a reduction in the mismatch between the competencies of young researchers and the expectations of stakeholders may not always indicate an improvement in researchers' skills or alignment with market demands. It can also result from a decreased importance assigned to a particular competence. This means that the perceived gap between the skill levels of researchers and the expectations of employers diminishes because the competence itself is no longer considered as critical as it once was. Thus, the reduction in mismatch could reflect a shift in the priorities or evolving needs of the industry and academia, where certain skills may become less relevant or valued over time. This underscores the importance of not only enhancing competencies but also continually reassessing the relevance of these skills in the context of changing market demands and stakeholder expectations.

Cognitive Abilities

In the domain of **Cognitive Abilities**, there are increases in mismatch across several competencies, including **abstract thinking** (0.4), **critical thinking** (1.7), **analytical thinking** (1.0), **strategic thinking** (0.5), and **systemic thinking** (0.6). These increases indicate a growing gap between the cognitive skills researchers currently possess and those anticipated to be required, potentially due to the rapid advancement in these fields. However, there is a decrease in mismatch for **problem solving** (-1.4), suggesting that researchers are expected to become better at tackling complex problems, possibly due to more focused problem-solving training.

Self-management

The **Self Management** area shows mixed trends. While **managing personal professional development** sees a decrease in mismatch of -1.3, indicating an expected improvement in this area, there is a significant increase in mismatch for **showing entrepreneurial spirit** and **coping with pressure**, with values of 1.7 and 0.8. This highlights potential areas where researchers may struggle more in the future, suggesting a need for better support systems to foster entrepreneurial skills and stress management.

Working with Others

Working with Others shows significant increases in mismatch for **developing networks** (2.3), **working in teams** (2.0), and **building mentor-mentee relationships** (2.4), indicating growing challenges in these collaborative competencies. This trend suggests that as interdisciplinary and collaborative research becomes more prevalent, researchers may need to develop stronger networking and teamwork skills. However, there is a decrease in mismatch for **interacting professionally** (-1.0), suggesting improvements in professional interactions, likely due to better communication training.

Doing Research

In the **Doing Research** area, **conducting interdisciplinary research** (2.6) and **writing research documents** (1.5) show significant increases in mismatch, highlighting the growing complexities and expectations in these areas. Conversely, there is a decrease in mismatch for **performing scientific research** (-1.1), suggesting that researchers are expected to maintain or improve their core research competencies.

Managing Research

In the **Managing Research** area, there is a notable decrease in mismatch for competencies such as **mobilizing resources** and **managing projects**, with decreases of -1.3 and -2.9, respectively. This suggests that researchers are expected to become more adept at securing and managing resources and projects, likely due to improved training and resource

availability. However, there is an increase in mismatch for **evaluating research** and **promoting open access publishing**, with values of 1.2 and 1.5. This indicates potential challenges ahead in effectively assessing research outcomes and advocating for open access, which may require additional emphasis in training programs.

Manage Research Tools

For **Managing Research Tools**, there is a notable decrease in mismatch for **managing research data** (-1.5), suggesting that researchers are expected to become more proficient in data management. However, **promoting citizen science** shows a slight increase in mismatch (0.3), indicating potential challenges in engaging the public in research activities.

Making an Impact

For **Making an Impact**, the mismatch for **participating in the publication process**, **disseminating results**, and **teaching in academic or vocational contexts** shows significant increases of 0.6, 1.6, and 2.7, respectively. This suggests growing challenges in these areas, possibly due to the increasing complexity of publication standards, the need for more effective communication within the research community, and the evolving demands of educational roles. Conversely, there is a decrease in mismatch for **communicating to the broad public** and **increasing the impact of science on policy and society**, with values of -1.4 and -0.9, indicating improvements in these competencies. This could be attributed to enhanced training in public engagement and policy advocacy.

5.4 MISMATCH BY FIELD OF RESEARCH

The predictive evaluation of the evolution of the mismatch between researchers' competencies and market demands provides a forward-looking analysis that is critical for strategic planning and educational development. This evaluation was conducted by examining the anticipated changes in the mismatch for each field of study and across various areas of competence as defined by the ResearchComp framework. By comparing the current (AS-IS) and projected future (TO-BE) states, we can identify trends and shifts in the alignment between researchers' skills and the expectations of stakeholders in academia, industry, and research centers.

The detailed analysis of the predicted mismatch variation across different fields of research and competency areas provides valuable insights into the evolving landscape of skill requirements. By examining how the mismatch is expected to change, we can identify specific trends and potential challenges that each field may face in the coming years. This section presents a comprehensive evaluation of these variations, supported by the quantitative data provided.

In the area of **managing research**, all fields show a predicted decrease in mismatch. **Engineering and Technology** (-0.5), **Humanities** (-0.2), **Mathematics** (-0.2), **Medical and Health Sciences** (-0.4), **Natural Sciences** (-0.3), and **Social Sciences** (-0.3) all exhibit a reduction in mismatch. This overall decrease suggests that researchers in these fields are expected to become more adept at managing research projects, mobilizing resources, and navigating the administrative aspects of research, aligning more closely with employer expectations. The uniform improvement across fields may be attributed to increased emphasis on research management training and skills development programs within academic and research institutions.

The area of **making an impact** shows a predicted increase in mismatch across all fields. **Engineering and Technology** (0.8), **Humanities** (0.7), **Mathematics** (0.6), **Medical and Health Sciences** (0.4), **Natural Sciences** (0.7), and **Social Sciences** (0.4) all indicate higher mismatch levels. This rise could stem from evolving employer expectations regarding the broader dissemination of research findings, public engagement, and policy influence. As the importance of research impact grows, researchers might need more training and experience in effectively communicating and applying their work beyond academic circles.

Predictions for **self-management** competencies are mixed. **Engineering and Technology** (0.5), **Humanities** (0.2), **Mathematics** (0.4), and **Medical and Health Sciences** (0.3) show moderate increases in mismatch, while **Natural Sciences** (0.2) and **Social Sciences** (-0.04) demonstrate a more stable or even decreasing mismatch. The varied trends suggest that self-management skills, such as personal development, entrepreneurship, and coping with pressure, might not uniformly meet employer expectations across fields. The slight

improvement in Social Sciences could reflect a growing emphasis on these competencies within the field, potentially through targeted training and development initiatives.

The predictions for **cognitive abilities** are quite polarized. **Engineering and Technology** (1.1) and **Social Sciences** (1.1) both show significant increases in mismatch, indicating that researchers in these fields may struggle to meet the evolving cognitive demands set by employers. Conversely, **Humanities** (-0.2), **Mathematics** (0.4), **Medical and Health Sciences** (-0.2), and **Natural Sciences** (-0.1) show minimal changes or slight improvements. The increase in mismatch in Engineering and Technology and Social Sciences might reflect the rapidly advancing requirements for abstract, analytical, and strategic thinking skills, which could be outpacing current training and educational frameworks.

The **Working with others** area exhibits a predicted increase in mismatch across all fields, with **Natural Sciences** (1.7) showing the highest increase, followed by **Medical and Health Sciences** (1.6), **Mathematics** (1.5), **Humanities** (1.2), **Engineering and Technology** (1.1), and **Social Sciences** (0.9). The rise in mismatch suggests that collaboration, networking, and teamwork skills are becoming increasingly important, yet researchers might not be fully equipped to meet these expectations. The significant increase in Natural Sciences and Medical and Health Sciences may reflect the growing complexity and interdisciplinary nature of research in these fields, requiring enhanced collaborative competencies.

The predictions for **managing research tools** reveal a mixed scenario. **Engineering and Technology** (-0.2), **Mathematics** (-0.4), **Medical and Health Sciences** (-0.6), **Natural Sciences** (-0.3), and **Social Sciences** (-1.2) all show a predicted decrease in mismatch, suggesting improvements in managing data, intellectual property, and research software. **Humanities** (0.8) is the exception, with an increase in mismatch, indicating that researchers in this field might face challenges in aligning with technological and data management expectations. The overall trend of decreasing mismatch in most fields could be due to the increasing integration of digital tools and data management practices in research training.

In the area of **conducting research**, all fields show an increase in mismatch. **Humanities** (1.6) and **Natural Sciences** (1.6) exhibit the highest increases, followed by **Medical and Health Sciences** (1.3), **Engineering and Technology** (1.2), and **Social Sciences** (0.9). The predicted rise in mismatch suggests that the demands for interdisciplinary research, ethical standards, and high-quality research output are growing, and researchers may need further development to meet these evolving expectations. The substantial increase in Humanities and Natural Sciences highlights the dynamic nature of research practices and the need for continuous adaptation and skill enhancement.

The predicted evolution of mismatch reveals a complex interplay of factors across different fields of research. While improvements are expected in areas such as managing research and research tools, significant challenges remain in making an impact, cognitive abilities, and working with others. Addressing these mismatches will require targeted interventions, enhanced training programs, and ongoing dialogue between researchers and employers to ensure that the future workforce is well-equipped to meet the demands of the evolving research landscape.

5.5 MISMATCH BY TYPE OF EMPLOYER

The predictive evaluation of mismatch evolution across different types of employers provides critical insights into the future alignment of researchers' competencies with market demands. This analysis delves into the expected changes in mismatch over the next five years, segmented by employer type—academia, industry, and research centers. By examining the predicted mismatch for each competency area as defined by the ResearchComp framework, we can identify specific trends and challenges that researchers are likely to face in different employment contexts.

In **academia**, the predicted mismatch variations present a mixed picture. **Managing research** (-0.2), **cognitive abilities** (-0.4), and **managing research tools** (-0.3) show a decrease in mismatch, indicating an expected improvement in these areas. Researchers in academia may be becoming better aligned with employer expectations regarding administrative and cognitive skills, likely due to enhanced training and institutional support. However, **making an impact** (0.6), **self-management** (0.7), **working with others** (1.2), and **doing research** (1.6) all exhibit increases in mismatch. The significant rise in doing research mismatch suggests that academic researchers might struggle to meet evolving demands for interdisciplinary work and high-quality output. The increase in working with others mismatch highlights potential challenges in collaboration and teamwork within academic settings.

For **associations**, the data shows a decrease in mismatch for **managing research** (-1.1) and **managing research tools** (-0.2), indicating improvements in these areas. Conversely, increases in mismatch are noted for **making an impact** (0.5), **self-management** (0.9), **cognitive abilities** (0.8), **working with others** (1), and **doing research** (1.5). The rise in mismatch for self-management and cognitive abilities suggests that researchers in associations may face difficulties in meeting heightened expectations for personal development and critical thinking. The substantial increase in doing research mismatch points to a potential gap in research skills and capabilities within this sector.

The **industry** sector exhibits a reduction in mismatch for **managing research** (-0.9) and **managing research tools** (-0.6), reflecting improvements in these areas. However, significant increases in mismatch are observed for **making an impact** (0.8), **self-management** (0.4), **cognitive abilities** (1.5), **working with others** (1.6), and **doing research** (1.6). The high mismatch in cognitive abilities suggests that industry researchers might struggle to meet the advanced analytical and strategic thinking skills demanded by employers. The increase in mismatch for working with others highlights potential challenges in teamwork and collaboration, which are critical in the industry sector.

Research centres present a unique profile with an increase in mismatch for **managing research** (1.1) and **cognitive abilities** (0.6), suggesting that researchers may face challenges in these areas. However, decreases in mismatch are seen in **self-management** (-0.2) and **managing research tools** (-0.3), reflecting improvements. The increase in mismatch for **working with others** (1.3) and **doing research** (0.9) indicates potential gaps in collaborative skills and research capabilities, possibly due to the interdisciplinary nature and high standards of research centres.

In the **third sector**, mismatch variations show decreases in **managing research** (-0.01), **cognitive abilities** (-0.4), and **managing research tools** (-0.1), indicating improvements. Increases in mismatch are observed for **making an impact** (0.3), **self-management** (0.2), **working with others** (1.1), and **doing research** (0.8). The decrease in cognitive abilities mismatch suggests that third sector researchers may be better equipped to meet analytical and strategic thinking demands. However, the increase in working with others mismatch highlights potential challenges in teamwork and collaborative efforts within this sector.

For **other employers**, the predicted mismatch variations show a decrease in **managing research** (-0.8) and **managing research tools** (-0.2), indicating improvements in these areas. However, increases in mismatch are seen in **making an impact** (0.6), **working with others** (1.4), and **doing research** (1.1). The decrease in **self-management** mismatch (-0.3) is notable, suggesting better alignment in personal development skills. The increase in working with others mismatch indicates potential difficulties in collaboration, which could be a result of diverse and non-standardized work environments.

The predicted evolution of mismatch across different types of employers reveals both improvements and emerging challenges. Academia and industry show significant increases in mismatch for collaborative and research competencies, indicating potential areas for targeted interventions. Associations and research centres highlight challenges in cognitive and research skills, suggesting the need for enhanced training and support. The third sector presents a mixed picture with improvements in cognitive abilities but challenges in

collaboration. Addressing these mismatches will require a concerted effort to align training programs with evolving employer expectations, ensuring that researchers are well-equipped to meet the demands of their respective sectors.

6. CONCLUSIONS AND DISCUSSION

The academic and labour market landscapes are undergoing significant transformations, requiring researchers to adapt by enhancing their skill sets with increasingly important competencies. These competencies particularly relate to interdisciplinary collaborations and ensuring that research has a societal impact by embracing the new principles of Open Science. While these skills are crucial for researchers' career trajectories in both academia and the labour market, Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) face considerable challenges in updating doctoral training to prepare researchers for current and future demands.

The comprehensive analysis of young researchers' competencies in the European context, based on self-assessment data, provides a multifaceted picture of the current state of early career researchers' skills and challenges.

The findings underscore that young researchers (R1 & R2) possess strong technical competencies in conducting research, robust cognitive abilities, and moderate self-management competencies. Additionally, the study finds also that researchers demonstrate strong disciplinary expertise and are effective in performing and evaluating research according to ethical and integrity principles, ensuring research of high-quality standards.

However, the analysis also reveals significant deficiencies, particularly in the application of Open Science principles and in ensuring that research has meaningful societal impacts. These gaps align with existing literature on young researchers' competences and reflect the current landscape of professional training that doctoral students receive, which is primarily centred around the production of high-quality research outcomes.

Both experts from academia and the labor market have emphasized that collaboration among researchers from different areas of expertise is increasingly necessary to meet new societal challenges. As societal problems become more complex, their solution requires the exchange of knowledge to foster innovation and ensure societal impact. In this context, interpersonal competencies are highly valued. In addition to communication abilities, experts have mentioned competencies pertaining to emotional intelligence, necessitating individuals to be flexible, open-minded to diverse perspectives, and to embrace diversity. However, evidence shows important deficiencies in these areas. Academic experts have underlined that working in teams is an area that is overlooked in doctoral training, whereas third sector and industry experts have pointed out situations where these deficiencies have led to strained relationships among colleagues, highly impacting the overall work and results of the team. This underqualification is evident when also looking at self-assessment scores. Self-assessment scores emphasize that researchers self-assess proficiency in working in teams, underlying that researchers contribute effectively to team dynamics and coordinate well for an efficient workflow. However, self-assessment is notably low regarding the abilities to conduct interdisciplinary research, integrate different data and results from interdisciplinary research, and conduct interdisciplinary projects. Similarly, low scores are found in relation to ensuring well-being at work and promoting inclusion and diversity.

In addition to capabilities related to working with others, self-planning and management are fundamental. Nonetheless, experts from both academia and the labor market have underlined that researchers often lack capabilities related to project and time management. This lack is also confirmed by self-assessment scores in planning and self-organization, where researchers face struggles in maintaining optimal organization and meeting deadlines.

Moreover, the score for managing projects indicates that researchers exhibit difficulties in effectively planning and allocating resources for their research projects.

Another important area of underqualification pertains to ensuring that research has an impact. This issue is particularly pronounced within academia, where experts have emphasized that researchers face significant barriers in communicating their research to a broader audience. The lack of these competencies is especially evident in self-assessment scores, which reveal significant deficiencies in communicating research findings to the public, as well as in promoting citizen science and open innovation.

The importance of transversal skills cannot be overstated. Doctoral graduates with strong transversal skills hold a competitive advantage over those who lack these competencies, as these skills are crucial in differentiating candidates during the recruitment process and enhancing their career prospects. The advantage of transversal skills is particularly significant in the rapidly evolving work environment, where technical skills can quickly become outdated. In this context, lifelong learning becomes essential, requiring motivation, an open-minded attitude, flexibility, and adaptability to adapt to new developments. These traits are increasingly considered in hiring decisions, with self-motivation and the ability to adapt being key factors in career growth. Despite strong technical proficiency, individuals may face career setbacks or even dismissal if they are deemed unsuitable for the team dynamic or long-term organizational goals. Finally, strong competences in areas related to cognitive abilities, promoting open innovation, and enhancing and maintain networks with external stakeholders are key in ensuring that projects are innovative and effective in solving complex problems.

The examination of current mismatches between the competencies possessed by researchers and those valued by employers exposes a significant divergence that has implications for both the academic training of researchers and the expectations of the job market. Researchers tend to self-assess their abilities in core competencies such as conducting research, self-management, and cognitive skills with a high degree of confidence, reflecting a strong foundation in academic and technical environments. However, this self-perception often does not match the competencies that employers prioritize, which include managing research, making an impact, and communicating to the public.

Employers across various sectors are looking for skills that extend beyond traditional academic research, emphasizing the need for researchers to be able to translate their work into practical applications with societal relevance. The mismatch analysis reveals that researchers are under skilled in areas that are critical for driving research success in a broader context, such as project management, open innovation, policy influence, and knowledge transfer. Conversely, researchers may overestimate their cognitive abilities, such as problem-solving and critical thinking, relative to the practical demands of their roles as perceived by employers.

The largest mismatches are observed in the areas of cognitive abilities and making an impact, indicating that researchers may need to recalibrate their self-assessment and focus on developing competencies that align with the evolving demands of the job market. The analysis also suggests that while researchers are adept at working with others, their self-assessment in this area may not fully reflect the level of collaboration and teamwork valued by employers.

Despite the ongoing transformation in European doctoral education, the analysis shows that European researchers predominantly receive traditional training, working independently within narrow disciplinary confines. The lag in doctoral training relative to evolving needs is evident from significant gaps researchers present in several areas. These gaps, with few exceptions, are evident whether we look at the self-assessment scores of researchers or consider the qualitative insights from academic, third-sector, and industry experts.

Competency gaps are primarily explained by the challenges faced by HEIs in effectively integrating appropriate training into doctoral programs. One major challenge is the strong resistance to incorporating programs necessary for developing new competencies, including both transversal skills and training related to Open Science principles. This resistance is reflected in either the absence of such training from the programs or a lack of engagement from researchers even when these programs are included. Additionally, a significant challenge is ensuring that the training is effective and assessing the development of transversal skills.

However, there is evidence that HEIs are increasingly adopting innovative strategies to address these issues. One of the most effective strategies is the implementation of Industrial Doctoral programs, where academic and industry partners coordinate research projects. These programs provide students with both expertise and practical experience, facilitating their transition to industry by expanding their networks and demonstrating their skills in real-world contexts. Such collaborations have been successful in creating job opportunities and aligning doctoral skills with industry needs.

Finally, to assess the impact of transversal skills training, universities are increasingly incorporating novel approaches such as engaging with stakeholders and monitoring researchers career progress to ensuring that researchers' competencies align with industry expectations.

The predictive analysis of researchers' and employers' perspectives on the evolution of research competencies over the next five years presents a nuanced view of the research landscape. It is evident that the value placed on certain skills is expected to shift, with a general trend towards the increasing importance of impact-driven, collaborative, and technology-supported competencies. The anticipated decline in the importance of traditional cognitive and self-management skills suggests a reconfiguration of the researcher's role, where advanced technologies and institutional support systems play a more significant part in the research process. For example, this could imply a more collaborative approach to problem-solving and a reliance on collective expertise rather than individual cognitive skill. It also suggests that researchers anticipate more robust support structures that alleviate the need for intense focus on personal management skills.

The data indicates that young researchers are preparing for a future where making a tangible societal impact, managing interdisciplinary projects, and navigating the complexities of a technology-rich environment are paramount. The growing emphasis on skills such as science communication, policy influence, and societal engagement reflects a broader expectation for research to address real-world problems and contribute to public discourse.

From an employer's perspective, the expectation of a general decrease in the importance of several competencies over the next five years highlights the need for adaptable and multifaceted training programs. This aligns with the necessity for continuous dialogue

between researchers and employers to ensure that the competencies developed are in sync with evolving market demands.

The emergence of new competencies such as Advanced Digital Skills - AI, Quality Management, and Green Skills, among others, underscores the importance of integrating these skills into current training programs. These competencies reflect the transformative potential of AI, the need for high-quality research outputs, and the global shift towards sustainability.

In conclusion, the research environment is heading towards a more impact-driven, collaborative, and technologically advanced era. To thrive in this changing landscape, young researchers must be proactive in developing the competencies that will be most in demand. HEIs must also play their part by providing the necessary training and support to bridge any potential skill gaps. By doing so, the HEI can ensure that the next generation of researchers is well-prepared to contribute effectively to the challenges and opportunities that lie ahead.

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APPENDIX A

INTERVIEW GUIDELINES – QUESTIONS FOR ACADEMIA

Introduction and Background (note is this block for every typology of interviewees? Then we added third sector too)

12. Can you please start by introducing yourself, your current role, and your affiliation with academia or industry/third sector?
13. What insights can you provide about the academic and professional journey of PhD graduates in your field?

Transversal Skills Importance and Identification (note is this block for every typology of interviewees?)

14. From your perspective, what transversal skills do you believe are most critical for PhD students as they prepare for careers in today's workforce (inside and outside the academia)?
15. Could you share instances where you've observed these transversal skills making a significant difference in the career trajectories of PhD graduates?

Academic Environment and Transversal Skills: (note is this block only for academia interviewees?)

16. How can higher education institutions ensure that the transversal skills are effectively integrated with the mskills upon completion of their programs?
17. Can you share examples of innovative approaches or successful initiatives/trainings aimed at enhancing transversal skills development for Ph.D. students?
18. What challenges or gaps have you observed in the current provision of transversal skills training for Ph.D. students?
19. Are there specific transversal skills that you believe are often overlooked in Ph.D. programs, and if so, what are they?
20. What methods or tools do you recommend for assessing and measuring the effectiveness of transversal skills training programs for Ph.D. students?
21. What are the transversal skills you believe are most valued in academic career jobs? For instance, what skills you believe are most valued when hiring a post-doc researchers?

Industry (or Third Sector) Expectations and Transversal Skills: (note is this block only for industry/third sector interviewees?)

22. Do you believe early career researchers and PhD students applying in your job are adequately equipped with the transversal skills necessary in a non-academic careers?
23. Moving to the industry side, what are some of the key transversal skills that employers in your sector value when hiring PhD graduates? In other words, how have you seen PhD graduates' transversal skills facilitate the transition from academia to industry?
24. Can you provide examples of scenarios where strong transversal skills have set candidates apart during the hiring process or subsequent career growth?

Future Trends and Transversal Skills: (note is this block for every typology of interviewees?)

25. As industries, research and third sector fields evolve, from your perspective, which transversal skills do you foresee becoming even more crucial for the success of PhD graduates in the next 5-10 years? And Why?
 26. Considering these anticipated changes, what advice would you give to current PhD students to ensure their transversal skills remain relevant and adaptable?
 27. In conclusion, in general can you list in your opinion the professions which will be the most requested in future jobs market?
-

Back Up QUESTIONS related future trends:

18. With the rise of automation and technological advancements, how do you envision transversal skills complementing technical expertise in ensuring the effectiveness of PhD graduates in their roles? Are there specific transversal skills that could help bridge this gap?
19. As remote work and virtual collaboration become increasingly prevalent, which transversal skills do you believe will be most essential for PhD graduates to effectively navigate and excel in these new work environments?
20. Interdisciplinary projects and cross-functional teams are becoming more common. How do you anticipate transversal skills aiding PhD graduates in embracing diverse perspectives and collaborating effectively in such dynamic environments?
21. With the growing emphasis on sustainability, ethics, and societal impact, do you think certain transversal skills, such as ethical decision-making and social responsibility, will gain prominence in shaping the careers of PhD graduates?
22. Communication channels are rapidly diversifying, including social media, podcasts, and online platforms. How might the evolution of communication methods influence the communication-related transversal skills that PhD graduates should develop?
23. The ability to continuously learn and adapt is becoming a career-long necessity. How can cultivating transversal skills like resilience, adaptability, and a growth mindset empower PhD graduates to embrace lifelong learning and stay relevant in their fields?
24. In an increasingly globalized world, where cross-cultural interactions are commonplace, which transversal skills do you think will enable PhD graduates to effectively navigate cultural differences and work successfully in international contexts?
25. As AI and machine learning technologies advance, do you anticipate any specific transversal skills becoming pivotal for PhD graduates in areas that are traditionally associated with high-level human expertise, such as research design and complex problem-solving?
26. Beyond technical proficiency, industries are placing greater emphasis on customer experience and stakeholder engagement. How might transversal skills like empathy, customer-centric thinking, and relationship-building contribute to the success of PhD graduates in roles that involve direct interaction with stakeholders?
27. In light of these anticipated changes in the job market, what advice would you offer to current PhD students to proactively develop and refine their transversal skills to remain competitive and adaptable in their future careers?

APPENDIX B: INTERVIEW GUIDELINES - QUESTIONS FOR INDUSTRY AND THIRD SECTORS

Introduction and Background

1. Can you please start by introducing yourself, your current role, and your affiliation with academia or industry/third sector?
2. What insights can you provide about the academic and professional journey of PhD graduates in your field?

Transversal Skills Importance and Identification

3. From your perspective, what transversal skills do you believe are most critical for PhD students as they prepare for careers in today's workforce (inside and outside the academia)?
4. Could you share instances where you've observed these transversal skills making a significant difference in the career trajectories of PhD graduates?

Industry (or Third Sector) Expectations and Transversal Skills

5. Do you believe early career researchers and PhD students applying to your job positions are adequately equipped with the transversal skills necessary in a non-academic career?
6. Moving to the industry side, what are some of the key transversal skills that employers in your sector value when hiring PhD graduates? In other words, how have you seen PhD graduates' transversal skills facilitate the transition from academia to industry?
7. Can you provide examples of scenarios where strong transversal skills have set candidates apart during the hiring process or subsequent career growth?

Future Trends and Transversal Skills: (note is this block for every typology of interviewees?)

8. As industries, research and third sector fields evolve, from your perspective, which transversal skills do you foresee becoming even more crucial for the success of PhD graduates in the next 5-10 years? And Why?
9. Considering these anticipated changes, what advice would you give to current PhD students to ensure their transversal skills remain relevant and adaptable?
10. In conclusion, in general can you list in your opinion the professions which will be the most requested in future jobs market?

Back Up QUESTIONS related future trends:

28. With the rise of automation and technological advancements, how do you envision transversal skills complementing technical expertise in ensuring the effectiveness of PhD graduates in their roles? Are there specific transversal skills that could help bridge this gap?
29. As remote work and virtual collaboration become increasingly prevalent, which transversal skills do you believe will be most essential for PhD graduates to effectively navigate and excel in these new work environments?

30. Interdisciplinary projects and cross-functional teams are becoming more common. How do you anticipate transversal skills aiding PhD graduates in embracing diverse perspectives and collaborating effectively in such dynamic environments?
 31. With the growing emphasis on sustainability, ethics, and societal impact, do you think certain transversal skills, such as ethical decision-making and social responsibility, will gain prominence in shaping the careers of PhD graduates?
 32. Communication channels are rapidly diversifying, including social media, podcasts, and online platforms. How might the evolution of communication methods influence the communication-related transversal skills that PhD graduates should develop?
 33. The ability to continuously learn and adapt is becoming a career-long necessity. How can cultivating transversal skills like resilience, adaptability, and a growth mindset empower PhD graduates to embrace lifelong learning and stay relevant in their fields?
 34. In an increasingly globalized world, where cross-cultural interactions are commonplace, which transversal skills do you think will enable PhD graduates to effectively navigate cultural differences and work successfully in international contexts?
 35. As AI and machine learning technologies advance, do you anticipate any specific transversal skills becoming pivotal for PhD graduates in areas that are traditionally associated with high-level human expertise, such as research design and complex problem-solving?
 36. Beyond technical proficiency, industries are placing greater emphasis on customer experience and stakeholder engagement. How might transversal skills like empathy, customer-centric thinking, and relationship-building contribute to the success of PhD graduates in roles that involve direct interaction with stakeholders?
 37. In light of these anticipated changes in the job market, what advice would you offer to current PhD students to proactively develop and refine their transversal skills to remain competitive and adaptable in their future careers?
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